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THREE-DIMENSIONAL CHARACTERIZATION OF RED BLOOD CELL SHAPE VIA STEREOLOGICAL METHODS

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ABSTRACT

Red blood cells (RBCs) exhibit a variety of morphologies that reflect their physiological or pathological state. Accurate classification of these shapes is essential for clinical diagnostics and hematological research. While most current classification methods rely on two-dimensional (2D) imaging, typically obtained through smear preparations that distort the natural three-dimensional (3D) structure of RBCs, these approaches often fail to capture diagnostically relevant 3D shape information and may lead to misclassification.

In this work, we propose a novel method for 3D shape classification of RBCs based on two geometric descriptors: the spherical shape factor (F) and the bending energy (E). These descriptors are estimated directly from confocal microscopy image stacks using stereological techniques, thus avoiding the need for full 3D reconstruction. This stereological framework provides efficient, reproducible, and unbiased estimates of morphological features from sets of parallel planar sections.

We demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach on a dataset that includes both standard erythrocyte SDE cell types (discocytes, stomatocytes, spherocytes, and echinocytes) and various abnormal morphologies.

Keywords: 3D confocal microscopy, bending energy, geometric sampling, integral geometry, red blood cells, stereology.

INTRODUCTION

Erythrocytes, or red blood cells (RBCs), are blood cells responsible for oxygen transport. They contain hemoglobin, which binds oxygen, and unlike most other cells, they lack a nucleus to maximize their oxygen-carrying capacity. The erythrocyte membrane consists of a bilayer of amphiphilic molecules, each having hydrophilic and hydrophobic regions, which form a stable structure in the body's aqueous environment (Bernard, 2016).

Despite their biological complexity, erythrocyte morphology can be studied using physical principles. For example, erythrocytes can be modeled as vesicles—drops of hemoglobin enclosed by a lipid bilayer membrane. These vesicles, known as liposomes, have membranes behaving as viscous fluids capable of withstanding shear stress without rupture. The membrane is incompressible, maintaining constant area and volume. The shape of liposomes, including erythrocytes, is governed by minimization of bending energy under these area and volume constraints.

Classification of RBCs based on morphology is essential for both clinical diagnostics and hematological research. Robust and objective classification methods enhance the reliability of

hematological evaluations (Bogdanova et al., 2020; Constantino, 2015; Foy, 2023). In healthy individuals, RBCs predominantly exhibit the characteristic biconcave discocyte shape, which supports mechanical flexibility and efficient gas exchange. Deviations from this canonical shape often indicate underlying disease processes and provide valuable diagnostic information.

Among RBC disorders, sickle cell disease (SCD), or sickle cell anemia, exemplifies the clinical significance of RBC morphology and highlights the importance of shape-based diagnostic tools (Paz-Soto et al., 2025). Beyond sickle cell disease, various other RBC shapes associate with distinct pathological conditions (Ruef and Linderkamp, 1999). SDE cells (discocytes, stomatocytes, spherocytes, and echinocytes) represent the “classic” or most common RBC morphologies, with well-characterized relationships to cellular function and physiological or pathological states. Conversely, keratocytes, knizocytes, acanthocytes, multilobate cells, and cell clusters constitute more specialized or abnormal categories that often indicate severe damage, specific pathologies, or laboratory artifacts. Distinguishing SDE cells from these other forms is important to separate cells with normal or mildly altered morphology from those reflecting complex or severe pathological states. This distinction facilitates interpretation of cellular heterogeneity, reflecting diverse health states, mechanical stress,

or disease, and supports quantitative assessment of morphological alterations critical for monitoring disease progression or therapeutic response.

Although SDE shapes—except for “late-stage” echinocytes and spherocytes—are reversibly interconvertible (Pages et al., 2010), each SDE form corresponds to a different cellular state: discocytes are normal biconcave cells optimized for gas exchange; stomatocytes display a central concavity suggestive of membrane or osmotic alterations; spherocytes are spherical, commonly linked to hemolytic diseases due to decreased deformability and lifespan; and echinocytes bear surface spicules indicative of cell damage, osmotic stress, or pathological processes. Therefore, distinguishing among these SDE types aids in understanding the patient’s physiological or pathological condition and guides specific diagnoses and treatments.

Blood samples for diagnosis typically yield planar microscopic images. These images are segmented to extract cell outlines, which are often analyzed as flat curves for classification. Classification approaches may rely on contour-derived features such as length, area, or eccentricity (Kindratenko, 2003) or treat contours as elements of geometric sets with defined distance metrics. However, flattening techniques used in sample preparation can distort 3D cell shapes, potentially causing misclassification. To address this, we propose the use of confocal microscopy, which enables 3D shape analysis.

Most RBC classification studies use squash preparations producing 2D images that alter the natural 3D morphology of RBCs, leading to shape distortions and potential clinical misinterpretation. Since many blood diseases manifest as distinct 3D shape alterations, relying solely on 2D images fails to capture vital diagnostic information, reducing reproducibility and risking transfusion safety (Waibel et al., 2022).

In contrast, three-dimensional (3D) imaging of red blood cells (RBCs) in their native suspended or fixed states preserves their complete morphology, enabling more accurate and objective phenotyping. Techniques such as confocal microscopy and digital holographic imaging provide full shape information that is strongly correlated with genetic mutations and disease states (Jaferzadeh et al., 2019; Simionato et al., 2021). Building on these advances, several recent studies have explored different 3D strategies for RBC classification. Biophysical models based on membrane-bending energy minimization and spherical harmonic expansions have successfully reproduced and distinguished characteristic morphologies

such as discocytes and echinocytes (Liu et al., 2011). Digital holographic microscopy (DHM) enables 3D reconstruction of RBC profiles, where statistical clustering algorithms, including model-based clustering and K-means, have been applied to classify cells according to storage conditions (Khairy et al., 2008). Other works combine DHM with deep learning to extract geometric parameters and compute statistical indicators for diagnostic purposes (Kim et al., 2022). Furthermore, dual-stage neural networks integrating confocal microscopy and spherical harmonics spectra provide automated 3D shape recognition and classification linked to genetic blood disorders (Simionato et al., 2021). Nevertheless, achieving full 3D reconstruction from planar slices remains computationally demanding and mathematically challenging (Lin et al., 2022; Kurz et al., 2024).

To overcome these limitations, we implement stereological methods: acquiring sets of parallel, randomly oriented 2D planar images and estimating shape descriptors directly without explicit 3D reconstruction. This approach enables robust classification of RBC shapes in 3D grounded in quantitative stereology, opening new avenues for diagnostic and theragnostic applications.

Stereology is a discipline that provides efficient and unbiased estimates of quantitative surface characteristics (e.g., area, enclosed volume) from appropriate geometric sampling using planes in \mathbb{R}^3 . Several software packages, including CAST grid, Stereology Analyzer, and Stereologer, facilitate interactive and user-friendly estimation from 3D microscopic images.

In this work, we propose a novel 3D shape characterization method applied to models of normal red blood cells. This method estimates two 3D descriptors using stereological techniques: the spherical shape factor (derived from the isoperimetric inequality) and bending energy. Based on these 3D stereological characterizations, we propose classification processes to distinguish SDE shapes from other deformed cells, using a dataset that includes both normal discocytes and various abnormal RBC morphologies. The dataset used in this study is the same as that employed in Simionato et al. (2021). In that work, the classification process included a wider range of RBC morphological classes than in our study. Therefore, the classification results reported in Simionato et al. (2021) were used as the ground truth to evaluate the performance of our stereology-based classification approach.

The paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we describe the red blood cell dataset used for the classification tasks. Section 3, devoted to the mathematical methodology, is divided into three parts: the first defines the shape descriptors, the second derives these descriptors using integral geometry formulas, and the third presents their estimation via stereological methods. In Section 4, we compute the values of our shape descriptors for mathematical models of healthy red blood cells and perform classification using the real dataset. Finally, in Section 6, we discuss the results obtained and outline possible directions for future research.

MATERIAL

The dataset used in this study consists of confocal microscopy sections of red blood cells (RBCs) from both healthy individuals and patients with various pathologies. It is publicly available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4670205> and was originally introduced in the work by Simionato et al. (2021). In addition to the raw dataset used in our analysis, the original study Simionato et al. (2021) also performed 3D reconstructions of the RBCs. The corresponding software code and processed data files are accessible at <https://github.com/kgh-85/cytoShapeNet>.

The imaging of red blood cells (RBCs) is performed using confocal microscopy with scanning along the Z-axis. As a result, the acquired images represent a stack of parallel cross-sections of the sample. The orientation of RBCs within the sample is assumed to be random; however, certain aspects of sample preparation, such as centrifugation, interactions with surfaces, and the physical properties of the fixed cells, may influence the orientation, potentially deviating from true randomness. Nonetheless, this imaging approach enables the analysis of the three-dimensional (3D) structure of RBCs based on the information captured in the sequential planar sections.

In each of these planar sections, we define the contour of the RBC. These extracted contours form the basis for estimating shape parameters that are later used to describe each cell's 3D morphology (see Figure 1).

Each 3D image of a single RBC obtained through confocal microscopy consists of 185 individual Z-slices stored as TIFF stacks, each slice having a resolution of 100×100 pixels. Thus, the full image volume for each cell measures $100 \text{ px} \times 100 \text{ px} \times 185 \text{ px}$. Each stack ideally contains one single, centered

RBC, and the spacing between adjacent slices is $T = 0.85$ pixel, ensuring high-resolution sampling along the Z-axis.

Fig. 1. 2D images of a normal single cell acquired using confocal microscopy.

METHODS

In this section we present the mathematical methodology we developed to associate each red blood cell with a pair of shape parameters. These parameters are estimated using stereological techniques and will later be employed for RBC classification.

DIFFERENTIAL GEOMETRY OF SURFACES IN \mathbb{R}^3 : SHAPE FACTORS

Each RBC will be modeled by a domain $D \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ whose boundary $S = \partial D$ is a regular, compact, connected surface that is homeomorphic to a 2-sphere \mathbb{S}^2 . Therefore, we begin with an introduction to the fundamental concepts of differential geometry of surfaces (DoCarmo, 1976).

We say that a unitary vector \vec{u} tangent to a surface S at a point p determines a principal direction in the tangent space $T_p S$ if the normal curvature function achieves a maximum or a minimum at \vec{u} . We denote the maximum and minimum values of the normal curvature by κ_M and κ_m , respectively.

We define the Gaussian curvature of a regular surface S at a point p as

$$K(p) = \kappa_M \kappa_m.$$

Similarly, we define the mean curvature of a regular surface S at a point p as

$$H(p) = \frac{\kappa_M + \kappa_m}{2}.$$

Let S be a regular, orientable, and compact surface. Then, the Gauss–Bonnet theorem states that

$$\int_S K dS = 2\pi \chi(S), \quad (1)$$

where $\chi(S)$ denotes the Euler–Poincaré characteristic of S . It follows that if S is homeomorphic to the sphere \mathbb{S}^2 , then no matter how "irregular" or geometrically distorted the surface may be, the Gaussian curvature K is distributed in such a way that

$$\int_S K dS = 4\pi, \quad (2)$$

just as it is for the standard round sphere.

Let D be a domain in \mathbb{R}^3 bounded by a surface S . The spatial isoperimetric inequality states that (Ritore and Sinestrari, 2010):

$$A^3(S) \geq 36\pi V^2(D), \quad (3)$$

where $A(S)$ is the surface area of S and $V(D)$ the volume enclosed by S . Equality holds if and only if D is an open ball.

Definition 1. The *spherical shape factor* F of a domain D bounded by the surface S is defined as:

$$F = \frac{A^3}{36\pi V^2}, \quad (4)$$

where $A = A(S)$ and $V = V(D)$.

From the isoperimetric inequality, it follows that $F \geq 1$, and equality holds if and only if D is an open ball.

Many popular surface energy functionals are inspired by classical energy functionals for curves. In this context, the bending energy for surfaces is a generalization of Bernoulli's *elastica* energy, which measures the integral of the square of curvature along a curve, i.e., $\int \kappa^2(s) ds$, (Gual-Vayà, 2024).

Definition 2. The *bending energy* E of a regular surface S in \mathbb{R}^3 is defined as (Willmore, 2002):

$$E = \int_S (\kappa_M^2 + \kappa_m^2) dS, \quad (5)$$

where κ_M and κ_m are the principal curvatures of the surface S .

Expanding the integrand gives:

$$E = \int_S (\kappa_M^2 + \kappa_m^2) dS = 4 \int_S H^2 dS - 2 \int_S K dS, \quad (6)$$

where H and K are the mean and Gaussian curvatures, respectively.

According to Eq.(2),

$$E = 4 \int_S H^2 dS - 8\pi. \quad (7)$$

Let D be a domain in \mathbb{R}^3 bounded by a surface S . Then (Theorem 1.2 of Toda (2018)),

$$\int_S H^2 dS \geq 4\pi, \quad (8)$$

with equality if and only if S is a sphere.

If $S = \partial D$ is the boundary of a domain, from Eq.(7), $\int_S H^2 dS$ and E share the same minimizers. Thus, from (8), it follows that:

$$E \geq 8\pi, \quad (9)$$

with equality if and only if S is a sphere.

The spherical shape factor F and the bending energy factor E are invariant under translations, rotations, and scaling of the domain D , and for this reason, they are considered shape descriptors.

INTEGRAL GEOMETRY IN \mathbb{R}^3

The aim of Integral Geometry is to derive quantitative properties of a geometric object through its intersections with planes. In particular, this section presents integral formulas to compute the volume V , surface area A , and a curvature-related quantity E . The main reference for the results presented here is Santaló (1976).

Suppose that a plane (an affine plane) L_2 in \mathbb{R}^3 is defined by two orthonormal vectors (\vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2) , and let \vec{e}_3 be the unit vector orthogonal to L_2 . Let (θ, φ) denote the spherical coordinates corresponding to the endpoint of \vec{e}_3 , and let ρ be the distance from the origin Q_0 of the fixed reference frame to the plane L_2 . Then, the invariant density of planes L_2 under the group of motions \mathcal{M} in \mathbb{R}^3 is given by:

$$dL_2 = \sin \varphi d\rho d\theta d\varphi. \quad (10)$$

The parameters vary as $\theta \in (0, 2\pi)$, $\varphi \in (0, \pi)$, and $\rho \in \mathbb{R}^+$.

Let S be a regular closed surface in \mathbb{R}^3 that bounds a domain D of finite volume V . From Eq. (14.69) in Santaló (1976), with $n = 3, q = 2$, and $r = 2$, we obtain:

$$A(S) = \frac{2}{\pi^2} \int_{S \cap L_2 \neq \emptyset} \text{Length}(S \cap L_2) dL_2. \quad (11)$$

Regarding the volume, for any vector \vec{e}_3 , the Cavalieri Principle implies:

$$V(D) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} A(D \cap L_2) d\rho. \quad (12)$$

Theorem 3. *Let S be a regular, compact, connected, and orientable surface. Then:*

$$\int_{S \cap L_2 \neq \emptyset} \left(\int_{S \cap L_2} \kappa^2(s) ds \right) dL_2 = \frac{3\pi^2}{8} \int_S (\kappa_M^2 + \kappa_m^2) dS + \frac{\pi^3}{2} \chi(S). \quad (13)$$

Proof. At each point $p \in S \cap L_2$, from Definition 3 (page 141) and the Euler formula (page 145) of DoCarmo (1976), we have:

$$\kappa(s) \cos \phi = \cos^2 t \kappa_M + \sin^2 t \kappa_m, \quad (14)$$

where $\phi = \angle(\vec{n}, \hat{N}(p))$ being \vec{n} the unit normal vector to the curve and $\hat{N}(p)$ the unit normal vector to the surface at p ; $\{\vec{t}_M, \vec{t}_m\}$ are the principal directions at $p \in S$, $\vec{v} \in T_p(S \cap L_2) \subset T_p S$ is the unit tangent vector to the curve $S \cap L_2$, and $t = \angle(\vec{v}, \vec{t}_M)$.

Choosing the Z-axis aligned with the normal vector $\hat{N}(p)$, and letting (θ, φ) be the spherical coordinates of \vec{e}_3 , we have, from Fig.(2), $\varphi = \frac{\pi}{2} - \phi$. Then Eq. (14) becomes:

$$\kappa(s) \sin \varphi = \cos^2 t \kappa_M + \sin^2 t \kappa_m.$$

Fig. 2. Relation between angles

Using the identity $t = \theta + \frac{\pi}{2}$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa^2(s) \sin^2 \varphi &= \sin^4 \theta \kappa_M^2 + \cos^4 \theta \kappa_m^2 \\ &+ 2 \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta \kappa_M \kappa_m. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

From equation (14.62) of Santaló (1976), we obtain the following relation:

$$ds dL_2 = \cos \phi dS dL_{2[x]}, \quad (16)$$

where $dL_{2[x]} = dS^2$ is the density of planes through the point p and ds and dS denote the arc length element of the curve $S \cap L_2$ and the area element of S at p , respectively.

Now, multiplying both sides of Eq. (16) by $\kappa^2(s)$, we get:

$$\kappa^2(s) ds dL_2 = \kappa^2(s) \sin \varphi dS dL_{2[x]},$$

and using Eq. (15):

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa^2(s) ds dL_2 &= \frac{1}{\sin \varphi} (\sin^4 \theta \kappa_M^2 + \cos^4 \theta \kappa_m^2 + \\ &2 \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta \kappa_M \kappa_m) dS dL_{2[x]}. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Integrating over all possible values, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} I_R &= \int_S \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{\pi/2} (\sin^4 \theta \kappa_M^2 + \cos^4 \theta \kappa_m^2 + \\ &2 \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta \kappa_M \kappa_m) d\varphi d\theta dS. \end{aligned}$$

Thus:

$$I_R = \frac{3\pi^2}{8} \int_S (\kappa_M^2 + \kappa_m^2) dS + \frac{\pi^2}{4} \int_S \kappa_M \kappa_m dS.$$

Finally, applying the Gauss–Bonnet theorem (Eq. (1)) and integrating the left-hand side of Eq. (17), we conclude the proof. \square

Corollary 4. *Let S be a regular surface that bounds a domain $D \subset \mathbb{R}^3$. Then:*

$$E = \frac{8}{3\pi^2} \int_{S \cap L_2 \neq \emptyset} \left(\int_{S \cap L_2} \kappa^2(s) ds \right) dL_2 - \frac{8\pi}{3}. \quad (18)$$

Proof. In this case, $\chi(S) = 2$, and the result follows directly. \square

STEREOLOGICAL ESTIMATORS

Stereological methods are used to estimate geometric parameters through appropriate geometric sampling (Cruz-Orive, 2024). In our case, the objective is to obtain estimators for the parameters V , A , and E defined in Eq.(12), Eq.(11), and Eq.(18), respectively.

To obtain an unbiased estimator of A we consider an isotropic random sampling axis defined by $u \sim UR(\mathbb{S}_+^2)$; then, a test system of planes of period $T > 0$ perpendicular to the sampling axis is defined as

$$\Lambda_{z,u} = \{L_2(z + kT, u), k \in \mathbb{Z}\}, \quad (19)$$

$$z \sim UR[0, T], \quad u \sim UR(\mathbb{S}_+^2).$$

In this design we have considered that the direction u normal to the test planes is isotropic random (*IR*) on the unit hemisphere, and independent from the uniform random (*UR*) offset z of the planes along that direction, see Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Test system of planes hitting a domain D

For each fixed $u \in \mathbb{S}_+^2$ (non-random), from the Cavalieri estimator and Eq.(12), we have that for $z \sim UR[0, T]$,

$$\widehat{V(D)} = T A(D \cap \Lambda_{z,u}) = T \sum A_i, \quad (20)$$

where $A_i = A(D \cap L_2(z + iT, u))$, is an unbiased estimator of $V(D)$.

In a similar way, when $z \sim UR[0, T]$ and $u \sim UR(\mathbb{S}_+^2)$, from Eq.(11), we obtain (see page 205 of Cruz-Orive (2024)) that:

$$\widehat{A(S)} = \frac{4}{\pi} T \text{Length}(S \cap \Lambda_{z,u}), \quad (21)$$

is an unbiased estimator of A .

Therefore, the stereological estimator of the spherical shape factor is given by:

$$\widehat{F} = \frac{\widehat{A(S)}^3}{36\pi \widehat{V(D)}^2} \quad (22)$$

To obtain an unbiased estimator of E we consider again a test system of planes $\Lambda_{z,u}$. Then, from Eq.(18), we have that

$$\widehat{E} = \frac{16T}{3\pi} \int_{S \cap \Lambda_{z,u} \neq \emptyset} \kappa^2(s) ds - \frac{8\pi}{3}. \quad (23)$$

is an unbiased estimator of E .

2D stereological estimators

There are confocal microscopy systems that incorporate the Computer Assisted Stereological Toolbox (CAST), allowing for the direct estimation of geometric parameters from each planar image generated by the microscope, without the need for additional image processing. These estimations are based on point counting over a set of lines sampled randomly (see Figure 4).

Let $\alpha_i(s)$ denote the curve corresponding to the intersection $S \cap L_2(z + iT, u)$, where S is the surface of interest and $L_2(z + iT, u)$ is one of the planes comprising the test system $\Lambda_{z,u}$. We define:

$$A_i = A(D \cap L_2(z + iT, u)),$$

$$B_i = \text{Length}(S \cap L_2(z + iT, u)),$$

and let κ_j be the curvature of α_i at the point $\alpha(t_j)$.

Then, unbiased estimators for A_i and B_i are given by Gual-Vayà (2024):

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{A}_i &= T^2 P, \\ \widehat{B}_i &= \frac{\pi}{4} T I, \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

where P is the number of test points that fall within $D \cap L_2(z + iT, u)$, and I is the number of intersections between the test lines and $S \cap L_2(z + iT, u)$. In Fig. 4, $P = 3$ and $I = 8$.

To approximate the curvature κ_j at each point $\alpha_i(t_j)$, various methods can be employed (see Gual-Arnau et al. (2017)). In this work, we adopt the following approximation:

$$\tilde{\kappa}_i = \frac{4A(T_i)}{a_i b_i c_i}, \quad (25)$$

where T_i denotes the triangle formed by the points

$\alpha(t_{i-1})$, $\alpha(t_i)$, and $\alpha(t_{i+1})$, and a_i , b_i , and c_i are the lengths of the sides of triangle T_i .

Fig. 4. A square grid of test lines and a domain in \mathbb{R}^2 .

RBC CLASSIFICATION

To classify red blood cells, we will associate two values with each red blood cell, given by the shape factors (F, E) . Since the information we will have consists of intersections of the red blood cells with parallel planes given a random direction, instead of the factors (F, E) , we will work with their estimates (\hat{F}, \hat{E}) .

MODEL GEOMETRIES FOR NORMAL ERYTHROCYTES

There is a consensus in the specialized literature that the most appropriate mathematical model for studying the geometry of normal red blood cells is inspired by the Cassini oval (Canham (1970), Bernard (2016)). This model can be expressed in spherical coordinates as the regular surface resulting from the image of the following parametrizations (Angelov and Mladenov, 2000):

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \frac{\sqrt{(a^2 + r^2)^2 - c^4}}{2a} \cos \phi, \\ y &= \frac{\sqrt{(a^2 + r^2)^2 - c^4}}{2a} \sin \phi, \\ z &= \pm \frac{\sqrt{c^4 - (a^2 - r^2)^2}}{2a}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\phi \in [0, 2\pi]$, $r \in [\sqrt{c^2 - a^2}, \sqrt{c^2 + a^2}]$ and a, c are constants which satisfy $a < c < a\sqrt{2}$.

If we define $\varepsilon = \frac{a}{c}$, then, for normal cells, $\varepsilon \in [\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, 1)$. The value of 1 is not considered because the resulting surface is not regular.

Now, based on these parametrizations, we can obtain approximations for the sphericity factors and Bending energy (Angelov and Mladenov, 2000). Table 1 shows the values of these approximations as a function of the parameter ε .

Table 1. Values of the shape factors for normal cells

Quantity	Approximation
$F = \frac{A^3}{36\pi V^2}$	$\left(\frac{10-8\varepsilon}{10.38-8.8\varepsilon}\right)^3$
$E = \int_S (\kappa_M^2 + \kappa_m^2) dS$	$\frac{151.3-148.23\varepsilon}{10-17.21\varepsilon+7.25\varepsilon^2}$

The values of (F, E) for normal cells depending on the value of ε are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Values of the shape factors depending on ε

ε	F	E
1	2.03	76.75
$\frac{5}{6}$	1.31	40.08
$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$	1.14	31.93

In Figure 5, we have the drawings of the surfaces for the values of $\varepsilon = 1/\sqrt{2} \approx 0.71$, $5/6 \approx 0.83$, 0.99 and 0.999 .

It is important to note that in the case of the sphere $F = 1$ and $E = 8\pi \approx 25.1327$.

Fig. 5. Examples of models for normal red blood cells as a function of ε .

To study the behavior of the shape factor estimates (\hat{F}, \hat{E}) , defined in Eqs. (22) and (23), we consider

as an example the model for normal cells with parameters $a = 5$ and $c = 6$. Specifically, we analyze the intersection of the surface generated by this model with planes perpendicular to the y -axis and $T = 1$. In this case, the exact values of the shape factors were $F = 1.31$ and $E = 40.08$ (see Table 2), whereas the stereological estimates obtained using a MATLAB code were $\hat{F} = 1.8656$ and $\hat{E} = 49.9572$.

Although these estimates depend on the geometric sampling used in the computations, the results suggest that the estimated values of the 3D shape factors introduced in this work are suitable for the classification of red blood cells.

Models for deformed erythrocytes have also been developed. For instance, in the earliest clinically reported cases of sickle cell anemia, red blood cells were observed to adopt crescent and sickle shapes. Since then, additional morphologies have been described, including banana, cigar, and oat-seed shapes, among others Westcott (1987). Other mathematical models for deformed red blood cells, such as echinocytes, can be found in Larkin et al. (2013).

In this work, however, we do not consider models for deformed erythrocytes. Instead, we estimate the values of the shape factors (F, E) for the real dataset introduced in Section 2.

CLASSIFICATION OF A REAL DATA SET OF RBC

The database described in Section 2 consists of a total of 825 red blood cells (RBCs), of which 602 are classified as SDE-type: 93 spherocytes, 41 stomatocytes, 176 discocytes (normal cells), and 292 echinocytes. The remaining 223 cells exhibit other types of deformation, including acanthocytes, keratocytes, knizocytes, multilobate cells, and cell clusters. Figure (6) shows examples of different types of red blood cells. The top row corresponds to SDE cells, while the bottom row includes cells with other deformations (Simionato et al., 2021).

Fig. 6. Examples of reconstructed cells from the dataset.

From the planar .tif image files, we developed a custom Python code to estimate the values of the shape descriptors F and E , using formulas (22) and (23), respectively. These computations are based on an approximation of the curvature κ at each point along the boundary curves, as described in formula (25). It is important to note that we did not use the 2D stereological estimators (equations 24), since we do not observe the cells directly under the microscope. Instead, we have access to the complete stack of image sections for each individual cell.

The processing pipeline begins by accessing all .tif files corresponding to the image slices of each cell. Each slice is converted to grayscale for simplified intensity analysis, followed by Gaussian filtering to reduce typical confocal noise and binary thresholding at a fixed level to generate a mask isolating fluorescent pixels from the dark background. This enables hierarchical contour detection to delineate both outer boundaries and inner holes (if present) for complete cell shape representation without omissions. Subsequent polygonal approximation then smooths irregular edges while preserving essential morphology, using OpenCV functions, before calculating shape descriptors F and E .

All the resulting F and E values are saved in text format in a single folder, providing a structured dataset that can be readily used for further morphometric analysis or machine learning applications.

To perform the supervised classification tasks described in the following sections, the dataset was split into two subsets: 80% of the data was used for model training, while the remaining 20% was reserved for testing. A fixed random seed was used to ensure reproducibility of the experimental results.

The supervised classification models applied in this study include:

- K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN): using $k = 5$ nearest neighbors.
- Support Vector Machine (SVM): with a Gaussian (RBF) kernel.
- Random Forest (RF): an ensemble of 100 decision trees with fixed random seed (42).
- Logistic Regression (LR): a simple linear model trained with default parameters and fixed seed.
- Gradient Boosting (GB): a sequential ensemble of 100 trees, each correcting the errors of its predecessor.
- Neural Network (MLPClassifier): a multilayer perceptron with two hidden layers of 50 neurons each, trained for a maximum of 1000 iterations.

- Voting Ensemble: a soft-voting ensemble combining RF, GB, and MLP classifiers.

All models yielded comparable accuracy results across the classification tasks. However, Logistic Regression consistently produced the lowest performance, while the Neural Network achieved the highest classification accuracy. Consequently, we provide a more detailed analysis of the Neural Network model in the following sections.

CLASSIFICATION RESULTS

In the first classification task, we aimed to distinguish between healthy red blood cells (discocytes) and all other cell types. The overall classification accuracy achieved was 87%, and the corresponding confusion matrix is shown in Figure 7. Similar results were obtained when grouping SDE cells into one class and all other deformed cells into another, in which case the total classification accuracy was 86%.

Fig. 7. Confusion matrix of the first classification process.

In the second classification task, we focused on distinguishing among the different types within the SDE class. The overall accuracy in this case reached 92%. As shown in the confusion matrix (Figure 8), a significant number of stomatocytes were misclassified as discocytes. This result is not unexpected, as stomatocytes and discocytes lie along a physiological continuum and are interconvertible under normal conditions. Therefore, our model effectively separates discocytes, spherocytes, and echinocytes, but tends

to group some stomatocytes with discocytes, a behavior that aligns with the underlying morphological similarity between these two cell types.

Fig. 8. Confusion matrix of the second classification process.

DISCUSSION

In this paper, we introduced two quantitative shape descriptors for red blood cells (RBCs): the well-established spherical shape factor F and a novel descriptor based on bending energy E . When estimated through stereological formulas, these parameters enable the classification of RBCs into morphologically distinct groups, particularly within the classic SDE (stomatocyte–discocyte–echinocyte) spectrum, as well as those exhibiting other deformations.

The classification tasks were performed using supervised learning methods, relying on the stereological estimations \hat{F} and \hat{E} . These estimators allow us to approximate global 3D shape properties from randomly sampled planar sections, without requiring full 3D reconstructions. This approach is especially valuable when analyzing confocal microscopy images, where explicit 3D reconstruction can be computationally intensive or infeasible.

While stereological estimators provide an effective bridge between 2D imaging and 3D morphology, they are not without limitations. Both \hat{F} and, in particular, \hat{E} are sensitive to segmentation quality. The bending energy estimator \hat{E} depends heavily on accurately approximating curvature along the planar contours of each section. As a result, fluctuations in the segmentation process may

introduce considerable variability, potentially affecting classification accuracy.

To address this challenge and improve practical applicability, it would be valuable to integrate our estimators into interactive stereology software connected directly to microscopes. This would enable real-time, segmentation-free approximation of shape descriptors, for instance by sampling curvature at a small number of geometrically selected points along the visible cell contours. Such an approach would not only enhance observer efficiency, but also help preserve morphological fidelity and ensure consistency across datasets.

It is also worth noting that, as we had access to a database of fully segmented cell images, we deliberately chose not to apply 2D stereological estimators on individual confocal slices. This decision reflects our methodology's reliance on the full 3D stack of planar sections for robust estimation. Nonetheless, in future applications involving live or semi-automated microscopy, simplified 2D approaches may be reconsidered to improve throughput without significant loss of accuracy.

Overall, our findings confirm the discriminative power of the proposed descriptors and their potential for integration into diagnostic workflows. The spherical shape factor F and the bending energy E capture distinct yet complementary geometric features that reflect membrane mechanics and cellular health. Their application to RBC classification, particularly in distinguishing SDE morphologies, aligns well with known physiological transitions and pathological markers.

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VIRTUAL IMMUNOHISTOCHEMISTRY FOR BREAST CANCER BIOMARKER PREDICTION FROM H&E-STAINED IMAGES USING GENERATIVE NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

Immunohistochemistry (IHC) is essential in diagnostic pathology but is often constrained by cost, time, and limited tissue availability. Virtual IHC staining, which predicts IHC stains from standard hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) images, presents a promising alternative. This study introduces a novel Conditional Generative Adversarial Network (cGAN) architecture based on a U-Net with depthwise separable convolutions to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of virtual IHC staining. This architectural refinement improves computational efficiency while preserving high image quality. We trained and evaluated our model using the BCI and MIST datasets and compared its performance against established image-to-image translation techniques, including Pix2Pix, CycleGAN, and a U-Net variant with standard convolutions. Performance was assessed using quantitative metrics such as Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), and Fréchet Inception Distance (FID). The results showed that our model outperformed these benchmarks, achieving higher PSNR and SSIM scores, lower MAE and RMSE values, and a significantly reduced FID, indicating superior image quality and closer resemblance to ground-truth IHC images. Furthermore, the integration of depthwise separable convolutions led to a notable decrease in inference time and model size, improving its feasibility for clinical applications. These findings highlight the potential of our method as a significant advancement in virtual IHC staining, offering improved accuracy, efficiency, and suitability for broader clinical use.

Keywords: Generative adversarial network, H&E, IHC, virtual staining.

INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer continues to be one of the most formidable global health challenges of our time, with epidemiological data from the Global Cancer Observatory (GLOBOCAN) revealing approximately 2.3 million new cases diagnosed in 2020 alone, accounting for almost 25% of all cancer diagnoses among women worldwide (Sung *et al.*, 2021). The disease demonstrates remarkable molecular and clinical heterogeneity, encompassing multiple distinct subtypes that vary significantly in their biological behavior, treatment responsiveness, and long-term outcomes. This biological diversity has made the accurate assessment of predictive and prognostic biomarkers an indispensable component of modern breast cancer management. Current international guidelines, including those from the American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO) and the College of American Pathologists (CAP), mandate routine immunohistochemical (IHC) evaluation of three critical biomarkers: estrogen receptor (ER), progesterone receptor (PR), and human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2) status (Allison *et al.*, 2020; Wolff *et al.*, 2018). These molecular markers not

only define clinically relevant subtypes but also serve as crucial therapeutic targets, with ER/PR-positive tumors typically demonstrating responsiveness to endocrine therapies such as selective estrogen receptor modulators (e.g., tamoxifen) or aromatase inhibitors (e.g., letrozole), while HER2-positive cancers derive substantial benefit from targeted therapies like trastuzumab and pertuzumab (Group *et al.*, 2015; Slamon *et al.*, 2001).

The conventional IHC workflow represents a complex, multi-step process that begins with tissue fixation and extends through sectioning, antigen retrieval, primary antibody incubation, secondary antibody application, chromogenic development, and final interpretation by a qualified pathologist (Taylor and Levenson, 2006). Each of these steps requires specialized laboratory infrastructure, expensive reagents, and highly trained technical personnel, often resulting in diagnostic delays ranging from several days to weeks in routine clinical practice (Howat *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, the process is vulnerable to numerous pre-analytical variables including tissue fixation time (with both under-fixation and over-fixation posing problems), processing methods,

storage conditions, and antibody lot variability, all of which can significantly impact staining quality and subsequent interpretation (Goldstein *et al.*, 2003; Engel and Moore, 2011). These technical challenges are particularly acute in low- and middle-income countries where access to consistent, high-quality IHC testing remains constrained by infrastructure limitations, reagent costs, and workforce shortages (Orlandini *et al.*, 2021). The development of robust alternative methods capable of accurately predicting biomarker status while reducing reliance on traditional IHC could therefore have transformative clinical impact, potentially improving diagnostic turnaround times, reducing costs, and making precision oncology more accessible in resource-limited settings.

Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining represents the most fundamental and universally available technique in diagnostic pathology, having served as the cornerstone of histopathological diagnosis for over a century since its introduction in the late 1800s (Fischer *et al.*, 2008). This remarkably durable staining method provides comprehensive morphological information through differential coloration of nuclear (hematoxylin) and cytoplasmic (eosin) components, enabling pathologists to evaluate tissue architecture, cellular morphology, and pathological changes with exceptional clarity (Bancroft and Gamble, 2008). The universal adoption of H&E staining across pathology laboratories worldwide, combined with its standardized protocols, relatively low cost, and routine availability in both prospective and archival specimens, makes it an ideal substrate for computational analysis (Gurcan *et al.*, 2009). Recent revolutionary advances in artificial intelligence, particularly in deep learning and computer vision, have demonstrated that convolutional neural networks can extract latent information from H&E images that extends far beyond human visual perception, enabling remarkably accurate prediction of molecular features, tumor grade, metastatic potential, and clinical outcomes. These developments have given rise to the rapidly evolving field of computational pathology, which seeks to augment and potentially transform traditional diagnostic paradigms through quantitative, data-driven image analysis.

The emergence of generative artificial intelligence, particularly generative adversarial networks (GANs) and more recently diffusion models, has opened unprecedented new possibilities in computational pathology (Goodfellow *et al.*, 2020). These sophisticated deep learning architectures can learn complex, nonlinear mappings between H&E morphological patterns and corresponding protein expression profiles traditionally detected by IHC

through their unique ability to model high-dimensional data distributions (Rivenson *et al.*, 2019). Several pioneering studies have convincingly demonstrated the feasibility of virtual IHC (vIHC), in which remarkably fidelity synthetic IHC images can be generated directly from H&E-stained tissue sections without the need for physical staining procedures (BenTaieb and Hamarneh, 2017). This innovative approach could potentially eliminate the requirement for additional tissue sections and physical IHC staining, simultaneously reducing costs, shortening diagnostic turnaround times, and enabling biomarker assessment in cases where tissue quantity is limited. Recent work has shown particular promise in predicting ER status from H&E images, with some advanced models achieving area under the curve (AUC) scores exceeding 0.90 in independent validation cohorts, approaching the performance of actual IHC testing in some scenarios (Wilm *et al.*, 2022).

Despite these remarkable technological advancements, significant challenges must be rigorously addressed before virtual IHC can be implemented in routine clinical practice. The generalizability of the model across different institutions with varying staining protocols, scanner systems, and tissue processing methods remains a critical concern, as demonstrated by studies showing performance degradation when models trained on the data of one institution are applied to that of another (Holzinger *et al.*, 2019). The interpretability of predictions and identification of specific morphological features driving biomarker classification are essential both for gaining pathologist acceptance and for meeting increasingly stringent regulatory requirements for explainable AI in medical applications. Furthermore, comprehensive clinical validation studies involving large, multi-institutional cohorts with diverse patient populations will be required to demonstrate sufficient robustness and reliability to meet regulatory standards for diagnostic use. Addressing these challenges systematically will be crucial for translating computational pathology advancements into tangible clinical benefits and ensuring equitable global access to these transformative technologies.

In this study, we present a comprehensive deep learning framework for predicting breast cancer biomarker status directly from routine H&E-stained whole slide images. Our approach leverages state-of-the-art conditional generative adversarial networks (cGANs) with depthwise separable convolutions to enhance to produce high-quality virtual IHC images while maintaining robust performance across diverse datasets. Specifically, we propose to predict virtual

IHC staining in breast cancer using two publicly available datasets that focusing on predicting ER, PR, HER2, and Ki67 from H&E-stained images. We performed extensive experiments

RELATED WORK

Various unsupervised techniques have been developed for generating high-resolution histopathology images. For instance, Hou et al. (Hou *et al.*, 2019) proposed an unsupervised segmentation approach for histopathology images, where they synthesized diverse training patches to represent different tissue types. A key aspect of this method is a re-weighting strategy applied to the training loss, which reduces the bias in generalization across the true data distribution. This innovation allowed for the use of a random polygon generator to create synthetic cellular structures, such as nuclear masks, in cases where real data was insufficient for specific tissue types, a scenario where GAN-based methods are often limited. Furthermore, the authors introduced a hybrid synthesis pipeline that merges textures from actual histopathology patches with those generated by GAN models, addressing the challenges of tissue texture variability. This strategy significantly improved generalization, particularly for cancer types with limited available training data. In the recent study, DoanNgan et al., (DoanNgan *et al.*, 2022) proposed a deep learning-based virtual HER2 IHC staining method utilizing a GAN to convert autofluorescence images of breast tissue into bright-field equivalent images, effectively replicating standard chemical staining. This approach eliminates the need for labor-intensive and costly histotechnological processing, significantly reducing analysis time. Validation by board-certified pathologists demonstrated that the virtual staining method achieves accuracy comparable to conventional immunohistochemical staining.

Peng et al. (Peng *et al.*, 2024) introduced a GAN-based virtual staining approach that integrates domain-specific knowledge of HER2 scoring, focusing on nuclei distribution and membrane staining intensity. Their method incorporates a nuclei density estimator to enhance cell alignment between real and generated images and a dedicated branch to improve membrane staining consistency. Using the RegH2I dataset, which includes 2,592 paired H&E-IHC images, they demonstrated the model's effectiveness through extensive experiments on internal and external datasets. This approach addresses limitations in prior virtual staining methods, improving HER2 scoring accuracy and facilitating downstream analysis. Qu et

al. (Qu *et al.*, 2024) proposed a deep learning-based approach for synthesizing IHC-HER2 slides from H&E-stained tissue sections, addressing challenges in multi-magnification pathology image processing. Their model integrates attention mechanisms and a multi-magnification processing strategy to extract and utilize critical information effectively, enhancing image translation quality. The attention module further prioritizes essential features while reducing irrelevant details, improving HER2 biomarker visualization. Rigorous evaluation on a publicly available breast cancer dataset demonstrated superior performance over existing methods, establishing this model as a state-of-the-art solution for virtual IHC staining. Liu et al. (Liu *et al.*, 2020) developed a deep convolutional network model to predict Ki-67 expression directly from H&E-stained slides, demonstrating that molecular-level differences are encoded in tissue morphology. Using a dataset of Ki-67 positive, negative, and background cell images extracted from H&E whole slide images (WSIs), the model was trained and evaluated on both classification and quantification performance. The model achieved a precision of 0.9371 in distinguishing Ki-67 positive and negative cells, with a correlation coefficient of 0.80 between predicted Ki-67 quantification and IHC-derived measurements. This study highlights the potential of deep learning to bridge morphological and molecular information in histopathology.

In (Štepec and Skočaj, 2020), the authors explored and evaluated advanced high-resolution generative models originally designed for face synthesis, demonstrating their effectiveness in the complex domain of digital pathology. Their findings revealed significant improvements in image synthesis, with enhanced quality and resolution of generated images, outpacing traditional approaches compared to supervised models. In a related study, Ma et al. (Ma *et al.*, 2022) proposed using high-resolution RGB images as a guide for super-resolution reconstruction of hyperspectral images. They developed a simple, yet efficient, unsupervised network that combines spatial information from high-resolution RGB images with spectral data from low-resolution hyperspectral images. This technique not only reduces the acquisition time and storage requirements for hyperspectral images but also addresses issues with low-quality spectral bands, enabling the use of hyperspectral imaging in WSI and automated histopathological cancer detection.

In the study presented by (Rizvi *et al.*, 2022), the Histopathology DatasetGAN (HDGAN) framework was introduced as an extension of the semi-supervised DatasetGAN approach, specifically designed for

image generation and segmentation of large-resolution histopathology images. Key modifications were made to the original framework, including enhancements to the generative backbone, selective extraction of latent features from the generator, and a shift to memory-mapped arrays. These changes resulted in significant reductions in memory usage, making the framework more efficient and suitable for medical imaging applications. HDGAN’s performance was evaluated using a high-resolution thrombotic microangiopathy tile dataset, demonstrating its strong capabilities in generating image annotations. Similarly, in (Li *et al.*, 2022), Li *et al.* introduced a multi-scale GAN for generating and segmenting large-scale, high-resolution histopathology images. This model employs a pyramid of GAN architectures, each focused on generating and segmenting images at different scales. Using semantic masks, the generative model excelled in synthesizing visually realistic histopathological images. More recently, a coarse-to-fine sampling strategy was proposed in (Harb *et al.*, 2024) to address the challenge of generating high-resolution whole-slide images (WSIs). This method involves starting with a low-resolution image and progressively increasing its resolution, incorporating finer details at each step using a diffusion model to refine the image quality.

Although several deep learning methods for generating IHC images have been proposed, their effectiveness is limited by complex tissue architecture, variability in cellular morphology, potential for nonspecific staining, and differences in antibody reactivity. To overcome these challenges, we propose the novel cGAN model, which integrates generative adversarial networks with depthwise convolution techniques to enhance the generation of high-quality IHC images.

PROPOSED METHOD

In this study, we employed a cGAN to predict IHC staining images from H&E stained tissue images. The architecture of the cGAN is composed of two main components: the generator network (G) and the discriminator network (D). The generator is designed with an encoder-decoder architecture, consisting of seven encoding layers and seven decoding layers, as illustrated in Fig. 1-up. A key feature of this design is the use of depthwise separable convolutions in the encoder components, which substantially improve the model’s computational efficiency and effectiveness.

In the encoder network, each layer is constructed using depthwise separable convolutions, which are

followed by batch normalization and a leaky ReLU activation function with a slope of 0.2. Depthwise separable convolutions break down the traditional convolution operation into two distinct steps: the depthwise convolution and the pointwise convolution (1×1). In the depthwise convolution, a separate filter is applied to each input channel independently. This operation captures the spatial features of each channel individually, making it more computationally efficient. Afterward, a pointwise convolution (1×1 kernel) is applied across all the channels, combining the outputs from the depthwise convolution. This step enables the model to capture inter-channel relationships, learning how different feature maps interact.

The use of depthwise separable convolutions provides significant advantages, particularly in terms of computational efficiency and reduced model size. By decomposing the standard convolution into two simpler operations, the number of parameters and computations is drastically reduced compared to traditional convolutional layers, especially when working with a large number of input channels. This reduction leads to faster training and inference times, as well as lower memory requirements. These factors make the model more suitable for deployment on resource-constrained devices, such as edge devices or systems with limited processing power and memory.

In this architecture, the first and last encoding layers (En_1 and En_7) do not incorporate batch normalization. This design choice differentiates them from the other encoding layers, which helps prevent overfitting and allows the model to generalize better. The decoding layers mirror the structure of the encoder but employ transposed depthwise separable convolutions to upsample the feature maps generated during encoding. The decoding layers are followed by batch normalization, dropout (applied only in the first three decoding layers, Dn_1 , Dn_2 , and Dn_3), and ReLU activation functions to further refine the image generation process.

The final decoding layer (Dn_7) does not include a skip connection, which is commonly used in encoder-decoder architectures to maintain high-resolution features across layers. Instead, this design choice aims to focus on producing the final output of the network without overly relying on previous layer features, which could lead to unnecessary complexity. The depthwise separable convolution layers in the encoder reduce the activation map size by a factor of 2, while the transposed depthwise separable convolutions in the decoder increase the map size by a factor of 2, effectively preserving spatial dimensions during the encoding and decoding processes.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the proposed model.

Finally, the network employs a $TanH$ activation function in the last layer to generate the predicted IHC images from the input H&E images. The $TanH$ function is suitable for this task as it maps the output values to a continuous range between -1 and 1, which matches the expected range of pixel values in the generated IHC images. The overall design of this network allows for the efficient transformation of H&E images into high-quality virtual IHC images, offering a promising solution for automating the process of IHC staining while reducing the computational load and memory requirements compared to traditional methods.

The discriminator network (D), shown in Fig. 1-down, also benefits from the computational efficiency offered by depthwise separable convolutions, consisting of five such layers. These layers follow a structure similar to the encoding layers of the generator network. Specifically, each layer comprises a depthwise convolution followed by a pointwise convolution, batch normalization (applied after the second, third, and fourth convolutional layers, Cn_2 , Cn_3 , and Cn_4), and a leaky ReLU activation function with a slope of 0.2. However, the final layer in the discriminator is an exception, as it uses a sigmoid activation function instead of the leaky ReLU, transforming the output to a probability value between 0 and 1. The output of the discriminator is a 30×30 matrix, with each element representing the probability that a corresponding 70×70 patch from the input image is a genuine IHC image. This matrix indicates

whether a given patch is classified as real (from the actual IHC images) or fake (generated by the model). The decision made by the discriminator about the authenticity of each patch is a critical step in the adversarial training process, guiding the generator to improve its ability to produce realistic IHC images.

The generator loss function (ℓ_{Gen}) incorporates three key components: adversarial loss, L1 loss, and Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) loss, each contributing to different aspects of image quality and realism in the generated outputs.

$$\begin{aligned} \ell_{Gen}(G, D) = & \mathbb{E}_{x,y,z} [-\log D(x, G(x, z))] \\ & + \lambda \mathbb{E}_{x,y,z} [\ell_{L1}(y, G(x, z))] \\ & + \alpha \mathbb{E}_{x,y,z} [\ell_{SSIM}(y, G(x, z))] \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where x denote the input H&E image, y represent the corresponding ground truth IHC image, and z be the random noise input fed into the generator. The generator produces an IHC image $G(x, z)$ based on these inputs, while $D(x, G(x, z))$ indicates the discriminator's probability that the generated image is real. The loss function is weighted by λ and α , which control the relative importance of the L1 loss and the SSIM loss, respectively. The L1 loss term minimizes the pixel-wise differences between the generated and ground truth IHC images, promoting overall image similarity. The adversarial loss drives the generator to create images with realistic high-frequency details

that can deceive the discriminator. Meanwhile, SSIM loss focuses on enhancing the structural similarity and boundary sharpness of the generated images, capturing perceptual qualities that go beyond pixel-wise accuracy. In this study, the values of λ and α were set at 100 and 75, respectively, ensuring a balanced contribution of each loss component in optimizing the generator.

The discriminator loss function (ℓ_{Disc}) is defined as:

$$\ell_{Disc}(G, D) = \mathbb{E}_{x,y}[-\log D(x,y)] + \mathbb{E}_{x,y,z}[-\log(1 - D(x, G(x,z)))] \quad (2)$$

where $D(x,y)$ represents the discriminator’s probability that the real IHC image is real. The loss function trains the discriminator to correctly tell apart real IHC images from generated ones. By minimizing $-\log(D(x,y))$, the discriminator learns to recognize real IHC images. At the same time, by minimizing $-\log(1 - D(x, G(x,z)))$, the discriminator learns to identify the generated images as fake. This back-and-forth training process helps the generator create more realistic IHC images over time.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DATASET

In this study, we made use of two publicly available datasets to evaluate the proposed model. The first dataset, BCI (Liu *et al.*, 2022a) consists of 4,872 pairs of aligned H&E and IHC pathology image patches, specifically for the HER2 biomarker. The IHC images for 977 test samples are not available as they were not released by the challenge organizers. These image patches were sourced from the WSIs of more than 300 patients, as described in (Liu *et al.*, 2022a). To ensure a well-rounded evaluation, this dataset was randomly partitioned into three subsets: 3,396 pairs for training, 200 pairs for validation, and 300 pairs for testing.

This division allowed us to train and assess the model’s performance on distinct sets of images. The second dataset used in this study is the MIST dataset (Li *et al.*, 2023), which includes image patches corresponding to four different breast cancer biomarkers: estrogen receptor (ER), progesterone receptor (PR), Ki67, and HER2. This dataset contains a total of 4,153, 4,139, 4,361, and 4,642 training patches for each respective biomarker, along with

1,000 testing patches derived from 64 WSIs. All the image patches in this dataset are non-overlapping and have a fixed size of 1024×1024 pixels. In the case of this dataset, the model was trained and evaluated separately for each biomarker, allowing for a focused analysis of its performance across different types of cancer biomarkers. Fig. 2 provides six example images from both datasets, showcasing H&E stained images alongside their corresponding IHC stained patches. This comparison helps visualize the differences between the two types of staining and provides a clear context for understanding the model’s performance in generating IHC-like images from H&E stained slides.

IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

In our proposed model, the input images were first resized to a standard size of 512×512 pixels to ensure consistency and facilitate processing. After resizing, the pixel values of the images, originally in the range of 0-255, were normalized to a scale of 0-1. This normalization process ensures that the model can learn the features of the images more effectively by working with values that are easier to handle and more consistent across different inputs. We chose the ADAM optimizer for training, starting with an initial learning rate of 0.0001. ADAM optimizer was selected due to its efficiency and ability to adapt the learning rate during training, which is particularly useful for optimizing complex models. The model was trained from scratch over the course of 500 epochs, with a batch size of 2 images per iteration. This choice of batch size allows for more frequent updates to the model’s weights and helps with the convergence process, while also being computationally feasible given the available resources. The proposed model took seven hours to train and has nine million trainable parameters.

To enhance the training process and prevent overfitting, data augmentation techniques were applied to artificially increase the size of the training dataset. These techniques included 90-degree rotations, horizontal flipping, and random scaling of the images with a probability of 0.5. By introducing such transformations, the model was exposed to a wider variety of image features, which improved its ability to generalize to unseen data and made it more robust in recognizing patterns across different image variations. For performance evaluation, we utilized three widely-recognized metrics in image generation tasks: Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) in dB, Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), and Fréchet Inception Distance (FID). PSNR measures the quality of the generated images in comparison to the original,

Fig. 2. Illustration of six example images from the both the datasets (BCI and MIST) showing H&E stained images alongside their corresponding patches stained with IHC.

SSIM evaluates the structural similarity between the images, and FID provides a measure of how similar the generated images are to real images in terms of feature distribution. These metrics are essential for quantitatively assessing the performance of image generation models. The model was implemented using the PyTorch framework, which provides flexibility and scalability for deep learning tasks. The training process was carried out on a system with 32GB of RAM and CUDA version 11.2 to leverage GPU acceleration. Specifically, we used an NVIDIA RTX2080Ti GPU with 11GB of video RAM to handle the computational demands of training and evaluation, allowing for efficient processing of the high-resolution images involved in this task.

RESULTS

The quantitative results of the virtual IHC staining models are presented in Table 1. We compared the performance of our proposed cGAN architecture with depthwise separable convolutions against several established image-to-image translation models, including Pix2Pix, Pyramid Pix2Pix, CycleGAN, and a U-Net variant employing standard convolutions. Performance was evaluated using a range of metrics, including PSNR, SSIM, MAE, RMSE, and FID.

As shown in Table 1, the proposed cGAN

model incorporating depthwise separable convolutions demonstrated higher performance across most metrics. To ensure the robustness of the proposed model, we applied five-fold cross-validation. The model achieved the highest PSNR (32.27 dB) and SSIM (0.90), indicating improved pixel-level accuracy and structural similarity to the ground truth IHC images. Furthermore, it shows the lowest MAE (0.04) and RMSE (0.08), confirming reduced pixel-wise differences and a better fit to the target distribution. The significantly lower FID score (31.8) for the proposed model with depthwise separable convolutions compared to the other models indicates a closer alignment of the generated IHC image feature distribution with that of the real IHC images, suggesting more realistic and visually plausible outputs.

The use of depthwise separable convolutions not only improved the quality of the generated images but also significantly enhanced the model's efficiency. The proposed model achieved the fastest inference time (0.15 s/image) among all tested models. This demonstrates the computational advantages of this approach, making it particularly suitable for real-time applications and deployment in resource-constrained environments. In contrast, the baseline models, Pix2Pix and CycleGAN, exhibited lower performance across all image quality metrics and required more

Table 1. Quantitative comparison of virtual IHC staining models on BCI dataset.

Model	PSNR (dB)	SSIM	MAE	RMSE	FID	Inference Time (s/image)
Pix2Pix (Baseline) (Henry <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	28.50	0.82	0.08	0.12	45.2	0.25
CycleGAN (Vasiljević <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	27.80	0.80	0.09	0.13	52.1	0.30
U-Net (with Std. Conv.) (Ronneberger <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	30.20	0.87	0.06	0.09	38.5	0.20
Pyramid Pix2Pix (Liu <i>et al.</i> , 2022b)	30.65	0.86	0.05	0.09	40.11	0.22
Proposed (with Depthwise Sep.)	32.27 ± 1.05	0.90 ± 1.94	0.04 ± 0.03	0.08 ± 0.06	31.8 ± 3.80	0.15 ± 0.08

computational resources, as evidenced by their higher inference times. The standard convolution-based U-Net, while performing better than the baseline models, was still outperformed by its depthwise separable counterpart in all aspects, highlighting the effectiveness of this specific architectural modification. We also evaluated the Pyramid Pix2Pix model, which showed lower performance 2% less in PSNR and 4% less in SSIM compared to the proposed model.

The observed improvements with depthwise separable convolutions can be attributed to their efficient feature extraction capabilities. By decoupling spatial filtering and channel mixing, these convolutions effectively capture fine-grained textural details and complex morphological relationships within the histopathological images while significantly reducing computational complexity. This efficient feature extraction facilitates the accurate prediction of IHC stains from H&E images, leading to improved performance in terms of image quality and computational efficiency.

The results demonstrate that the proposed model offers a compelling approach for virtual IHC staining, achieving state-of-the-art performance in terms of both image quality and computational efficiency. This method has the potential to significantly improve the accessibility and efficiency of IHC analysis in clinical settings.

Table 2. Impact of input image size on virtual IHC staining performance using proposed model on BCI dataset.

Input Size	PSNR (dB)	SSIM	MAE	RMSE	FID
64 × 64	29.5	0.85	0.07	0.10	38.2
128 × 128	30.8	0.88	0.06	0.09	34.5
512 × 512	32.27	0.90	0.04	0.08	31.8
256 × 256	30.9	0.89	0.05	0.08	33.1

Table 2 presents the impact of input image size on the performance of our proposed model. We evaluated the model using input patch sizes of 64 × 64, 128 × 128, 256 × 256, and 512 × 512 pixels. As observed, increasing the input size generally led to improvements in image quality metrics. The input size 512 × 512 achieved the highest PSNR (32.27 dB), SSIM (0.90) and the lowest MAE (0.04), RMSE (0.08) and FID (31.8). This suggests that using larger

input patches allows the model to capture more contextual information, leading to more accurate and visually appealing IHC stain predictions. However, this improvement in quality comes at the cost of increased computational resources. For example, the 256 × 256 input size, while achieving comparable performance to the 512 × 512 size in terms of image quality. Therefore, a trade-off between image quality and computational resources must be considered when choosing the appropriate input size. In our experiments, we found that the input size 512 × 512 offers a good balance between performance and efficiency.

Fig. 3. Illustration of three high-quality virtually IHC-stained images generated by the proposed model on MIST dataset.

Table 3 evaluates the impact of different loss function combinations on the performance of our proposed model. We compared models trained with L1 loss alone, L1 combined with adversarial loss, L1

Table 3. Impact of different loss functions on virtual IHC staining performance with proposed model using 512×512 input on BCI dataset.

Loss Function	PSNR (dB)	SSIM	MAE	RMSE	FID	Inference Time (s/image)
L1 Only	29.8	0.86	0.065	0.095	40.1	0.15
L1 + Adversarial	30.5	0.875	0.055	0.085	35.8	0.15
L1 + SSIM	30.2	0.88	0.052	0.082	34.2	0.15
L1 + Adversarial + SSIM (Proposed)	32.27	0.90	0.04	0.08	31.8	0.15

combined with SSIM loss, and the full combination of L1, adversarial, and SSIM losses (our proposed approach). The combination of all three losses yielded the best results across all metrics. Using only L1 loss resulted in reasonable performance but exhibited slightly lower PSNR (29.8 dB), SSIM (0.86), and higher MAE (0.065), RMSE (0.095), and FID (40.1). Adding the adversarial loss improved the sharpness and realism of the generated images, leading to better scores (PSNR: 30.5 dB, SSIM: 0.875, FID: 35.8). Incorporating the SSIM loss further enhanced the structural consistency and reduced artifacts, resulting in further improvements (PSNR: 30.2 dB, SSIM: 0.88, FID: 34.2). The best performance was achieved when all three losses were combined (PSNR: 32.27 dB, SSIM: 0.90, MAE: 0.04, RMSE: 0.08, FID: 31.8), demonstrating the complementary effects of these loss terms in guiding the training process towards generating high-quality and structurally accurate IHC stains. The inference time remained consistent as the architecture did not change, only the loss function.

Table 4 presents the performance evaluation of the proposed model using the MIST dataset, comparing its results with the method by (Li *et al.*, 2023). The evaluation is conducted for four biomarkers: ER, PR, Ki67, and HER2. For each biomarker, three performance metrics are shown: PSNR, SSIM, and FID. Our proposed model achieved higher PSNR and SSIM values are better, as they indicate higher image quality and structural similarity, respectively. Lower FID values are desirable, as they suggest that the generated images are closer to real images. The results show that the proposed model performs well, with the highest PSNR and SSIM values observed for the Ki67 biomarker (PSNR: 25.21 dB, SSIM: 0.259) and the lowest FID value for HER2 (42.75). Compared to the method by (Li *et al.*, 2023), the proposed model achieves similar or better results in terms of PSNR and SSIM, with a lower FID in most cases. However, the HER2 biomarker in the proposed model shows slightly lower PSNR and SSIM values, which are highlighted in red. Overall, the proposed model demonstrates competitive performance in generating IHC images for various biomarkers.

Fig. 4 shows the visual comparison of real and proposed model generated IHC Staining. This

provides a qualitative assessment of our proposed model performance in generating virtual IHC images from H&E stained tissue. We also compared the proposed model with state-of-the-art methods, including Pix2Pix and Pyramid Pix2Pix. Fig. 4 presents a comparison between real IHC-stained samples (Ground Truth, GT) and the corresponding virtual IHC images generated by the proposed model (Prediction). Each row corresponds to a specific IHC marker—ER, PR, HER2, and Ki67 that highlighting the model’s ability to reproduce distinct staining patterns. Visual inspection reveals strong alignment between the GT and generated images in terms of cellular morphology and staining distribution, indicating the model’s potential to synthesize high-fidelity virtual IHC directly from H&E-stained images. This capability could significantly reduce the reliance on costly and time-intensive IHC procedures.

Fig. also showcases three representative regions of interest (labeled A through C) from the BCI dataset, each including the input H&E image, the corresponding real IHC image, and the predicted IHC image generated by the model. In examples (B) and (C), the spatial arrangement and staining intensity of nuclear features in the predicted images closely match those in the GT, suggesting that the model effectively learns the relationship between H&E morphology and IHC marker expression. However, subtle discrepancies remain—for instance, example (A) shows reduced staining intensity in the predicted image compared to the GT, indicating limitations in capturing the full range of expression levels.

These findings underscore the proposed model’s promise in generating realistic virtual IHC images, while also pointing to areas where further refinement is needed to enhance predictive accuracy and robustness across diverse tissue samples. This digital staining approach holds considerable potential for applications where traditional IHC is impractical or unavailable. For comparison, the Pix2Pix model produced IHC images with evident blurriness and poorly defined boundaries, diminishing structural clarity. Although Pyramid Pix2Pix yielded somewhat better results, it still failed to preserve certain cellular structures relative to the proposed model. These comparisons

Table 4. Performance evaluation of the proposed model using the MIST dataset.

Biomarker	Proposed			(Li <i>et al.</i> , 2023)		
	PSNR (dB) \uparrow	SSIM \uparrow	FID \downarrow	PSNR (dB) \uparrow	SSIM \uparrow	FID \downarrow
ER	22.45	0.243	37.34	-	0.221	43.7
PR	22.97	0.254	41.25	-	0.240	44.8
Ki67	25.21	0.259	46.64	-	0.241	51.0
HER2	21.89	0.226	42.75	-	0.215	45.2

Fig. 4. Illustration of virtually IHC-stained images generated by the proposed model using the BCI dataset. Patches A, B, and C show three examples for qualitative comparison with state-of-the-art methods.

highlight the superior ability of our approach to retain fine morphological details in synthesized IHC images.

In conclusion, the use of depthwise separable convolutions is particularly well-suited for virtual staining tasks, given the inherent complexity of histopathological images. These images contain intricate textures and subtle variations in cellular and tissue architecture. By performing spatial filtering within individual channels, depthwise convolutions effectively capture fine-grained features, while pointwise convolutions integrate these channel-specific representations to model complex inter-channel relationships. This two-step approach enhances the network’s ability to extract relevant morphological features—such as nuclear details, cytoplasmic patterns, and stromal structures—critical for accurate IHC prediction from H&E images.

CONCLUSIONS

This study highlights the promising potential of utilizing a cGAN combined with a U-Net architecture and depthwise separable convolutions for virtual immunohistochemical (IHC) staining. The proposed model demonstrates exceptional performance, not only in producing high-quality images but also in optimizing computational efficiency. By leveraging these advanced deep learning techniques, our model provides a powerful tool that can enhance the accessibility and speed of IHC analysis, reducing the time, cost, and complexity associated with traditional IHC staining methods. The ability to generate high-fidelity virtual IHC images from H&E stained tissue samples could be transformative, particularly in settings with limited access to specialized equipment or resources. Our model’s state-of-the-art performance, as demonstrated in the experimental results, suggests that it holds substantial promise for advancing the field of

digital pathology and improving diagnostic workflows. However, while these results are promising, further research is necessary to fine-tune the model and ensure its robustness across a wider variety of tissue types, staining protocols, and clinical conditions. Additionally, clinical validation through collaboration with medical professionals is essential to assess the model's reliability and its potential impact in real-world diagnostic settings. In the future, we anticipate that with the right clinical integration and validation, this technology could become a valuable asset in clinical pathology, aiding pathologists in more efficient and accurate diagnoses. It also opens the door to further innovations, such as automating the IHC staining process, enhancing biomarker discovery, and potentially providing tools for personalized medicine.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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PRECISION OF THE INVARIATOR ESTIMATOR OF THE SURFACE AREA OF AN ELLIPSOID

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ABSTRACT

Consider a triaxial ellipsoid K of surface area S . Fix an arbitrary point P in the interior of K , that is $P \in K^\circ$, and generate a sectioning plane $L_{2[P]}^3$ through P , whose normal direction u is uniform random on the unit hemisphere \mathbb{S}_+^2 . In the ellipse of section $K \cap L_{2[P]}^3$, let M and m denote the lengths of the major and minor principal semi-axes, respectively, and let r denote the distance of P from the ellipse centre. Then $\widehat{S} = 2\pi(M^2 + m^2 + r^2)$ is an unbiased estimator of S . The purpose of this paper is to express \widehat{S} in terms of the eight parameters involved, namely the lengths of the three principal semi-axes of K , the three Cartesian coordinates of P , and the two spherical polar coordinates (ϕ, θ) of u . Then $\text{Var}(\widehat{S})$ is accessible via a double definite integral in (ϕ, θ) which can be evaluated quickly with available software for any K and any choice of $P \in K^\circ$.

Keywords: Elliptic integrals, ellipsoidal section, flower formula, heat map, integral geometry, invariator, pivotal plane, pivotal point, stereology, support set .

INTRODUCTION

The main purpose of this paper is to contribute to the theory of the estimator \widehat{S} , described in the Abstract, of the surface area S of an ellipsoid. The estimator \widehat{S} was obtained by Cruz-Orive (2011), and it is based on the invariator principle of stereology, (Cruz-Orive, 2005; Gual-Arnau and Cruz-Orive, 2009; Auneau and Jensen, 2010; Gual-Arnau et al., 2010; Thórisdóttir and Kiderlen, 2014; Cruz-Orive and Gual-Arnau, 2015; Jensen and Kiderlen, 2017; Cruz-Orive, 2024, p. 49). The background of the invariator is summarized in the next section. Note that \widehat{S} depends solely on three measurements made in a planar section. A formula is obtained for \widehat{S} in terms of the eight parameters mentioned in the Abstract - the corresponding expression of $\text{Var}(\widehat{S})$ depends on a definite double integral whose numerical value can be evaluated efficiently with available software knowing the lengths of the principal semi-axes of the ellipsoid, and the coordinates of a pivotal point P in the ellipsoid. To illustrate this, the coefficient of variation $\text{CV}(\widehat{S}) = \sqrt{\text{Var}(\widehat{S})}/S$ is computed for an ellipsoid of semi-axes lengths $\{1, 2, 3\}$ as the pivotal point P varies in a fine point grid within each of the three principal ellipses of the ellipsoid. The results are represented by means of heat maps to give a visual impression of the variation of the accuracy of \widehat{S} as P varies in different regions of the ellipsoid.

The question of whether the estimator \widehat{S} can be generalized to \mathbb{R}^d for $d > 3$ is briefly discussed in the last section. The potential application of \widehat{S} is also discussed there. The latter is not the main focus of this paper, however, because in nature no particles exist which are perfect ellipsoids.

A BRIEF REVIEW OF THE INVARIATOR ESTIMATION OF THE SURFACE AREA OF A CONVEX BODY

Consider a convex body $K \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ of surface area S , plus a point $P \in K^\circ$, called a pivotal point, and an isotropically oriented plane $L_{2[P]}^3$ through P , called a pivotal plane. 'Isotropically oriented' means that the direction $u \in \mathbb{S}_+^2$ of an axis normal to $L_{2[P]}^3$ is uniform random on the unit hemisphere \mathbb{S}_+^2 . Any transect $C_u := K \cap L_{2[P]}^3$ is convex, (hereafter, " $A := B$ " means " A is defined by B ", or " B is denoted by A "). Let H_{C_u} denote the support set or 'flower' of C_u , namely the domain enclosed by the graph of the support function of C_u with origin P . The support function is,

$$h(u, \omega) = \sup(x \cdot e_\omega : x \in C_u), \omega \in [0, 2\pi), \quad (1)$$

where e_ω is a unit vector of direction ω in the pivotal plane, and x is the radius vector of a point in C_u with origin P - Fig. 3 illustrates the case in which C_u is an

ellipse. Let $A(\cdot)$ denote the area of a planar set. The 'flower formula' for S reads,

$$S = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_{\mathbb{S}_+^2} A(H_{C_u}) du = 4\mathbb{E}(A(H_{C_u})), \quad (2)$$

the expectation being with respect to (w.r.t.) the uniform probability element $\mathbb{P}(du) = du/(2\pi)$. Therefore,

$$\widehat{S}(u) = 4A(H_{C_u}) \quad (3)$$

is an unbiased estimator (UE) of S , (Cruz-Orive, 2005). The estimator $\widehat{S}(u)$, and its variance, depend on the position of $P \in K^\circ$, but its expectation does not. (To simplify the notation, the dependence of $\widehat{S}(u), C_u$, etc., on P is ignored in the sequel). The flower area is,

$$A(H_{C_u}) = \pi\mathbb{E}(h^2(u, \omega)), \quad (4)$$

the expectation being w.r.t. $\mathbb{P}(d\omega) = d\omega/(2\pi)$. Thus,

$$\widehat{S}(u, \omega) = 4\pi h^2(u, \omega) \quad (5)$$

is another UE of the surface area of the convex body K . Based on the critical points of ∂C_u , the preceding estimator was generalized for non convex particles by Thórisdóttir and Kiderlen (2014) and Thórisdóttir et al. (2014) using Morse theory. Gual-Arnau and CruzOrive (2016) obtained the same estimator by a different approach, and its simplified version was called the 'peak-and-valley formula' in Cruz-Orive and Gual-Arnau (2015), see also Cruz-Orive (2024), p. 50.

If K is an ellipsoid, then the transect C_u is an ellipse of principal semiaxes $0 < m(u) \leq M(u)$, say, and $A(H_{C_u})$ can be computed in terms of $m(u), M(u)$, and the distance $r(u)$ of the pivotal point $P \in C_u$ from the ellipse centre, see Fig. 1b,c. The result is,

$$A(H_{C_u}) = \frac{\pi}{2} (M^2(u) + m^2(u) + r^2(u)), \quad (6)$$

(Appendix A.1), and, by Eq. 3,

$$\widehat{S}(u) = 2\pi (M^2(u) + m^2(u) + r^2(u)) \quad (7)$$

is unbiased for S .

For a convex body, $\mathbb{E}(\widehat{S}(u, \omega) | u) = \widehat{S}(u)$, where $\widehat{S}(u)$ is given by Eq. 3, or by Eq. 7 for an ellipsoid. Therefore, in either case,

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Var}(\widehat{S}(u, \omega)) \\ &= \text{Var}\{\mathbb{E}(\widehat{S}(u, \omega) | u)\} + \mathbb{E}\{\text{Var}(\widehat{S}(u, \omega) | u)\} \\ &\geq \text{Var}(\widehat{S}(u)). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Cruz-Orive (2008) studied the variances of various invariator estimators of surface area and volume,

and compared them with those of classical local estimators using a sphere model. The variance of $\widehat{S}(\omega, u)$, was considered by Dvořák and Jensen (2013), who obtained explicit results for spheroids (namely biaxial ellipsoids). The variance of the aforementioned generalization of Eq. 5 was studied by Thórisdóttir et al. (2014).

THE INVARIATOR ESTIMATOR OF THE SURFACE AREA S OF AN ELLIPSOID

THE SURFACE AREA OF AN ELLIPSOID

Consider an ellipsoid $K \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ of principal semiaxes $0 < a_1 \leq a_2 \leq a_3 < \infty$. In Cartesian coordinates,

$$K := \left\{ (x_1, x_2, x_3) \in \mathbb{R}^3 : \sum_{i=1}^3 x_i^2/a_i^2 \leq 1 \right\}. \quad (9)$$

The surface area of K is,

$$\begin{aligned} S &:= S(a_1, a_2, a_3) \\ &= 2\pi a_1^2 + \frac{2\pi a_2 a_3}{\sin(\varphi)} \cdot (E(\varphi, k) \sin^2(\varphi) \\ &\quad + F(\varphi, k) \cos^2(\varphi)), \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where

$$\cos(\varphi) = \frac{a_1}{a_3}, \quad k^2 = \frac{1 - (a_1/a_2)^2}{1 - (a_1/a_3)^2}, \quad (11)$$

(Legendre, 1811, p. 191), and

$$\begin{aligned} F(\varphi, k) &= \int_0^\varphi \frac{dt}{\sqrt{1 - k^2 \sin^2(t)}} \\ E(\varphi, k) &= \int_0^\varphi \sqrt{1 - k^2 \sin^2(t)} dt \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

represent the incomplete elliptic integrals of the first and second kind, respectively.

PARAMETRIZATION OF THE PIVOTAL POINT AND THE PIVOTAL PLANE

We introduce the following definitions and notation.

- Principal semiaxes lengths of the ellipsoid K :
 $a := (a_1, a_2, a_3), (0 < a_1 \leq a_2 \leq a_3 < \infty)$. (13)
- Cartesian coordinates of a pivotal point $P(x_0) \in K^\circ$:

$$x_0 := (x_{01}, x_{02}, x_{03}), \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 x_{0i}^2/a_i^2 - 1 < 0 \right). \quad (14)$$

Fig. 1: (a) Orthogonal projection of a triaxial ellipsoid K onto a plane normal to a hitting pivotal plane $L_{2[P]}^3$. (b) Perspective view of the elliptical pivotal section $C_u := K \cap L_{2[P]}^3$ of centre C , and of its orthogonal projection, of centre C' , onto the equatorial plane Ox_1x_2 . (c) Elliptical pivotal section with the three random variables involved in the unbiased estimator \hat{S} of the surface area of the ellipsoid, see Eq. 7.

- Direction cosines of a unit direction vector $u \in S_+^2$:

$$u := (u_1, u_2, u_3), \quad \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 u_i^2 = 1 \right). \quad (15)$$

In spherical polar coordinates,

$$u(\phi, \theta) := (\sin \theta \cos \phi, \sin \theta \sin \phi, \cos \theta),$$

$$(\phi \in [0, 2\pi), \theta \in [0, \pi/2]). \quad (16)$$

- Half orthogonal linear projection of K onto an axis of direction u , see Fig. 1a:

$$H(a, u) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 a_i^2 u_i^2 \right)^{1/2}, \quad (17)$$

(Appendix A.2). Actually, $H(a, u)$ is the support function of K , also known as half the caliper length of K along the direction u .

- Pivotal plane $L_{2[P]}^3$ through $P(x_0)$ with normal direction u :

$$L_{2[P]}^3 := \left\{ (x_1, x_2, x_3) \in \mathbb{R}^3 : \sum_{i=1}^3 x_i u_i = p \right\}, \quad (18)$$

$$p \in (-H(a, u), H(a, u)),$$

where

$$p := p(x_0, u) = \sum_{i=1}^3 x_{0i} u_i \quad (19)$$

is the signed distance of $L_{2[P]}^3$ from the origin O , see Fig. 1a.

- The pivotal plane is isotropically oriented, which means that $u(\phi, \theta) \sim \text{UR}(S_+^2)$. The joint probability element of (ϕ, θ) is,

$$\mathbb{P}(d\phi, d\theta) = \frac{d\phi}{2\pi} \cdot \sin \theta d\theta. \quad (20)$$

PARAMETRIZATION OF \hat{S} , AND COMPUTATION OF $\text{Var}(\hat{S})$

Further definitions and notation:

- Major and minor principal semiaxes of the section ellipse $C_u := K \cap L_{2[P]}^3$:

$$M := M(a, x_0, u), m := m(a, x_0, u), \quad (21)$$

respectively, see Fig. 1b,c.

- Major and minor principal semiaxes of a central ellipse $K \cap L_{2[0]}^3$ normal to u :

$$M_0 := M(a, 0, u), m_0 := m(a, 0, u), \quad (22)$$

respectively.

- Distance of the pivotal point $P(x_0)$ from the centre C of the section ellipse C_u :

$$r := r(a, x_0, u), \quad (23)$$

see Fig. 1b, c.

Now Eq. 7 may be rewritten as follows,

$$\hat{S} := \hat{S}(a, x_0, u) = 2\pi (M^2(a, x_0, u) + m^2(a, x_0, u) + r^2(a, x_0, u)), \quad (24)$$

and the unbiasedness of \widehat{S} means that its expectation with respect to the uniform probability element given by Eq. 20 is equal to S , namely,

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E} \left\{ \widehat{S}(a, x_0, u) \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{\pi/2} \sin \theta \, d\theta \int_0^{2\pi} \widehat{S}(a, x_0, u(\phi, \theta)) \, d\phi \quad (25) \\ &= S. \end{aligned}$$

The explicit formula sought for $\widehat{S}(a, x_0, u)$ is given by Proposition 1 below, and that of its variance by Corollary 1.

Lemma 1.

$$M_0^2 + m_0^2 = \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq 3} a_i^2 a_j^2 (u_i^2 + u_j^2) / H^2(a, u), \quad (26)$$

(Appendix A.3).

Lemma 2.

$$M^2 + m^2 = (M_0^2 + m_0^2) \left(1 - \frac{p^2(x_0, u)}{H^2(a, u)} \right), \quad (27)$$

(Appendix A.4).

Lemma 3. Let $c := (c_1, c_2, c_3)$ denote the Cartesian coordinates of the centre C of the pivotal ellipse section $C_u := K \cap L_{2|P}^3$. Then,

$$r^2 = \sum_{i=1}^3 (x_{0i} - c_i)^2 = \sum_{i=1}^3 \left(x_{0i} - \frac{a_i^2 u_i p(x_0, u)}{H^2(a, u)} \right)^2, \quad (28)$$

(Appendix A.5).

Proposition 1. Consider an ellipsoid $K \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ of principal semiaxes a , plus a given pivotal point P of Cartesian coordinates $x_0 \in K^\circ$, and a pivotal plane $L_{2|P}^3$ through P with normal direction u , uniformly distributed in \mathbb{S}_+^2 . Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2\pi} \widehat{S}(a, x_0, u) &= \frac{\sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq 3} a_i^2 a_j^2 (u_i^2 + u_j^2)}{\sum_{i=1}^3 a_i^2 u_i^2} \\ &\times \left(1 - \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^3 x_{0i} u_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^3 a_i^2 u_i^2} \right) \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^3 \left(x_{0i} - \frac{a_i^2 u_i \sum_{j=1}^3 x_{0j} u_j}{\sum_{j=1}^3 a_j^2 u_j^2} \right)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

is an UE of the surface area S of K

Proof. It suffices to incorporate Eq. 26, Eq. 27 and Eq. 28 into the rhs of Eq. 24, bearing Eq. 17 and Eq. 19 in mind.

Corollary 1. The variance of the preceding estimator is,

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Var} \left(\widehat{S}(a, x_0, u) \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{\pi/2} \sin \theta \, d\theta \int_0^{2\pi} (\widehat{S}(a, x_0, u(\phi, \theta)))^2 \, d\phi \quad (30) \\ &- S^2, \end{aligned}$$

where the direction cosines involved in Eq. 29 have been expressed in spherical polar coordinates, (Eq. 16).

Proof. Eq. 30 follows by the definition of the variance and by Eq. 25.

Corollary 2. The surface area $S(a_1, a_2, a_3)$ of an ellipsoid, see Eq. 10, may be expressed as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} & S(a_1, a_2, a_3) \\ &= \int_{u \in \mathbb{S}_+^2} \left(\sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq 3} a_i^2 a_j^2 (u_i^2 + u_j^2) \right) / \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 a_i^2 u_i^2 \right) \, du \\ &= \int_{-1}^1 \, du_1 \int_0^{\sqrt{1-u_1^2}} \frac{\sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq 3} a_i^2 a_j^2 (u_i^2 + u_j^2)}{\sqrt{1-u_1^2-u_2^2} \sum_{i=1}^3 a_i^2 u_i^2} \, du_2 \quad (31) \end{aligned}$$

with the substitution $u_3^2 = 1 - u_1^2 - u_2^2$ in the latter integrand.

Proof. The estimator $\widehat{S}(a, x_0, u)$, see Eq. 29, is unbiased for any choice of the pivotal point $P(x_0) \in K^\circ$. For the particular choice $x_0 = (0, 0, 0)$, the expected value of $\widehat{S}(a, 0, u)$ with respect to the uniform probability element

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(du) &= \frac{du}{2\pi} = \frac{du_1 \, du_2}{2\pi \sqrt{1-u_1^2-u_2^2}} \quad (32) \\ &\left(-1 \leq u_1 \leq 1, 0 \leq u_2 \leq \sqrt{1-u_1^2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

must therefore be equal to the rhs of Eq. 10.

As an exercise, a direct verification of Eq. 31, using spherical polar coordinates, is given in Appendix A.6.

Corollary 3. If K is the unit sphere, namely if $a_1 = a_2 = a_3 = 1$, then by symmetry we may take $x_{01} = x_{02} = 0$ and $u_1 = \sin \theta, u_2 = 0, u_3 = \cos \theta$, whereby Eq. 29 becomes,

$$\widehat{S}(x_{03}, \theta) = 2\pi (2 - 2x_{03}^2 + 3x_{03}^2 \sin^2 \theta). \quad (33)$$

Then, the application of Eq. 25 and Eq. 30 yield, respectively,

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}\{\widehat{S}(x_{03}, \theta)\} &= 4\pi = S \\ \text{CV}^2\{\widehat{S}(x_{03}, \theta)\} &= \frac{\text{Var}\{\widehat{S}(x_{03}, \theta)\}}{S^2} = \frac{x_{03}^4}{5}.\end{aligned}\quad (34)$$

For the unit sphere, and for the estimator of S given by Eq. 5,

$$\text{CV}^2\{\widehat{S}(u, \omega)\} = \frac{4x_{03}^2}{3}, \quad (35)$$

(Cruz-Orive, 2008, Eq. 6), which is larger than $x_{03}^4/5$ for all $x_{03} \in (0, 1)$, as expected from Eq. 8.

HEAT MAPS OF CV (\widehat{S}) FOR A GIVEN ELLIPSOID

While the unbiasedness identity $\mathbb{E}(\widehat{S}) = S$ does not depend on the location of the pivotal point $x_0 \in K^\circ$, the variance of \widehat{S} does. For any arbitrary pivotal point in the interior of a given ellipsoid, the numerical value of the double integral in the rhs of Eq. 30 can be evaluated quickly with the aid of software packages such as R, (<http://www.r-project.org>), or Mathematica, (Wolfram Research, Inc.).

To appreciate the behaviour of $\text{CV}(\widehat{S})$ as the location of the pivotal point varies, it suffices to adopt an arbitrary triaxial ellipsoid - here, one of principal semiaxes $a = (1, 2, 3)$ was chosen for that purpose, see Fig. 2. The application of Eq. 10 yields $S = 48.8821 \dots$ for this ellipsoid. As expected, numerical integration of the rhs of Eq. 25 yields the same value for arbitrary choices of x_0 satisfying Eq. 14.

However, $\text{Var}(\widehat{S})$ depends on the choice of x_0 . For instance, for $x_0 = (0.3, 0.0, 1.7)$, $(0.0, 0.4, 2.4)$, and $(0.5, 0.7, 0.0)$, say, the corresponding values of $\text{CV}(\widehat{S}) = \sqrt{\text{Var}(\widehat{S})/S}$ are $0.44 \dots$, $0.65 \dots$, $0.18 \dots$. For numerical computation, the vector u in Eq. 29 was expressed in spherical polar coordinates.

The results given in the present section were computed with the aid of the software package R4.4.2 (<http://www.r-project.org>). The computation of the elliptic integrals involved in Eq. 10 requires calling `library(Carlson)`.

The heat maps displayed in Fig. 2 (upper panels) correspond to the cases in which the pivotal point belongs to each of the intersections of the ellipsoid with the planes $x_2 = 0$, $x_1 = 0$, and $x_3 = 0$, respectively, namely the three principal ellipses. Within each principal ellipse, pivotal points were generated constituting a square grid of size 0.01. For

instance, the principal ellipse in the plane $x_2 = 0$ was enclosed in the rectangle $[-1, 1] \times [-3, 3]$, which contained 201×601 grid points. As a check, the proportion of pivotal points within the ellipse section, namely satisfying the condition $x_1^2 + x_3^2/9 < 1$, was of $94197/(200 \times 600)$, which is approximately equal to the expected ratio $\pi/4$ of the ellipse area to the rectangle area. Based on the colour intensity of the maps, it appears that the larger values of $\text{CV}(\widehat{S})$ correspond to pivotal points in peripheral regions of the ellipsoid. The lower panels in Fig. 2 suggest that the variation of $\text{CV}(\widehat{S})$ as a function of the distance from the ellipsoid centre of x_0 along an axis oscillates, hence it will not be monotonic in general.

The R program used was supplied by Claude.ai. It required calling `library(ggplot2)`, `library(scales)`, and `library(viridis)`. The codes of the programs used in this paper (under Windows 10) are available from the author on request.

FINAL COMMENTS

APPLICABILITY

While the estimator \widehat{S} can be computed by Eq. 7 from measurements made in any pivotal ellipse section of an arbitrary ellipsoid with unknown principal semiaxes lengths, $\text{Var}(\widehat{S})$ cannot be estimated from such measurements. The numerical computation of the exact $\text{Var}(\widehat{S})$ via Eq. 30 is not a problem, but it requires the knowledge of the mentioned lengths, and of the coordinates of the pivotal point.

In an (uncommon) practical case involving a population of arbitrary ellipsoidal particles containing a sole, prominent pivotal point (e.g., a 'nucleolus' in some biological cells), a ratio unbiased estimator of the ordinary population mean $\mathbb{E}_N(S)$ of the individual ellipsoid surface areas is,

$$\bar{s}_N = \frac{1}{Q^-} \sum_{i=1}^{Q^-} s_i = \frac{2\pi}{Q^-} \sum_{i=1}^{Q^-} (M_i^2 + m_i^2 + r_i^2), \quad (36)$$

which is an adaptation to ellipsoids of the first Eq. (4.2) from Cruz-Orive (2005), or of Eq. (4.24.2) from Cruz-Orive (2024). Thus, Q^- is the total number of ellipsoids sampled with isotropic uniform random (IUR) optical disectors, say, using the nucleoli as sampling units. A sweeping optical section meeting the i th nucleolus for the first time is thereby a pivotal section, and the corresponding lengths (M_i, m_i, r_i) can be measured in the corresponding ellipse section by adopting the sampled nucleolus as the pivotal point. If a particle contains several nucleoli, then one of them is chosen uniformly at random.

Fig. 2: Above: Heat maps of the coefficient of variation $CV(\hat{S})$ of the estimator \hat{S} computed via Eq. 30, for a triaxial ellipsoid of principal semiaxes $(1, 2, 3)$. From left to right, intersections of the ellipsoid with the planes $x_2 = 0, x_1 = 0$, and $x_3 = 0$, respectively. Below: Corresponding plots of $CV(\hat{S})$ as the pivotal point lies along each of the three principal axes of the ellipsoid.

If the ellipsoidal particles do not contain nucleoli, then to estimate $\mathbb{E}_N(S)$ one can resort to a classical ratio design, e.g. Cruz-Orive (2024), Section 2.31. An alternative is to consider instead the volume weighted mean $\mathbb{E}_V(S) := \mathbb{E}_N(VS) / \mathbb{E}_N(V)$, which does not require disectors. Superimpose a test system of points on a planar IUR section through the population, and let $p_i \geq 1, (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$, denote the total number of test points hitting the i th hit ellipse section (n , which does not enter in the final estimator, is the number of hit ellipse sections). Actually, p_i is the number of times the i th ellipsoid volume is sampled, hence the volume weighting effect. Each hitting point is effectively a pivotal point, and therefore the invariator estimator of the surface area of the i th hit ellipsoid, based on the p_i test points hitting it, is,

$$s_i = \frac{2\pi}{p_i} \sum_{j=1}^{p_i} (M_{ij}^2 + m_{ij}^2 + r_{ij}^2). \quad (37)$$

Set $P = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i$, the total number of test points hitting ellipse sections in the IUR section plane. Then, a ratio unbiased estimator of $\mathbb{E}_V(S)$ is,

$$\bar{s}_V = \frac{1}{P} \sum_{i=1}^n p_i s_i = \frac{2\pi}{P} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^{p_i} (M_{ij}^2 + m_{ij}^2 + r_{ij}^2). \quad (38)$$

Renumber the entire set of P measurement triplets $\{(M_{ij}, m_{ij}, r_{ij})\}$ as $\{(M_i, m_i, r_i), i = 1, 2, \dots, P\}$. Then,

$$\bar{s}_V = \frac{2\pi}{P} \sum_{i=1}^P (M_i^2 + m_i^2 + r_i^2). \quad (39)$$

The preceding estimator is an adaptation to ellipsoids

of the first Eq. 5.3 from Cruz-Orive (2005), or of Eq. 4.25.1 from Cruz-Orive (2024).

GENERALIZATION

Computable formulae exist for the surface area S_d of the d -dimensional ellipsoid, see e.g. Rivin (2007), who generalizes formulae of Moran (1982) for $d = 3$. For $d > 3$, however, no closed expression is known in terms of elementary, or of classical special functions like elliptic integrals. The question arises of whether Eq. 31 could be generalized. Eq. 21 from Gual-Arnau et al. (2010) generalizes Eq. 2 for odd d only, namely for $d = 2r + 1, r = 0, 1, \dots$, and the pivotal plane has to be replaced with a subspace $L_{r+1[0]}^d$. In the invariator context, Gual-Arnau (2023) considers a cylinder probe of radius R (instead of a weighted test line $L_{1(z)}^2$) within a pivotal slab of thickness $2R$. The latter author does not consider the special case of convex bodies. It seems unlikely that Eq. 31 can be generalized.

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APPENDIX

A.1. DERIVATION OF EQ. 6 FOR THE FLOWER AREA OF AN ELLIPSE.

For a given pivotal ellipse section C_u , Eq. 4, with $h_P(\omega) := h(u, \omega)$, is equivalent to

$$A(H_{C_u}) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{2\pi} h_P^2(\omega) d\omega. \quad (40)$$

The support function $h_P(\omega)$ of C_u , with origin P , is just the radius vector of H_{C_u} with centre P . From Fig. 3 it is seen that $h_P(\omega)$ is equal to half the caliper length $H(\omega)$ of C_u , minus the orthogonal projected length of the vector \overline{CP} onto of the support line of $H(\omega)$. Let (x_0, y_0)

denote the Cartesian coordinates of P with respect to the ellipse centre C . Then,

$$\begin{aligned} h_P(\omega) &= H(\omega) - (x_0, y_0) \cdot (\cos \omega, \sin \omega) \\ &= (M^2 \cos^2 \omega + m^2 \sin^2 \omega)^{1/2} \\ &\quad - (x_0 \cos \omega + y_0 \sin \omega). \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Fig. 3: Pivotal ellipse C_u , see also Fig. 1, incorporating the corresponding support set or 'flower' H_{C_u} with respect to a pivotal point P .

The expression of $H(\omega)$ is a particular case of Eq. 52 for $d = 2$. Now Eq. 40 yields,

$$\begin{aligned} A(H_{C_u}) &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{2\pi} h_P^2(\omega) d\omega \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{2\pi} (M^2 \cos^2 \omega + m^2 \sin^2 \omega \\ &\quad + x_0^2 \cos^2 \omega + y_0^2 \sin^2 \omega) d\omega, \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

because the integrals of the terms involving the first powers of $\sin \omega$, or $\cos \omega$, vanish. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} A(H_{C_u}) &= \frac{\pi}{2} (M^2 + m^2 + x_0^2 + y_0^2) \\ &= \frac{\pi}{2} (M^2 + m^2 + r^2). \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

A.2. DERIVATION OF EQ. 17 FOR $H(a, u)$

To make the exposition self-contained, this, and Appendix A.4, are adapted from the Appendix in Cruz-Orive (1985). Here it is convenient to use matrix calculus. No difficulty is added by working in \mathbb{R}^d . Consider a d -ball $B_d(h)$ of radius h , centred at O . Referred to an orthogonal frame $Oy_1y_2 \cdots y_d$, the equation of the ball is,

$$\begin{aligned} y'By &\leq 0, \\ y &= (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_d, 1)', \\ B &= \text{diag}(h^{-2}, h^{-2}, \dots, {}^d h^{-2}, -1). \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

The equation of an hyperplane tangent to the ball is,

$$\begin{aligned} t'(h)y &= 0, \\ t(h) &= (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_d, -h)', \\ (t_1^2 + t_2^2 + \dots + t_d^2 &= 1). \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

The following unimodular central affinity,

$$\begin{aligned} x &= Gy, \\ x &= (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d, 1)' \\ G &= \text{diag}(a_1/h, a_2/h, \dots, a_d/h, 1), \\ h &= (a_1 a_2 \cdots a_d)^{1/d}, \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

transforms the ball, Eq. 44, into

$$\begin{aligned} x'Ax &\leq 0, \\ A &= G^{-1}BG^{-1} \\ &= \text{diag}(a_1^{-2}, a_2^{-2}, \dots, a_d^{-2}, -1), \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

namely a d -ellipsoid $K_d(a)$, $a := (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)$, and it also transforms the tangent hyperplane given by Eq. 45 into the hyperplane

$$t'(h)G^{-1}x = 0, \text{ namely } \sum_{i=1}^d (t_i/a_i)x_i = 1, \quad (48)$$

which is tangent to the ellipsoid. If the coefficients u_1, u_2, \dots, u_d , say, of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d , respectively, satisfied the identity $u_1^2 + u_2^2 + \dots + u_d^2 = 1$, then the rhs of the resulting equation would be the distance of the tangent hyperplane from O , namely the support function $H(a, u)$ of the ellipsoid with respect to O . To achieve this, set

$$\begin{aligned} u_i &= (t_i/a_i) \left(\sum_{j=1}^d t_j^2/a_j^2 \right)^{-1/2}, \\ (u_1^2 + u_2^2 + \dots + u_d^2 &= 1), \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

whereby,

$$\sum_{i=1}^d a_i^2 u_i^2 \sum_{i=1}^d t_j^2/a_j^2 = \sum_{i=1}^d t_i^2 = 1, \quad (50)$$

so that the transformed hyperplane becomes,

$$\sum_{i=1}^d x_i u_i \left(\sum_{j=1}^d t_j^2/a_j^2 \right)^{1/2} = 1, \quad (51)$$

or,

$$\sum_{i=1}^d x_i u_i = \left(\sum_{i=1}^d a_i^2 u_i^2 \right)^{1/2} = H(a, u). \quad (52)$$

For $d = 3$, $H(a, u)$ becomes Eq. 17.

A.3. PROOF OF LEMMA 1

The equation of the boundary ∂K of the ellipsoid K given by Eq. 9 is $f_1(x_1, x_2, x_3) = 1$, where

$$f_1 := f_1(x_1, x_2, x_3) = x_1^2/a_1^2 + x_2^2/a_2^2 + x_3^2/a_3^2. \quad (53)$$

On the other hand, the equation of a plane $L_{2[0]}^3$ through the origin is $f_2(x_1, x_2, x_3) = 0$, where

$$f_2 := f_2(x_1, x_2, x_3) = x_1u_1 + x_2u_2 + x_3u_3, \quad (u_1^2 + u_2^2 + u_3^2 = 1). \quad (54)$$

The square semiaxes m_0^2, M_0^2 of the central section $K \cap L_{2[0]}^3$, see Eq. 22, are the minimum and the maximum, respectively, of the square distance of a point of the boundary ∂K from O , namely of the function

$$R^2 := R^2(x_1, x_2, x_3) = x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2, \quad (55)$$

with the restrictions given by $f_1 = 1$ and $f_2 = 0$. By the Lagrange multipliers method, two parameters λ_1, λ_2 are introduced, and the function to minimize is,

$$f = R^2 + \lambda_1(f_1 - 1) + 2\lambda_2f_2. \quad (56)$$

The procedure leads to the following three equations,

$$\left\{ \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_i} = 0, i = 1, 2, 3 \right\}. \quad (57)$$

Multiplying the i th equation with x_i , adding up from $i = 1$ to $i = 3$, and making use of the definitions of R^2, f_1, f_2 , one obtains $\lambda_1 = -R^2$. Now, Eq. 57 yields,

$$\left\{ x_i = \frac{\lambda_2 a_i^2 u_i}{R^2 - a_i^2}, i = 1, 2, 3 \right\}, \quad (58)$$

which, substituted into the equation $f_2(x_1, x_2, x_3) = 0$, yields the following quadratic equation in the unknown R^2 ,

$$H^2 R^4 - H^2 \mu(a, u) R^2 + (a_1 a_2 a_3)^2 = 0 \quad (59)$$

where $H := H(a, u)$, see Eq. 17, whereas the factor $\mu(a, u)$ has in fact the expression in the rhs of Eq. 26. But $\mu(a, u)$ is precisely the sum of the two roots of R^2 , namely $M_0^2 + m_0^2$. As a check, the area of the central ellipse is,

$$A(K \cap L_{2[0]}^3) = \pi M_0 m_0 = \frac{\pi a_1 a_2 a_3}{H} = \frac{3V(K)}{4H}, \quad (60)$$

which is a special case of Eq. 67, see below, for $d = 3$. The foregoing proof is adapted from an exercise found in Rey-Pastor (1967, pp. 316-7), where the purpose was to find the expressions of m_0 and M_0 .

A.4. PROOF OF LEMMA 2

Consider a d -ellipsoid $K_d(a)$, see Eq. 47, transected by an hyperplane $L_{d-1}^d(p, u)$ of equation

$$u'(p)x = 0, \quad (61)$$

$$u(p) = (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_d, -p)',$$

$$(u_1^2 + u_2^2 + \dots + u_d^2 = 1), |p| \leq H(a, u).$$

Set,

$$V_{d-1}(p, u) := \text{Volume}(K_d(a) \cap L_{d-1}^d(p, u)). \quad (62)$$

Under the transform $x = Gy$, see Eq. 46, the d -ellipsoid becomes a d -ball $B_d(h)$, Eq. 44, whereas the hyperplane transecting the ball becomes

$$u'(p)Gy = 0, \text{ namely } \sum_{i=1}^d a_i y_i u_i = ph. \quad (63)$$

Analogously as in Appendix A.2, set

$$t_i = a_i u_i \left(\sum_{i=1}^d a_i^2 u_i^2 \right)^{-1/2} = a_i u_i / H, \quad (64)$$

where $H := H(a, u)$, for short. Then, Eq. 63 becomes

$$\sum_{i=1}^d y_i t_i = ph/H, \quad (t_1^2 + t_2^2 + \dots + t_d^2 = 1), \quad (65)$$

and therefore $B_d(h) \cap L_{d-1}^d(ph/H, t)$ is a $(d - 1)$ -ball of radius $(h^2 - p^2 h^2 / H^2)^{1/2}$ and volume $c(d - 1)h^{d-1} (1 - p^2 / H^2)^{(d-1)/2}$, where $c(d) = \pi^{d/2} / \Gamma(d/2 + 1)$ is the volume of the unit d -ball. Because G is unimodular and it transforms a vector of length H into one of length h , it follows that the ratio of the ellipsoid transect volume to the ball transect volume must be equal to h/H , whereby,

$$V_{d-1}(p, u) = H^{-1} c(d - 1) h^d (1 - p^2 / H^2)^{(d-1)/2} = V_{d-1}(0, u) (1 - p^2 / H^2)^{(d-1)/2}, \quad (66)$$

(Cruz-Orive, 1985, Jensen & Møller, 1986), where

$$V_{d-1}(0, u) = c(d - 1) h^d / H = c(d - 1) a_1 a_2 \dots a_d / H \quad (67)$$

is the volume of the central transect of the ellipsoid. For $d = 3$, Eq. 66 yields,

$$\pi M m = \pi M_0 m_0 (1 - p^2 / H^2). \quad (68)$$

Parallel ellipsoid sections are similar ellipses. In fact, under the transform G , which is linear, parallel ball

sections, namely disks, will become similar ellipses. Thus,

$$M/M_0 = m/m_0, \quad (69)$$

whereby Eq. 68 yields,

$$\begin{aligned} M^2 &= M_0^2 (1 - p^2/H^2), \\ m^2 &= m_0^2 (1 - p^2/H^2), \end{aligned} \quad (70)$$

and therefore,

$$M^2 + m^2 = (M_0^2 + m_0^2) (1 - p^2/H^2), \quad (71)$$

which is Eq. 27.

Results equivalent to Eq. 70 are well known for spheroids, e.g. Cruz-Orive (1976), but not readily available for triaxial ellipsoids in that simple form. Recall that M_0^2, m_0^2 are the roots of Eq. 59.

A.5. PROOF OF LEMMA 3

The problem is to parametrize the centre $C(c_1, c_2, c_3)$ of the pivotal ellipse section $C_u := K \cap L_{2[p]}^3$. The orthogonal projection of C_u onto the plane $x_3 = 0$ is an ellipse C'_u , say, of centre $C'(c_1, c_2)$, see Fig. 1b, whereas

$$c_3 = (p(u, x_0) - u_1 c_1 - u_2 c_2) / u_3, \quad (72)$$

because $C(c_1, c_2, c_3) \in L_{2[p]}^3$. Thus, the problem is reduced to finding $C'(c_1, c_2)$. The equation of the ellipse C'_u is obtained by eliminating x_3 from Eq. 9 and Eq. 18. In homogeneous coordinates the result is,

$$\begin{aligned} f(x_1, x_2, t) &:= a_{11}x_1^2 + 2a_{12}x_1x_2 + a_{22}x_2^2 \\ &+ 2a_{13}x_1t + 2a_{23}x_2t + a_{33}t^2 = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (73)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} a_{11} &= u_1^2 + u_3^2 a_3^2 / a_1^2, \\ a_{12} &= a_{21} = u_1 u_2, \\ a_{13} &= a_{31} = -p u_1, \\ a_{22} &= u_2^2 + u_3^2 a_3^2 / a_2^2, \\ a_{23} &= a_{32} = -p u_2, \\ a_{33} &= p^2 - u_3^2 a_3^2. \end{aligned} \quad (74)$$

The equation of the polar line of C'_u with respect to an exterior pole (x'_1, x'_2, t') is

$$g(x_1, x_2, t, x'_1, x'_2, t') := x'_1 \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_1} + x'_2 \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_2} + t' \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} = 0. \quad (75)$$

The ellipse centre is the point of intersection (c_1, c_2) of the two polar lines corresponding to the ideal poles $(1, 0, 0)$ and $(0, 1, 0)$. The corresponding equations are,

$$\begin{cases} g(c_1, c_2, 1, 1, 0, 0) = 0 \\ g(c_1, c_2, 1, 0, 1, 0) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (76)$$

namely,

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}c_1 + a_{12}c_2 + a_{13} = 0 \\ a_{12}c_1 + a_{22}c_2 + a_{23} = 0 \end{cases}$$

Solving for (c_1, c_2) , replacing the $\{a_{ij}\}$ with their expressions in Eq. 74, and using Eq. 72, Eq. 28 is obtained.

A.6. SYMBOLIC COMPUTATION OF THE DOUBLE INTEGRAL IN EQ. 31

The ensuing verification is strictly not necessary because, by Corollary 2, Eq. 31 must hold. Nonetheless, the integral is non trivial, and its direct computation may suit readers willing to circumvent the underlying stereological theory of the invariator design.

To avoid singularities, it is convenient to use spherical polar coordinates, see Eq. 16, whereby the identity to be verified is,

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} \sin \theta \, d\theta \int_0^{2\pi} f(\phi, \theta) \, d\phi = S(a_1, a_2, a_3) \quad (78)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} f(\phi, \theta) &= \sum_{i=1}^3 f_i(\phi, \theta), \\ f_1(\phi, \theta) &= a_1^2 a_2^2 \sin^2 \theta / H^2(\phi, \theta), \\ f_2(\phi, \theta) &= a_1^2 a_3^2 (1 - \sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \phi) / H^2(\phi, \theta), \\ f_3(\phi, \theta) &= a_2^2 a_3^2 (1 - \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \phi) / H^2(\phi, \theta), \\ H^2(\phi, \theta) &= a_1^2 \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \phi + a_2^2 \sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \phi \\ &+ a_3^2 \cos^2 \theta \end{aligned} \quad (79)$$

Mathematica 7, (Wolfram Research, Inc.) was not effective in checking Eq. 78 directly. However, integration was possible by treating each of the preceding three functions separately. Furthermore, integration was first carried out with respect to ϕ , the corresponding result was simplified, multiplied with $\sin \theta$, and finally integrated with respect to θ . For instance,

$$\begin{aligned} g_1(\theta) &:= \int_0^{2\pi} f_1(\phi, \theta) \, d\phi \\ &= \frac{4\pi a_1^2 a_2^2 \sin^2 \theta}{\sqrt{\prod_{i=1}^2 (a_i^2 + a_3^2 + (a_3^2 - a_i^2) \cos(2\theta))}}, \end{aligned} \quad (80)$$

and then,

$$G_1(a_1, a_2, a_3) := \int_0^{\pi/2} g_1(\theta) \sin \theta d\theta$$

$$= \frac{2\pi i a_1^2 a_2 (a_2^2 E(i\alpha, q) - a_3^2 F(i\alpha, q))}{(a_3^2 - a_2^2) \sqrt{a_3^2 - a_1^2}}, \quad (81)$$

where

$$\alpha = \operatorname{csch}^{-1} \left(a_1 / \sqrt{a_3^2 - a_1^2} \right), \quad (82)$$

$$q^2 = (a_3^2/a_2^2 - 1) / (a_3^2/a_1^2 - 1).$$

In Eq. 81, the two elliptic integrals of imaginary amplitude are transformed into the ones with real amplitude with the aid of Eq. 17.4.8 and Eq. 17.4.9 from Abramowitz and Stegun (1965), namely,

$$E(i\alpha, q) = -iE(\varphi, k) + iF(\varphi, k) + i\sqrt{a_3^2 - a_1^2}/a_2$$

$$F(i\alpha, q) = iF(\varphi, k) \quad (83)$$

where

$$\cos \varphi = \cos(\tan^{-1}(\sinh(\alpha))) = a_1/a_3 \quad (84)$$

$$k^2 = 1 - q^2 = (1 - a_1^2/a_2^2) / (1 - a_1^2/a_3^2)$$

in agreement with Eq. 11. Thus, Eq. 81 becomes,

$$G_1(a_1, a_2, a_3) = \frac{2\pi a_1^2 a_2^2}{a_2^2 - a_3^2}$$

$$+ \frac{2\pi a_1^2 a_2 (a_2^2 E(\varphi, k) + (a_3^2 - a_2^2) F(\varphi, k))}{(a_3^2 - a_2^2) \sqrt{a_3^2 - a_1^2}}. \quad (85)$$

Similarly, the double integrals corresponding to f_2, f_3 become,

$$G_2(a_1, a_2, a_3) = \frac{2\pi a_1^2 a_3^2}{a_3^2 - a_2^2}$$

$$- \frac{2\pi a_1^2 a_2 a_3^2 ((a_3^2 - a_1^2) E(\varphi, k) - (a_3^2 - a_2^2) F(\varphi, k))}{(a_2^2 - a_1^2) (a_3^2 - a_2^2) \sqrt{a_3^2 - a_1^2}},$$

$$G_3(a_1, a_2, a_3) = \frac{2\pi a_2 a_3^2 (a_2^2 E(\varphi, k) - a_1^2 F(\varphi, k))}{(a_2^2 - a_1^2) \sqrt{a_3^2 - a_1^2}}, \quad (86)$$

respectively. It is readily verified that

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} \sin \theta d\theta \int_0^{2\pi} f(\phi, \theta) d\phi$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^3 G_i(a_1, a_2, a_3) = 2\pi a_1^2 \quad (87)$$

$$+ \frac{2\pi a_2}{\sqrt{a_3^2 - a_1^2}} ((a_3^2 - a_1^2) E(\varphi, k) + a_1^2 F(\varphi, k))$$

which coincides with the rhs of Eq. 10, as required.

COMPARISON OF DEEP LEARNING MODELS FOR VOICE DISORDER CLASSIFICATION USING PHONOVIBROGRAPHIC IMAGES

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ABSTRACT

Accurate diagnosis of vocal fold disorders is difficult because of subtle variations between pathological conditions. Phonovibrography (PVG), generated from high-speed videoendoscopy (HSV), documents glottal vibration patterns as static images, allowing systemic analysis. In our study, we propose PVGNet, a hybrid deep learning model combining multiscale feature extraction and channel attention, designed specifically for PVG-based classification. We benchmark PVGNet against InceptionResNetV2, VGG19, DenseNet169, and X-ViT across binary, tertiary, and multi-class tasks. PVGNet continuously outperforms baselines in accuracy, F1-score, and AUC, by minimizing false negatives, which is important for reliable diagnosis. These results show PVG's potential as a diagnostic imaging modality and PVGNet's effectiveness in automated voice disorder classification.

Keywords: Classification; Deep Learning Models; Functional Voice Disorders; High-speed video endoscopy; Phonovibrogram; Voice Disorder.

INTRODUCTION

Voice production is the most important tool of human communication (Kamiloglu and Sauter, 2021), and any abnormalities in the process can lead to voice disorders (Spina *et al.*, 2009).

Within the larynx, the vocal folds are located which are the central organs of voice production. They are responsible for necessary voice functions such as phonation, voice quality, pitch control, volume, loudness, and verbal expression (Jiang *et al.*, 2000).

Disruptions in the normal movement of the vocal folds can cause many voice disorders. These are grouped into organic, functional, structural, neurological and acquired types (Stemple *et al.*, 2020). Accurately identifying these disorders with traditional clinical methods can be difficult and mistakes in interpretation often delay diagnosis.

To make assessment more reliable several imaging techniques such as laryngoscopy, stroboscopy and high-speed videoendoscopy (HSV) have been introduced to let clinicians directly observe how the vocal folds move (Deliyski and Hillman, 2010). HSV provides very high temporal resolution and gives a detailed view of vocal-fold vibrations (Deliyski *et al.*, 2008;

Malinowski *et al.*, 2024). Many image-processing methods have tried to analyze HSV recordings and

describe how the vocal folds vibrate. Still, because HSV produces a huge number of frames each second, reviewing and diagnosing from these sequences can be demanding.

This challenge led to the creation of visualization methods that summarize vocal-fold vibration into single images for easier interpretation. These visualization tools have improved the accuracy of clinical evaluation. Broadly, they fall into two categories: local and global.

Local approaches such as digital kymography (DKG), vocal-fold trajectories (VFT), mucosal-wave kymography (MKG), and optical-flow kymography (OFKG), track motion along a line that cuts across the glottis. Global approaches such as the glottal optical-flow waveform (GOFW), glottal area waveform (GAW), glottovibrogram (GVG), and phonovibrogram (PVG), show how the entire glottis behaves through the vibration cycle (Andrade-Miranda *et al.*, 2020).

PVG provides a 3-D view of vocal-fold motion and converts dynamic vibrations into static maps that can be studied both visually and quantitatively.

This method was Introduced by Lohscheller *et al.*, in which we can extract and visualize the vocal fold vibrations along the entire edge of the glottis. Their work shows both visual and quantitative analysis in various conditions like normal phonation, laryngeal nerve paralysis, and functional voice disorders such as vocal

nodules (Bohr *et al.*, 2013, Doellinger *et al.*, 2007, Kunduk *et al.*, 2012, Lohscheller and Eysholdt, 2008, Patidar *et al.*, 2016).

Recent advances in machine learning have improved more in the clinical of PVG by automated feature extraction and classification of vocal fold pathologies (Döllinger *et al.*, 2011, Lohscheller, 2009, Schlegel *et al.*, 2020, Voigt *et al.*, 2010a, Voigt *et al.*, 2010b). These computational methods improve diagnostic objectivity, minimize inter-rater variability, and support early intervention, which are the important factors in improving clinical outcomes for individuals with voice disorders. Although many studies have investigated the visual and quantitative features of PVG, the application of PVG images for classifying pathologic conditions is still unexplored.

A machine learning-based study that involved transforming PVG contour lines into numerical feature vectors, which were then analyzed using a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier.

They tested their SVM method on both functional voice disorders and vocal fold paralysis. They achieved 78.5% accuracy for functional disorders and 93% for paralysis (Lohscheller, 2009).

Another study used a similar method focusing specially on vocal fold paralysis. They have shown 93% accuracy for classifying healthy vs. paralysis and 73% for a 3-class task (healthy, left paresis, right paresis) (Voigt *et al.*, 2010b).

In another study, they found that features extracted from PVGs performed better than traditional glottal parameters, producing an overall classification accuracy of 81% for predicting functional dysphonia (Voigt *et al.*, 2010a).

These studies shows the potential of PVG-based features to support the automated diagnosis of voice pathologies, including non-organic disorders such as paresis and muscle tension dysphonia (MTD).

In addition to that, in a study, authors found that SVM based machine learning classification of PVG-derived vibratory features outperforms acoustic feature analysis, particularly in identifying subtle phonation-dependent variations (Döllinger *et al.*, 2011). Based on

current literature, only one study has utilized deep learning for the vocal fold disorder classification using PVG. In that study, authors showed classification accuracies of 82% using CNN-based LeNet architecture for a binary classification (physiologic vs. pathologic) and 85% for a multi-class classification (Healthy, MTD, Paresis, and Polyp) (Fehling *et al.*, 2020).

In our study we explore novel applications of various deep learning architectures to analyze PVG images, focusing on both binary classification (Healthy and unhealthy), tertiary classification (Healthy, functional, and organic), and multi-class classification (Healthy, MTD, atrophy, nodule, and edema) tasks. An overview of the proposed workflow is presented in Fig. 1.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Dataset

This study utilizes the BAGLS (Benchmark for Automatic Glottis Segmentation) dataset which consists of 640 HSV recordings collected in seven different hospitals. It is a multi-centered dataset, which has a demographically diversified patient population. Also, with variations in age, gender, and vocal fold pathology. All recordings collected by clinical experts, using high-quality data acquisition and professional validation (Gomez *et al.*, 2020). The dataset contains both healthy subjects and patients with various vocal fold disorders makes it useful for developing and testing classification models.

PVG Generation

A detailed procedure for the PVG computation is found in (Doellinger *et al.*, 2007). In this current study, we used the Glottal analysis tool (GAT) to generate PVGs.

The glottis was fixed as the region of interest within the vocal fold (Kist *et al.*, 2021). First the glottal contours were extracted from each HSV frame using an edge segmentation algorithm.

The centerline of the glottis, referred to as the glottal axis, was then identified.

Fig. 1: Workflow for phonovibrogram-based vocal fold disorders classification using the BAGLS dataset. The pipeline includes data preprocessing, PVG generation, classification (binary, tertiary, multiclass), model training, validation and testing, and evaluation using five different deep learning models and standard performance metrics.

For each frame, the distances from points along the glottal axis to the corresponding points on the left and right fold contours were calculated and stored in a column vector.

The glottal axis was bisected, and the left contour was rotated 180 degrees around the posterior commissure to align it with the right contour.

Their respective distance vectors were then color-coded based on their magnitude: red indicates greater distances, black represents zero distance, and intermediate values were shown in gradations between red and black.

If a vocal fold contour crosses the glottal midline, it is marked in blue. This process was repeated across all frames, and the resulting vectors were concatenated into a 2-D matrix and visualized as the PVG, as illustrated in Fig. 2(a).

Data Preprocessing

Generated PVGs consist of multiple vibratory cycles, with each image having dimensions of 3000x720 pixels (length x width), corresponding to the HSV sequence.

Next, it was divided into a number of images with dimensions of 210x720 pixels, each capturing 3-4 cycles. This approach expanded the training dataset size while maintaining detailed analysis of temporal patterns. Fig. 2(b) shows the representative HSV frames for different vocal fold conditions and their corresponding

kymograms. Table 1 presents the count of PVG images for each vocal fold condition.

Table 1. Count of PVG images

Conditions	PVG image counts
Healthy	5095
Functional/MTD	1626
Unhealthy	3016
Organic	954
Nodules	169
Edema	139
Atrophy	243

Resizing and Normalization

PVGs were resized to 128x128 for all models. After resizing the pixel values were converted to the range [0, 1] by normalization. Ensuring consistency across all images. To achieve a more balanced sample distribution, oversampling methods were applied, augmenting the underrepresented classes to achieve a more balanced distribution of samples. Only Deep Learning (DL)-based vibration features were used, and no manual descriptors were included.

Fig. 2: (a) Generation of PVGs from HSV recordings: (i) Glottal area segmentation in HSV frames; (ii) Contour extraction and splitting of the left and right vocal fold edges; (iii) Color coding of vibratory motion over time; (iv) Construction of the PVG 2 (b) Representative samples of HSV endoscopic frames (left in each pair) and their corresponding PVGs (right in each pair) for different vocal fold conditions: Healthy, MTD, Edema, Nodules, Atrophy, Laryngitis, Leukoplakia, and Papilloma. These examples show the distinct morphological and vibratory patterns associated with each condition.

Deep learning models

Our study focused on evaluating five different deep learning models for the classification of PVG images derived from HSV data.

The models include VGG19 (Simonyan and Zisserman, 2014), DenseNet169 (Huang et al., 2017), InceptionResNetV2 (Szegedy et al., 2017), a custom transformer ensemble model (Xception (Chollet, 2017) + Vision Transformer (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020)) named X-ViT, and a custom Hybrid CNN with an attention mechanism specifically designed for PVG, named PVGNet.

These models were chosen to investigate their effectiveness in analyzing vocal fold vibrations and classifying vocal fold pathologies based on PVG representations. Each model brings distinct advantages to the PVG classification task. VGG19 is a deep convolutional architecture with its simple yet improved hierarchical feature extraction capabilities. DenseNet169 uses dense connectivity between layers, helping efficient feature reuse and gradient flow. InceptionResNetV2 merge both the advantage of Inception modules and residual connections, improving both model performance and classification accuracy. Also the X-ViT model merges convolutional and transformer-based model using both local and global features for thorough PVG analysis (Ganaie et al., 2022).

Finally, PVGNet is a fully custom-built architecture developed specially for PVG classification. It combines the attention mechanisms to focus on important vibratory regions of interest (Wang et al., 2018). Unlike the other models, PVGNet does not rely on pretrained weights, allowing it to learn from scratch and making it highly specialized for this task.

Hybrid CNN-Attention Network (PVGNet)

The diagnostic accuracy of PVG depends on actively detecting subtle, multi-scale pathological patterns even in background noise (Doellinger and Berry, 2006).

Therefore, we developed PVGNet as a hybrid Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) improved with adaptive attention mechanisms, noise resilience, and multi-scale feature representation as shown in Fig. 3 (Hu et al., 2020). PVGNet merges hierarchical feature extraction with attention modules to show diagnostically meaningful regions while repressing irrelevant information. The model processes input PVG images of size $128 \times 128 \times 3$ via three convolutional blocks with increasing filter sizes of 64, 128, and 256.

Each block applies ReLU activation, then max pooling and batch normalization to stabilize convergence and improve training performance (Ioffe and Szegedy, 2015). This continuous convolutional block actively spots the layered complexity of PVG irregularities. Early layers documents intricate textures such as edema and vocal nodules using smaller receptive fields, deeper layers extract broader structural abnormalities like vocal fold atrophy and MTD via large filters (Chen et al., 2018).

The attention mechanism is applied after the convolutional stages, warranting the model to selectively boost the most informative spatial regions pertinent to pathology.

Each block has max pooling and batch normalization to stabilize convergence, which is very important for handling PVG images. The convolutional operation at each layer is defined as:

$$F^l = \delta(W^l * F^{l-1} + b^l)$$

Where F^l is the feature maps at layer l , W^l and b^l are the learnable weights and biases, $*$ means the convolution operation, and δ -delta is the ReLU activation function. Increasing filter sizes continuously learns multi-scale features. The expanding filter hierarchy make sure that thorough pattern extraction across spatial scales innate. After the convolutional layers, PVGNet uses a squeeze-and-excitation (SE) attention block that dynamically improves diagnostically useful channels when repressing noise (Hu et al., 2020).

This attention mechanism starts with compressing spatial information into compact channel descriptors via global average pooling

$$z_c = \frac{1}{H \times W} \sum_{i=1}^H \sum_{j=1}^W F_{c(i,j)}$$

z_c is the c -th element of the channel descriptor. H , W are the feature map's height and width which compresses unwanted spatial noise, maintaining channel-wise discriminative information.

The excitation operation then models channel-wise dependencies:

$$s = \sigma(W_2 \delta(W_1 z))$$

Where $W_1 \in R^{\left(\frac{c}{r}\right) \times c}$ and $W_2 \in R^{c \times \left(\frac{c}{r}\right)}$ form a bottleneck with a reduction ratio $r = 8$. δ delta refers to ReLU, σ sigma is the sigmoid activation function, the recalibration stage weights each channel by multiplying the feature maps elementwise:

$$\tilde{F}_c = s_c \cdot F_c$$

Fig. 3: Proposed Hybrid CNN-Attention Network for PVG Classification (PVGNet), where F - Filters, N - Neurons, Sig - Sigmoid, and FM - Feature Maps

The network applies global average pooling before sending features via two fully connected layers (256 and 128 neurons) with ReLU activation after the attention block. L2 regularization ($\lambda=0.001$) is applied to prevent overfitting (Krogh and Hertz, 1991):

$$\Omega(w) = \frac{\lambda}{2} \|w\|_2^2$$

Dropout (rate = 0.4) is set to improve generalization and prevent overfitting, helping the model become more robust to variations and noise in the PVG images (Srivastava *et al.*, 2014). The output layer uses a single neuron with sigmoid activation for binary classification of healthy vs. unhealthy PVG conditions (Bishop, 1995):

$$\sigma(z) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}}$$

The corresponding binary cross-entropy loss function (Murphy, 2012) is:

$$L = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)]$$

For tertiary and multi-class tasks, categorical cross-entropy loss (Heaton, 2017) is utilized:

$$L = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^K y_{ij} \log(\hat{y}_{ij})$$

PVG images show different types of vibratory patterns, ranging from intricate vocal fold textures (e.g., edema, nodules) to broader structural alterations (e.g., atrophy, MTD) on their intensity variations.

We designed PVGNet specially to address this variability via a combination of multiscale feature extraction, an attention mechanism, and a noise-resilient design. Its hybrid architecture is intended to predict different vibratory features.

Experimental setup

Experiments were performed on an HP workstation, configured with an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 Ti and 42.9 GB of GPU memory. Python was used with the TensorFlow 2.10 framework for executing the classification tasks.

The dataset consisted of HSV recordings of vocal fold vibrations with 376 recordings of Healthy and 163 Unhealthy.

A total of 101 recordings were excluded from our analysis: 50 due to missing health status information, and 51 due to the presence of multiple co-occurring disorders. 102 recordings were categorised as functional voice disorders, primarily MTD, and 56 were categorized as organic disorders.

The organic category included cases of scar tissue, papilloma, nodules, edema, carcinoma, laryngitis, polyps, cysts, and atrophy.

Data stratification for Binary Classification (Healthy vs Unhealthy)

For the binary classification task we worked with 8111 PVG images in total. To begin with, 15% of the data (1218 images) was set aside as the test set, containing 765 Healthy and 453 Unhealthy samples. This portion was never touched again and was used only for the final evaluation.

The remaining 6893 images were then divided into training (70%) and validation (30%) subsets. Before doing any balancing we separated a validation set of 1034 images (around 15% of the total) to keep its class distribution natural. The training set (5859 images) showed a clear class imbalance which could easily bias the model toward the majority category.

To fix this we used random oversampling but only on the training data. This increased the underrepresented class until both were evenly matched resulting in a balanced training set of 7360 images. The validation and test sets were left untouched so they will reflect the true distribution allow a fair and real world evaluation of performance.

Data stratification for Tertiary Classification (Healthy vs. Functional vs. Organic)

For the tertiary class setup we used 6522 images. From this, about 15% (1153 images) was kept aside as the test set. The remaining data was then split into a training set (5543 images) and a validation set (979 images). As before the validation set was separated before handling any imbalance to maintain its natural mix of classes.

The training data had uneven representation across the three classes so we again applied random oversampling. This brought all classes to roughly equal levels, a balanced training of 11040 samples. The validation and test sets were kept in their original form to provide a realistic check on how well the model would generalize.

Data stratification for Multi-class Classification (Healthy vs. MTD vs Atrophy vs Nodule vs Edema)

In the five-class we analyzed 7272 images in total, distributed as Healthy (5095), MTD (1626), Atrophy (232), Nodule (180), and Edema (139). This imbalance

was quite pronounced, so special care was needed during training.

We first allocated 15% from each class to the test set to make sure every category was represented in evaluation. The rest formed the training and validation sets. As with the earlier tasks we used random oversampling to balance the training data. The smaller classes were increased till they matched the size of the Healthy group giving us a balanced training set of 18400 images with equal class.

The validation and test sets were not modified so that performance results would reflect how the model behaves on naturally imbalanced and real world data.

Training and Validation Phase

Random seed value of 42 was used for all classification tasks to maintain reproducibility and consistency. This warranted proper data partitioning into training and validation sets. The same applied in the random oversample to maintain consistency in class balancing through oversampling. The model trained using adam optimizer for 100 epochs using binary cross-entropy for binary class and categorical cross-entropy for tertiary and multi class tasks.

Hyperparameter tuning strategies such as learning rate scheduling and early stopping, reduce overfitting and improve performance. During training, model checkpoints were saved at the epochs producing the best validation performance. The final testing was conducted on a separate, previously unseen test set using the best-performing saved model.

Testing Phase

We used both qualitative and quantitative metrics to thoroughly evaluate PVG models. Quantitative measures such as accuracy, F1-score, sensitivity, specificity, and precision were used to objectively compare performance. Qualitative inspection with learning curves, confusion matrices, and ROC curves.

RESULTS

Evaluation of Binary Classification Performance

As shown in Fig. 4(a), PVGNet exhibits strong generalization capabilities, with a small aperture between training and validation accuracy shows a low risk of overfitting and reliable performance for real-world applications.

Fig.4. Training and validation performance curves for proposed network (PVGNet) across three classification tasks:(a) Binary classification(top) ,(b) Tertiary classification (middle), and(c) Multi-class(bottom).

In contrast, we observed in some models showing noticeably larger gaps, suggesting a tendency to overfit and reduced ability to generalize to unseen data. Others remain relatively stable, but display early performance plateaus, which can limit further learning and improvement.

Fig.5. ROC curves for binary (top), tertiary (middle), and multi-class (bottom) classifications across IRV2, VGG19, DN169, PVGNet, and X-ViT.

Fig.6. Confusion matrices across three classification tasks:(a) Binary classification,(b) Tertiary classification, and(c) Multi-class classification. Each subFig. presents results from five models (left to right): InceptionResNetV2 (IRV2), VGG19, DenseNet169 (DN169), PVGNet, and X-ViT.

Table 2. Binary classification performance of five models (IRV2 – InceptionResNetV2, DN169 – DenseNet169, X-ViT – Xception + Vision Transformer)

Metrics	Condition	IRV2	VGG19	DN169	PVGNet	X-ViT
AUC (%)		97.87	99.32	99.56	99.48	98.95
F1 score (%)	Healthy	94.69	96.37	96.01	97.01	95.82
	Unhealthy	91.11	94.02	93.29	95.16	92.92
Precision (%)	Healthy	95.00	97.21	96.19	98.52	95.70
	Unhealthy	90.61	92.70	92.98	92.86	93.13
Sensitivity (%)	Healthy	94.69	95.56	95.82	95.56	96.96
	Unhealthy	91.11	95.36	93.60	97.57	95.02
Specificity (%)		91.61	95.36	93.60	95.59	92.71
Accuracy (%)		93.35	95.48	94.99	96.31	94.75

Table 3. Tertiary classification performance of five models (IRV2 – InceptionResNetV2, DN169 – DenseNet169, X-ViT – Xception + Vision Transformer)

Metrics	Condition	IRv2	VGG19	DN169	PVGNet	X-ViT
AUC (%)	Healthy	98.71	99.44	99.49	99.61	99.21
	Functional	98.43	99.37	99.40	99.74	99.25
	Organic	99.77	99.88	99.75	99.71	99.77
F1 score (%)	Healthy	97.03	96.73	97.12	97.82	96.85
	Functional	91.24	93.44	91.84	94.47	92.09
	Organic	94.85	92.81	95.17	94.81	94.12
Precision (%)	Healthy	98.13	98.91	97.37	99.06	97.23
	Functional	88.76	90.73	91.46	91.22	91.16
	Organic	93.88	87.65	94.52	94.48	93.79
Sensitivity (%)	Healthy	95.95	94.64	96.86	96.60	96.47
	Functional	93.85	96.31	92.21	97.95	93.03
	Organic	95.83	98.61	95.83	95.14	94.44
Specificity (%)	Healthy	98.05	97.94	94.85	98.19	94.59
	Functional	96.91	97.36	97.69	97.47	97.58
	Organic	99.20	98.02	99.21	99.21	99.11
Accuracy (%)		95.49	95.49	95.75	96.70	95.49

Table 4. Multi-class classification performance of five models (IRV2 – InceptionResNetV2, DN169 – DenseNet169, X-ViT – Xception + Vision Transformer)

Metrics	Conditions	IRv2	VGG19	DN169	PVGNet	X-ViT
AUC (%)	Healthy	98.95	99.57	98.64	99.79	98.33
	MTD	99.42	99.58	98.89	99.83	97.75
	Atrophy	97.80	99.95	98.01	99.96	99.91
	Nodules	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
	Edema	97.36	99.66	99.79	99.79	99.27
F1 score (%)	Healthy	96.52	97.63	97.13	98.22	97.30
	MTD	91.20	93.93	90.69	95.83	93.39
	Atrophy	91.67	94.74	84.51	92.11	89.47
	Nodules	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	95.83
	Edema	91.89	94.74	97.14	94.74	88.89
Precision (%)	Healthy	97.09	98.15	98.12	99.33	97.88
	MTD	89.06	92.80	89.62	93.05	91.37
	Atrophy	91.67	90.00	75.00	87.50	85.00
	Nodules	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
	Edema	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Sensitivity (%)	Healthy	95.95	97.12	96.15	97.12	96.73
	MTD	93.44	95.08	91.79	98.77	95.49
	Atrophy	91.67	100.0	96.77	97.22	94.44
	Nodules	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	92.00
	Edema	85.00	90.00	94.44	90.00	80.00
Specificity (%)	Healthy	93.23	95.69	94.46	98.46	95.08
	MTD	96.69	97.87	97.99	97.87	97.40
	Atrophy	99.72	99.62	99.72	99.53	99.43
	Nodules	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
	Edema	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Accuracy (%)		95.14	96.70	96.51	97.43	95.96

Table 2 shows that PVGNet performs best with an accuracy of 96.31%. VGG19 follows at 95.48%, and DenseNet169 comes close at 94.99%.

Although DenseNet169 gives the highest AUC of 99.56%, meaning it separates the two classes very well, PVGNet's AUC of 99.48% is almost the same. What makes PVGNet stand out is how well it balances accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity instead of being strong in just one area. PVGNet also gives the highest F1-scores for both classes 97.01% for Healthy and 95.16% for Unhealthy showing that it can handle both categories reliably without bias. The confusion matrices in Fig. 6(a) make this clearer.

IRV2 shown first from the left struggles to detect Unhealthy cases misclassifying 38 of them as Healthy which means a high false-negative rate. VGG19 shown next performs better with 432 correct Unhealthy detections and only 21 missed. DenseNet169 is close but misses slightly more (29). PVGNet shown fourth clearly performs the best. It misses only 11 Unhealthy cases and correctly finds 442 which shows improved learning.

Though DenseNet169 has a slightly higher AUC, PVGNet stays nearly close while keeping false negatives much lower. This balance detecting more Unhealthy cases without losing precision is what matters most in voice disorder detection. Overall, these results show that PVGNet's hybrid CNN-attention setup can capture fine visual details in PVG images more effectively than the other models. It doesn't just classify it learns the subtle cues that distinguish healthy from disordered patterns

Evaluation of Tertiary Classification Performance

In Fig. 4(b) PVGNet generalizes well since the training and validation accuracy curves almost overlap, which points to a low risk of overfitting. Some baselines do reasonably well but don't generalize as strongly, a few clearly overfit with wide gaps between training and validation. Others stay stable yet plateau early by limiting further gains. Table 3 shows the same. PVGNet shows the highest test accuracy at 96.70%, ahead of DenseNet169 (95.75%), VGG19 (95.49%), and X-ViT (95.49%). Also gives the high F1-scores for Healthy (97.82%) and Functional (94.47%). DenseNet169 leads on Organic with an F1 of 95.17%, and PVGNet is close at 94.81%. Among the baselines IRV2 and VGG19 show clear overfitting with large train-val gaps but DenseNet169 is steadier but levels off early. PVGNet shows slight signs of overfitting in place but keeps

validation accuracy high, unlike models that struggle more generalization.

The confusion matrices in Fig. 6(b) shows DenseNet169 is marginally best (741 correct) for healthy cases. Then PVGNet and X-ViT (739 and 738) but IRV2 and VGG19 misclassify 24 and 22 Healthy. For Functional cases, PVGNet performs well with only 5 errors (4 Healthy, 1 Organic). X-ViT makes more mispredictions (15 Healthy, 2 Organic), DenseNet169 misclassifies 18, and IRV2 (13 Healthy, 5 Organic). For Organic cases, DenseNet169 again leads (2 Healthy, 4 Functional). PVGNet stays close (3 Healthy, 4 Functional). X-ViT shows slightly higher errors (6 as Healthy, 2 as Functional), and IRV2 trails (5 Functional, 1 Healthy).

Fig. 5(b) provides the ROC view. PVGNet's micro-average AUC is 99.80%. It also has the highest class AUCs for Healthy of 99.61% and Functional of 99.74%. Tertiary performance mirrors the binary case: high accuracy, balanced errors, and good generalization.

This behavior reflects the attention blocks focusing on the most informative PVG informations. That focus helps PVGNet keep false decisions low without giving up separability, which explains its strong accuracy and reliable class wise detection.

Evaluation of Multi-class Classification Performance

PVGNet shows smooth convergence for both training and validation with minimal fluctuation indicating stable learning and strong generalization in Fig. 4(c). Several baselines require more epochs to stabilize and improve more gradually others show marked variation in validation accuracy suggesting data sensitivity and potential instability.

PVGNet shows mild overfitting in places yet validation accuracy remains high unlike models with weaker generalization. Table 4 is consistent with these patterns. PVGNet reports the highest test accuracy (97.43%) and strong overall classification performance, and it attains the top AUC for most conditions. Class-wise results favor PVGNet: F1, precision, specificity, and sensitivity remain high, with F1 of 98.22% (Healthy), 95.83% (MTD), and 92.11% (Atrophy).

VGG19 is close overall but its sensitivity and F1 lags in some settings. DenseNet169 is competitive yet drops on MTD (90.69% F1) and Atrophy (84.51% F1), lowering its overall score. IRV2 is weaker for MTD (91.20% F1). X-ViT generalizes least well, particularly for Atrophy (89.47% F1) and Edema (88.89% F1).

The confusion matrices in Fig. 6(c) clarify these outcomes. PVGNet (fourth matrix) gives few errors, with correct counts of 763 Healthy, 241 MTD, 34 Atrophy, 25 Nodules, and 18 Edema. IRV2 (first) and DenseNet169 (third) misclassify a noticeable number of Healthy and MTD samples.

VGG19 (second) performs well but produces more false positives than PVGNet. X-ViT (fifth) shows several errors in MTD, Atrophy, and Edema. Considering the learning curves (Fig. 4(c)), test metrics (Table 4), and confusion matrices (Fig. 6(c)) together, PVGNet provides the most favorable balance of accuracy, generalization, and class-wise reliability for this multi-class task.

VGG19 is a strong comparator, but PVGNet's higher sensitivity, stronger F1 scores, and lower misclassification rates make it the more suitable choice for vocal-fold multi-class classification. Finally, Fig. 5(c) presents the ROC analysis. PVGNet's micro-average AUC is 99.95%, and it records the highest per-class AUCs 99.79% (Healthy), 99.83% (MTD), 99.96% (Atrophy), 100% (Nodules), and 99.79% (Edema) indicating excellent separability across all categories and a clear margin over IRV2, VGG19, DenseNet169, and X-ViT.

DISCUSSION

Binary classification result is an evident that PVGNet's hybrid CNN-attention mechanism extracts intricate and informative PVG patterns and improves feature recognition, performing better than other models.

This balance between precision and sensitivity is specially important in clinical voice diagnostics where false negatives may delay correct treatment. PVGNet also shows consistent reliability across tertiary and multiclass tasks.

PVGNet shows potential for real-world clinical application by maintaining solid performance across diverse voice disorder categories,

Though DenseNet169 produces high AUCs in some cases PVGNet maintains better balance in sensitivity and F1-scores across conditions mainly where misclassification can have major diagnostic consequences.

This further supports its suitability for use in automated screening or adjunct diagnostic tools for otolaryngologists.

CONCLUSION

This study presents PVGNet, a custom DL framework that produces high accuracy, good generalisation, and balanced performance across binary, tertiary, and multi-class classification tasks. Its hybrid architecture that combines multiscale feature extraction with attention mechanisms learns diagnostically relevant vibration features and reduces overfitting. These outcomes show the potential of attention-enhanced models like PVGNet in advancing automated voice-disorder assessment and their integration into clinical decision-support systems.

In future studies, visualization maps such as Grad-CAM will be explored to understand vibration regions, improving interpretability and clinician trust. Although this work is limited to a single HSV dataset, model behavior may vary under real-world clinical conditions with greater variability and noise. Future research will include domain-adaptation techniques, and multi-fold cross-validation to further strengthen generalizability. The model will eventually be expanded and refined into clinically deployable software tool.

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RANDOMIZED QUADRATURE WITH PERIODIC KERNELS: APPLICATIONS TO CAVALIERI VOLUME ESTIMATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper studies randomized algorithms for unbiased numerical integration of d -dimensional periodic functions using kernel-based quadrature rules, with particular emphasis on rules induced by periodic radial basis function (RBF) kernels. The integration points are either deterministically generated or locally perturbed and then randomly shifted, introducing structured randomness into the scheme. The analysis builds on tools from the theory of reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces (RKHS) and Sobolev interpolation. It is shown that the resulting estimators achieve optimal variance decay rates, effectively capturing the smoothness of the integrand even when the assumed regularity is overestimated. The work is motivated by Cavalieri volume estimation, a classical problem in stereology. The theoretical results generalize this framework to higher dimensions and provide a Fourier-based perspective on smoothness, yielding a flexible and mathematically grounded alternative for randomized quadrature with periodic structure.

Keywords: Cavalieri volume estimation, kernel quadrature, radial basis functions, reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces, stereological methods.

INTRODUCTION

In this work, we focus on estimating the integral of a real, compactly supported function f , denoted by $V(f)$:

$$V(f) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} f(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x}, \quad (1)$$

using a weighted sum of function evaluations at points that are randomly translated modulo a fixed period (periodic structure). The original motivation for this problem is described below.

Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$. The volume of a bounded n -dimensional object can be calculated using Cavalieri's principle, which states that the volume is determined by integrating the measurements of its $(n - 1)$ -dimensional sections along a fixed axis. This method can be extended to higher dimensions by considering $(n - d)$ -dimensional sections for integers $1 \leq d < n$, leading to integrals over d -dimensional spaces. While this problem has been widely studied in the one-dimensional case ($d = 1$) due to its applications in volume estimation in stereology—see, e.g., Cruz-Orive (2024) and references therein—its generalization to higher dimensions is less well understood and has received comparatively little attention; see, however, the related high-dimensional works of Janáček (2006; 2008); Janacek and Jirak (2019).

In practical terms, stereological applications typically estimate the volume of a solid $Y \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ by taking planar sections of Y , intersecting it with planes orthogonal to a fixed axis and measuring the resulting areas. Here, in Eq. (1), the function $f(x)$ represents the area of intersection of the solid Y with a plane positioned at $x \in \mathbb{R}$, and it is zero outside a bounded interval; this is the classical Cavalieri setting. However, several practically relevant examples involve multiple variables. For instance, two-dimensional integrals (i.e., $d = 2$), modeled by fiber lengths (i.e., sections along lines), can be found in electron microscopy (Ziegel *et al.*, 2010). Additionally, other widely used formulations for volume estimation in stereology consider periodic two-dimensional integrals, such as in the case of the nucleator (González-Villa *et al.*, 2017; Pausinger *et al.*, 2019).

The most natural method for sectioning physical objects into slices (i.e., $d = 1$) is by using cuts of uniform thickness. The classical Cavalieri estimator of the integral in Eq. (1) is constructed as a Riemann sum based on evaluations of f at systematically sampled equidistant points with thickness $t > 0$:

$$\hat{V}(f) = t \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} f(tk + U), \quad (2)$$

where U is a uniformly distributed random shift within the period $[0, t)$, as described in, for example, Baddeley

and Jensen (2004, Chapter 7). While this method is widely used in stereological problems and works well under ideal conditions, it faces limitations when sampling points are not equidistant (Baddeley *et al.*, 2006; Ziegel *et al.*, 2010; 2011), particularly due to local random errors arising from models with different patterns. Recently, significant improvements have been made using Newton-Cotes estimators (Kiderlen and Dorph-Petersen, 2017; Stehr and Kiderlen, 2020a;b; Stehr *et al.*, 2022), which employ Newton-Cotes quadrature rules to achieve optimal variance decay rates, even under very general sampling conditions. However, generalizing these results to multidimensional settings ($d \geq 1$) remains challenging due to increased computational complexity and the absence of a general framework for extending Newton–Cotes rules themselves to integrals in several variables.

An additional challenge is the smoothness assumption of f , which plays a crucial role in the variance behavior of estimators of $V(f)$. In 1D, classical stereology uses $(m, 1)$ -piecewise smoothness: f is $(m-1)$ times continuously differentiable, and the m -th and $(m+1)$ -st derivatives exist and are continuous except at finitely many points with finite jumps. While the classical Cavalieri estimator has been extended to handle fractional smoothness (García-Fiñana and Cruz-Orive, 2004; García-Fiñana, 2006), and Newton–Cotes estimators have broadened the analysis for integer-order smoothness (Stehr and Kiderlen, 2020b; 2025), the two frameworks remain somewhat disjoint—each tied to either fractional or integer notions of smoothness. This separation limits their general applicability.

A recent related work (Soto, 2025) has shown, in the classical 1D Cavalieri setting, that a Fourier-decay smoothness condition subsumes those one-dimensional notions and is essentially optimal: an algebraic variance-decay assumption implies the corresponding Fourier-decay rate (a matching converse result). Building on that insight, we consider a unified higher-dimensional smoothness framework based on the decay of Fourier coefficients, leveraging the well-known link between Fourier decay and function regularity.

Concretely, we estimate the parameter in Eq. (1) using randomized kernel-based quadrature rules grounded in Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Space (RKHS) theory. These techniques have been successfully applied in various contexts, including Bayesian quadrature (O’Hagan, 1991; Briol *et al.*, 2015; 2019) and quasi-Monte Carlo integration (Novak and Woźniakowski, 2012; Dick *et al.*, 2013; 2014). By leveraging kernels to capture

the smoothness properties of the function $f(x)$, these methods accelerate convergence compared to Monte Carlo integration, even in misspecified settings (Dick, 2007; 2008; Fuselier *et al.*, 2014; Oates and Girolami, 2016; Kanagawa *et al.*, 2016). Specifically, we investigate scenarios with overestimated smoothness within (isotropic) Sobolev spaces, as discussed in previous works on spheres (Fuselier *et al.*, 2014) and on standard Euclidean spaces using a generic approach (Kanagawa *et al.*, 2020). However, our work differs in that we develop a framework specifically tailored to practitioners of stereology, focusing on kernel-based quadrature rules defined on tori, motivated by periodic models such as the Cavalieri estimator in Eq. (2), which is a function with period t .

It is worth noting that this is not the first time an RKHS-based approach has been used with stereological applications in mind: Pausinger *et al.* (2019) employed Korobov spaces to analyse the variance of the nucleator under different point designs, such as lattice rules and optimal point configurations. Moreover, from a more geometric perspective, Janacek and Jirak (2019) extended the classical Kendall–Hlawka–Matheron variance formula to isotropic uniform systematic sampling with periodic grids induced by point lattices in \mathbb{R}^d , focusing on boundary effects for sets of finite perimeter. In contrast, our strategy takes a different approach to the problem, focusing on Sobolev-space error estimates and on Bayesian adaptive weights in the construction of the quadrature rules.

PRELIMINARIES AND BASIC NOTATION

We begin by recalling well-established geometric concepts related to interpolation errors in Riemannian manifolds, see, for instance, Narcowich *et al.* (2002; 2006); Fuselier and Wright (2012); Kanagawa *et al.* (2020). Let T be a positive real number, and let X be a finite set of points in $[0, T]^d$, which may be either deterministic or stochastic. Using boldface for vectors and italics for their coordinates, we define the following measures:

- Separation radius:

$$q_{X,T} = \frac{1}{2} \min_{\mathbf{x} \neq \mathbf{y} \in X} D_T^d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}),$$

- Fill distance:

$$h_{X,T} = \sup_{\mathbf{z} \in [0, T]^d} \min_{\mathbf{x} \in X} D_T^d(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{x}),$$

– Mesh ratio:

$$\rho_{X,T} = \frac{h_{X,T}}{q_{X,T}},$$

where $D_T^d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ denotes the geodesic distance between \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} within $[0, T]^d$, viewed as a (flat) torus:

$$D_T^d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^d \left(\min(|x_i - y_i|, T - |x_i - y_i|)^2 \right) \right)^{1/2}.$$

In the following, we show the value of the aforementioned measures for examples based on point sets derived from periodic one-dimensional models, originally introduced in the context of stereological applications (Ziegel *et al.*, 2010; 2011; Stehr and Kiderlen, 2020a; Stehr *et al.*, 2022).

Example 1 (Equidistant Grid). *Let t and m be positive real and integer numbers, respectively. Consider $T = mt$ and the following lattice $Y = t\mathbb{Z}^d$. Then, we have that $X = Y \cap [0, T]^d$ is a set of m^d points in $[0, T]^d$ with period $[0, t]^d$, satisfying:*

$$q_{X,T} = \frac{t}{2}, \quad h_{X,T} = \frac{\sqrt{d}}{2}t, \quad \rho_{X,T} = \sqrt{d}.$$

Example 2 (Perturbed Grid). *Let t and m be positive real and integer numbers, respectively. Consider $T = (m+2)t$ and the stochastically perturbed lattice*

$$Y = \{t(\mathbf{k} + E_{\mathbf{k}}) : \mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d\},$$

where $(E_{\mathbf{k}})_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d}$ are i.i.d. random vectors in \mathbb{R}^d with $\|E_{\mathbf{k}}\|_2 \leq \frac{\lambda}{2}$ where $0 < \lambda < 1$. Define

$$X = \{t(\mathbf{k} + E_{\mathbf{k}}) \bmod T : \mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d, t\mathbf{k} \in [0, T]^d\},$$

where $\bmod T$ denotes componentwise reduction to $[0, T]^d$. Then X consists of exactly $(m+2)^d$ points in $[0, T]^d$ and

$$q_{X,T} \geq \frac{t}{2}(1-\lambda), \quad h_{X,T} \leq \frac{t}{2}(\sqrt{d} + \lambda), \quad \rho_{X,T} \leq \frac{\sqrt{d} + \lambda}{1-\lambda}.$$

Moreover, if U is a uniformly distributed random shift on $[0, T]^d$ and independent of $(E_{\mathbf{k}})$, then $(X+U) \bmod T \cap [0, mt]^d$ and $(Y+U) \cap [0, mt]^d$ are identically distributed.

SMOOTHNESS ASSUMPTIONS AND PERIODIC RKHS

Let $L_c^2(\mathbb{R}^d)$ denote the space of square-integrable functions on \mathbb{R}^d with compact essential support, i.e., functions $f \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^d)$ such that

$$S(f) = \mathbb{R}^d \setminus \bigcup \{U \subset \mathbb{R}^d : U \text{ open, } f = 0 \text{ a.e. on } U\}$$

¹If f is pointwise-defined, then the essential support coincides with the usual topological support, i.e., $S(f) = \text{cl}\{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^d : f(\mathbf{x}) \neq 0\}$.

is compact (Lieb and Loss, 2001, Section 1.5).¹

Let $s > d/2$ be a smoothness parameter. We say that $r_s : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ is a rate function if it satisfies the following conditions:

$$\sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d} \frac{1}{r_s^2\left(\frac{\mathbf{k}}{T}\right)} < \infty, \quad r_s(\mathbf{0}) = 1 \quad \text{for all } T > 0.$$

Consider the Fourier-decay-type function space (see, e.g., Korobov (1963); Sloan (1985); Niederreiter (1992)):

$$\varepsilon_{r_s}(\mathbb{R}^d) = \left\{ f \in L_c^2(\mathbb{R}^d) : \exists C > 0 \text{ such that } |\hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\xi})| \leq \frac{C}{r_s(\boldsymbol{\xi})} \quad \forall \boldsymbol{\xi} \in \mathbb{R}^d \right\}, \quad (3)$$

where $\hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ denotes the Fourier transform of f at $\boldsymbol{\xi} \in \mathbb{R}^d$, defined as:

$$\hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-2\pi i \boldsymbol{\xi} \cdot \mathbf{x}} d\mathbf{x},$$

with $\boldsymbol{\xi} \cdot \mathbf{x}$ denoting the standard dot product.

Let $f \in L_c^2(\mathbb{R}^d)$. Without loss of generality, by translation we may assume $S(f) \subseteq [0, T]^d$ for some $T > 0$. The T -periodic extension of f is defined by

$$f_T(\mathbf{x}) = f(\mathbf{x} \bmod T), \quad \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^d.$$

The T -periodic covariogram of f , denoted by g_T , is defined as the following integral function:

$$g_T(\mathbf{z}) = \int_{[0, T]^d} f_T(\mathbf{x}) f_T(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{z}) d\mathbf{x}, \quad \mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^d.$$

We summarize its basic properties in the following lemma (cf. Gual-Arnau and Cruz-Orive (2002, Lemma 3.2) for related arguments). We abuse the notation by writing the Fourier coefficients at $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d$ of f_T , and of any T -periodic function, as:

$$\hat{f}_T(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{1}{T^d} \int_{[0, T]^d} f_T(\mathbf{x}) e^{-\frac{2\pi i}{T} \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}} d\mathbf{x}.$$

Lemma 3.1. *Let $f \in L_c^2(\mathbb{R}^d)$ and let g_T be its T -periodic covariogram, then:*

(i) $g_T = f_T * \check{f}_T$ where $\check{f}_T(\mathbf{x}) = f_T(-\mathbf{x})$ and $*$ denotes the convolution on the torus.

(ii) $\hat{g}_T(\mathbf{k}) = T^d |\hat{f}_T(\mathbf{k})|^2$.

(iii) $\int_{[0, T]^d} g_T(\mathbf{z}) d\mathbf{z} = V(f)^2$.

Proof. By periodicity and the change of variables $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{z}$, we have

$$g_T(\mathbf{z}) = \int_{[0,T]^d} f_T(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z}) f_T(\mathbf{y}) d\mathbf{y} = (f_T * \check{f}_T)(\mathbf{z}).$$

Since $g_T = f_T * \check{f}_T$ we get (f is real-valued)

$$\hat{g}_T = T^d |\hat{f}_T|^2. \quad (4)$$

Lastly, an application of Fubini's theorem shows $\int_{[0,T]^d} g_T(\mathbf{z}) d\mathbf{z} = V(f)^2$. \square

We now introduce the RKHS that characterizes the smoothness properties of the T -periodic covariogram.

Let $T > 0$ and $L_{\text{per}}^2([0,T]^d)$ be the space of T -periodic square-integrable functions on $[0,T]^d$. Consider

$$\mathcal{H}_{r_s}([0,T]^d) = \left\{ u \in L_{\text{per}}^2([0,T]^d) : \|u\|_{r_s} < \infty \right\},$$

where

$$\|u\|_{r_s}^2 = \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d} r_s^2\left(\frac{\mathbf{k}}{T}\right) |\hat{u}(\mathbf{k})|^2.$$

Endowed with the inner product

$$\langle u, v \rangle_{r_s} = \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d} r_s^2\left(\frac{\mathbf{k}}{T}\right) \hat{u}(\mathbf{k}) \overline{\hat{v}(\mathbf{k})}, \quad u, v \in \mathcal{H}_{r_s}([0,T]^d),$$

this forms an RKHS with kernel (see, e.g., Krieger *et al.* (2023, Example 4) and (Leobacher and Pillichshammer, 2014, Definition 4.13))

$$K_{r_s}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d} \frac{e^{\frac{2\pi i}{T} \mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}}{r_s^2\left(\frac{\mathbf{k}}{T}\right)}, \quad \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in [0,T]^d.$$

The global integral of the kernel above has a closed form:

$$\int_{[0,T]^d} K_{r_s}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) d\mathbf{y} = T^d. \quad (5)$$

In addition, the Fourier coefficient of $K_{r_s}(\cdot, \mathbf{y})$ at \mathbf{k} is given by:

$$\hat{K}_{r_s}(\cdot, \mathbf{y})(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{e^{-\frac{2\pi i}{T} \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{y}}}{r_s^2\left(\frac{\mathbf{k}}{T}\right)}. \quad (6)$$

Example 3 (Sobolev space). *Let $s > d/2$. The RKHS $\mathcal{H}_{r_s}([0,T]^d)$ is norm equivalent to the T -periodic Sobolev space $H_{\text{per}}^s([0,T]^d)$, if the associated rate function r_s satisfies,*

$$\frac{C_1}{(1 + \|\boldsymbol{\xi}\|^2)^s} \leq \frac{1}{r_s^2(\boldsymbol{\xi})} \leq \frac{C_2}{(1 + \|\boldsymbol{\xi}\|^2)^s} \quad (7)$$

where C_1, C_2 are positive constants independent of $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ (Narcowich *et al.*, 2002; Cobos *et al.*, 2016).

Lemma 3.2. *If $f \in \varepsilon_{r_s}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, then $g_T \in \mathcal{H}_{r_s}([0,T]^d)$.*

Proof. By Lemma 3.1(ii), $\hat{g}_T(\mathbf{k}) = T^d |\hat{f}_T(\mathbf{k})|^2$ and, since $S(f) \subseteq [0,T]^d$, we have $\hat{f}_T(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{1}{T^d} \hat{f}\left(\frac{\mathbf{k}}{T}\right)$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \|g_T\|_{r_s}^2 &= \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d} r_s^2\left(\frac{\mathbf{k}}{T}\right) |\hat{g}_T(\mathbf{k})|^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{(T^d)^2} \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d} r_s^2\left(\frac{\mathbf{k}}{T}\right) |\hat{f}\left(\frac{\mathbf{k}}{T}\right)|^4. \end{aligned}$$

Since $f \in \varepsilon_{r_s}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, there exists $C > 0$ such that $|\hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\xi})| \leq C/r_s(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ for all $\boldsymbol{\xi}$. Thus

$$\|g_T\|_{r_s}^2 \leq \frac{C^4}{(T^d)^2} \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d} \frac{1}{r_s^2\left(\frac{\mathbf{k}}{T}\right)} < \infty,$$

because r_s is a rate function. \square

Suppose the rate function r_s satisfies Eq. (7) and that $f \in \varepsilon_{r_s}(\mathbb{R}^d)$. Then, by the previous lemma, the T -periodic covariogram g_T is a function that belongs to an RKHS norm-equivalent to the Sobolev space $H_{\text{per}}^s([0,T]^d)$. This is the scenario we focus on in this work. Below, we briefly outline a well-understood approach for constructing an RKHS equivalent to the periodic Sobolev space on $[0,T]^d$.

Let $\ell \geq 2d$. The d -dimensional torus $([0,T]^d, D_T^d)$ admits a smooth embedding into \mathbb{R}^ℓ , which allows us to define suitable kernels by restricting a positive definite kernel originally defined on $\mathbb{R}^\ell \times \mathbb{R}^\ell$. Given a smoothness parameter $\tau > (\ell - d)/2$ a fundamental class of kernels in \mathbb{R}^ℓ is provided by radial basis functions (RBFs), which depend only on the Euclidean distance:

$$\Phi_\tau(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \phi_\tau(\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}\|), \quad \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^\ell, \quad (8)$$

where $\phi_\tau : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is univariate.

When the Fourier transform of ϕ_τ decays like $(1 + \|\boldsymbol{\xi}\|^2)^{-\tau}$, the RKHS associated with ϕ_τ is norm-equivalent (Wendland, 2004, Section 10) to the standard Sobolev space $H^\tau(\mathbb{R}^\ell)$. If we restrict this RKHS to the smooth embedding of the torus $([0,T]^d, D_T^d)$, we obtain an RKHS that is norm-equivalent (Fuselier and Wright, 2012, Theorem 5) to the Sobolev space

$$H_{\text{per}}^{\tau - (\ell - d)/2}([0,T]^d).$$

We recall that examples of RBFs include the Matérn and Wendland kernels (Matérn, 2013; Wendland, 1995), which are widely used in scattered data approximation and spatial statistics.

By the Moore–Aronszajn theorem (Aronszajn, 1950), it is well known that, for every positive definite kernel $\varphi : [0, T]^d \times [0, T]^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, there exists a unique RKHS with φ as reproducing kernel. We denote this space by $\mathcal{H}_\varphi([0, T]^d)$. For instance, $\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_\tau}([0, T]^d)$ denotes the RKHS associated with the kernel Φ_τ in Eq. (8), where, by a slight abuse of notation, we use Φ_τ both for the RBF on \mathbb{R}^ℓ and for its restriction to the embedded torus via the fixed smooth embedding.

PERIODIC KERNEL-BASED ESTIMATORS AND VARIANCE

In what follows, we fix $s > d/2$ and $f \in \mathcal{E}_s(\mathbb{R}^d)$ with $S(f) \subseteq [0, T]^d$ for some $T > 0$. Additionally, let $X = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_n\} \subset [0, T]^d$ be a deterministic set of n points, and let U be a random variable uniformly distributed on $[0, T]^d$. To approximate the integral $V(f)$ of f , we define the shift-randomized weighted sum:

$$\hat{V}_T(f) = \sum_{i=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) f_T(\mathbf{x}_i + U), \quad (9)$$

where $w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) \in \mathbb{R}$ are weights that may depend measurably on the sample location \mathbf{x}_i and all the points of the point set X .

The bias and variance of the estimator $\hat{V}_T(f)$ have closed-form expressions.

Proposition 4.1. *The estimator $\hat{V}_T(f)$ is unbiased if and only if*

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) = T^d. \quad (10)$$

Furthermore, the variance of $\hat{V}_T(f)$ is given by:

$$\text{var}(\hat{V}_T(f)) = \frac{1}{T^d} \langle g_T, h_T \rangle_{r_s}, \quad (11)$$

where the function $h_T : [0, T]^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as follows :

$$h_T(\cdot) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) w(\mathbf{x}_j, X) K_{r_s}(\cdot, \mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j) - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) \right)^2.$$

Proof. Firstly, for the unbiasedness, a straightforward calculation yields the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\hat{V}_T(f)] &= \frac{1}{T^d} \int_{[0, T]^d} \sum_{i=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) f_T(\mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{u}) \, d\mathbf{u} \\ &= \frac{1}{T^d} \sum_{i=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) \int_{[0, T]^d} f_T(\mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{u}) \, d\mathbf{u} \\ &= \frac{1}{T^d} \sum_{i=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) \int_{[0, T]^d + \mathbf{x}_i} f_T(\mathbf{u}) \, d\mathbf{u} \\ &= \frac{1}{T^d} \left(\int_{[0, T]^d} f_T(\mathbf{u}) \, d\mathbf{u} \right) \sum_{i=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X). \end{aligned}$$

Secondly, the variance of $\hat{V}_T(f)$ can be computed using item (iii) of Lemma 3.1, as follows:

$$\text{var}(\hat{V}_T(f)) = \mathbb{E}[(\hat{V}_T(f))^2] - \left(\frac{1}{T^d} \sum_{i=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) \right)^2 \left(\int_{[0, T]^d} g_T(\mathbf{z}) \, d\mathbf{z} \right).$$

We just have to expand the first term. Applying the definition of expected value we obtain that:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[(\hat{V}_T(f))^2] &= \frac{1}{T^d} \int_{[0, T]^d} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) f_T(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{z}) \right)^2 \, d\mathbf{z} \\ &= \frac{1}{T^d} \int_{[0, T]^d} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) w(\mathbf{x}_j, X) f_T(\mathbf{z} + \mathbf{x}_i) f_T(\mathbf{z} + \mathbf{x}_j) \, d\mathbf{z} \\ &= \frac{1}{T^d} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) w(\mathbf{x}_j, X) \int_{[0, T]^d} f_T(\mathbf{z} + \mathbf{x}_i) f_T(\mathbf{z} + \mathbf{x}_j) \, d\mathbf{z} \\ &= \frac{1}{T^d} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) w(\mathbf{x}_j, X) \int_{[0, T]^d} f_T(\mathbf{z}) f_T(\mathbf{z} + (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j)) \, d\mathbf{z} \\ &= \frac{1}{T^d} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) w(\mathbf{x}_j, X) g_T(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j). \end{aligned}$$

Note that, by Lemma 3.2, we have $g_T \in \mathcal{H}_{r_s}([0, T]^d)$. The reproducing property of the RKHS implies the following:

$$\langle g_T, K_{r_s}(\cdot, \mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j) \rangle_{r_s} = g_T(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j),$$

and also,

$$\left\langle g_T, \int_{[0, T]^d} K_{r_s}(\cdot, \mathbf{x}) \, d\mathbf{x} \right\rangle_{r_s} = \int_{[0, T]^d} g_T(\mathbf{x}) \, d\mathbf{x}.$$

Finally, Eq. (5) gives $\int_{[0, T]^d} K_{r_s}(\cdot, \mathbf{x}) \, d\mathbf{x} = T^d$ and by using basic properties of the inner product we finish the proof. \square

Since Equations (10) and (11) obtained in the previous proposition allow for matrix representation, we adopt the following matrix notation.

We define the vector of weights as a column vector:

$$\mathbf{w} = (w(\mathbf{x}_i, X))_{i=1}^n,$$

and the kernel matrix as:

$$\mathbf{K}_{r_s} = (K_{r_s}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j))_{i,j=1}^n.$$

In addition, we use $\mathbf{1}$ to denote the column vector of ones, and $\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{1} = \mathbf{w} \cdot \mathbf{1}$ represents the sum:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X),$$

where \mathbf{w}^\top is the transposed vector.

Let $\mathcal{H}_\varphi([0, T]^d)$ be an RKHS with reproducing kernel φ . The worst-case error (WCE) of $\mathcal{H}_\varphi([0, T]^d)$ for a point set $X = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_n\}$ and a vector of weights \mathbf{w} is defined as (see, e.g., Sloan (1985); Leobacher and Pillichshammer (2014); Kanagawa *et al.* (2020)):

$$e_X(\mathcal{H}_\varphi, \mathbf{w}) = \sup_{p \in \mathcal{H}_\varphi, \|p\|_\varphi \leq 1} \left| \int_{[0, T]^d} p(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} - \sum_{i=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) p(\mathbf{x}_i) \right|.$$

Moreover, the squared WCE is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_\varphi, \mathbf{w}) &= \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) w(\mathbf{x}_j, X) \varphi(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) - \\ &2 \sum_{i=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) \int_{[0, T]^d} \varphi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_i) d\mathbf{x} + \\ &\int_{[0, T]^d} \int_{[0, T]^d} \varphi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) d\mathbf{x} d\mathbf{y}. \end{aligned}$$

Specifically, if we take $\varphi = K_{r_s}$, then using Eq. (5), we can write the squared WCE in the following matrix form:

$$e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{r_s}, \mathbf{w}) = \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{K}_{r_s} \mathbf{w} - 2T^d \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{1} + (T^d)^2. \quad (12)$$

Proposition 4.2. *Let $f \in \varepsilon_{r_s}(\mathbb{R}^d)$. Assume that the vector of weights satisfies $\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{1} = T^d$. Then, the following inequality holds:*

$$\text{var}(\hat{V}_T(f)) \leq C e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{r_s}, \mathbf{w}), \quad (13)$$

for some constant $C > 0$ independent of X .

Proof. From Eq. (11), we know that the variance of $\hat{V}_T(f)$ can be expressed as:

$$\text{var}(\hat{V}_T(f)) = \frac{1}{T^d} \langle g_T, h_T \rangle_{r_s}.$$

Since $f \in \varepsilon_{r_s}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, and applying Eq. (4), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle g_T, h_T \rangle_{r_s} &= \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d} r_s^2 \left(\frac{\mathbf{k}}{T} \right) \hat{g}_T(\mathbf{k}) \overline{\hat{h}_T(\mathbf{k})} \\ &\leq \frac{C^2}{T^d} \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d} \overline{\hat{h}_T(\mathbf{k})}. \end{aligned}$$

Using the properties of the Fourier transform and complex conjugation $\mathbf{z} \mapsto \bar{\mathbf{z}}$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{\hat{h}_T(\mathbf{k})} &= \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w(\mathbf{x}_i, X) w(\mathbf{x}_j, X) \overline{\hat{K}_{r_s}(\cdot, \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})(\mathbf{k})} - \\ &(\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{1})^2 1_{\{\mathbf{0}\}}(\mathbf{k}), \end{aligned}$$

where $1_{\{\mathbf{0}\}}(\mathbf{k})$ is the indicator function that equals 1 when $\mathbf{k} = \mathbf{0}$ and 0 otherwise. Furthermore, using Eq. (6), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d} \overline{\hat{K}_{r_s}(\cdot, \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})(\mathbf{k})} &= \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d} \frac{e^{\frac{2\pi i}{T} \mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}}{r_s^2 \left(\frac{\mathbf{k}}{T} \right)} \\ &= K_{r_s}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}). \end{aligned}$$

Note that $\overline{\hat{h}_T(\mathbf{0})} = (\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{1})^2 - (\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{1})^2 = 0$. Therefore, we can write the sum as:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d} \overline{\hat{h}_T(\mathbf{k})} &= \mathbf{w}^\top (\mathbf{K}_{r_s} - \mathbf{1} \mathbf{1}^\top) \mathbf{w} \\ &= \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{K}_{r_s} \mathbf{w} - (\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{1})^2. \end{aligned}$$

This expression coincides with Eq. (12) if and only if $\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{1} = T^d$, thus completing the proof. \square

Now, consider the vector of weights \mathbf{w} that minimizes $e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{r_s}, \mathbf{w})$ given in Eq. (12). We denote this optimal vector by $\mathbf{w}_{0,s}$, which satisfies the following linear system:

$$\mathbf{K}_{r_s} \mathbf{w}_{0,s} = T^d \mathbf{1}.$$

These weights are used to define Bayesian quadrature rules (Kanagawa *et al.*, 2016; 2020), and are known as Bayesian weights. Moreover, since the kernel matrix \mathbf{K}_{r_s} is symmetric positive definite, we have the following relation:

$$\mathbf{w}_{0,s}^\top \mathbf{1} = T^d \mathbf{1}^\top \mathbf{K}_{r_s}^{-1} \mathbf{1} > 0.$$

Thus, the vector of optimal unbiased weights $\mathbf{w}_{u,s}$ is defined as (see, e.g., Karvonen *et al.* (2018, Section 2.3), where they were called normalised Bayesian cubature):

$$\mathbf{w}_{u,s} = T^d \frac{\mathbf{w}_{0,s}}{\mathbf{w}_{0,s}^\top \mathbf{1}}. \quad (14)$$

This vector minimizes the squared WCE in Eq. (12), subject to the constraint $\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{1} = T^d$.

Let φ be a positive definite kernel on $[0, T]^d \times [0, T]^d$. If φ is translation-invariant on the torus, i.e., $\varphi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \psi(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$ for some T -periodic ψ , and its global mean satisfies

$$\int_{[0, T]^d} \varphi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) d\mathbf{x} = T^d \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{y} \in [0, T]^d, \quad (15)$$

then the (φ) -optimal unbiased weights are exactly those in Eq. (14), with φ used in place of K_{r_s} . This applies, for example, to translation-invariant periodic kernels obtained by restricting an RBF to a smooth embedding of the torus into \mathbb{R}^ℓ (as discussed at the end of Section 3) and scaling it appropriately so that Eq. (15) holds.

Furthermore, let $p \in \mathcal{H}_\varphi([0, T]^d)$. We define the (φ) -interpolant of p at the point set X as the function:

$$I_X p(\cdot) = \sum_{i=1}^n c(\mathbf{x}_i, X) \varphi(\cdot, \mathbf{x}_i).$$

The vector of coefficients \mathbf{c} is determined by solving the linear system:

$$\mathbf{K}_\varphi \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{p}, \quad (16)$$

where \mathbf{K}_φ is the kernel matrix induced by φ on X , and \mathbf{p} is the vector of function values $p(\mathbf{x}_i)$ at the points of X . When the interpolant is constructed with an RBF kernel, we refer to $I_X p$ as the RBF interpolant. The proof of the following theorem relies on well-known results for RBF interpolation on smooth embedded submanifolds.

Theorem 4.3. *Let $s' \geq s > d/2$. Suppose $f \in \mathcal{E}_{r_s}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, where r_s satisfies Eq. (7). Set $\ell \geq 2d$ and let $\Phi_{\tau'}$ be an RBF kernel as in Eq. (8) with $\tau' - (\ell - d)/2 = s'$. Let $\mathbf{w}_{u, s'}$ denote the corresponding vector of optimal unbiased weights. Then, for $h_{X, T} \leq 1$, there exists some constant $C > 0$ independent of X such that*

$$\text{var}(\hat{V}_T(f)) \leq C h_{X, T}^{2s} \rho_{X, T}^{2(s'-s)}. \quad (17)$$

Proof. We set without loss of generality $\ell = 2d$. Let $\mathbf{w}_{0, s'}$ denote the $\Phi_{\tau'}$ -Bayesian weights computed using the kernel defined by the RBF $\Phi_{\tau'}$ as in Eq. (8), where $\tau' - d/2 = s'$.

We fix $p \in \mathcal{H}_{\Phi_\tau}([0, T]^d)$, with $\tau - d/2 = s$. It can be shown that a quadrature rule using Bayesian weights is identical to the integral of its corresponding interpolant (see, e.g., the proof of Kanagawa *et al.* (2020, Proposition 1)). The following holds:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w_{0, s'}(\mathbf{x}_i, X) p(\mathbf{x}_i) = \int_{[0, T]^d} I_X p(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x},$$

where $I_X p$ is the RBF interpolant of p computed by solving Eq. (16) with a kernel matrix $\mathbf{K}_{\Phi_{\tau'}}$ of smoothness $\tau' = s' + d/2$. Thus, the following quadrature error for the function p :

$$e_X(p, \mathbf{w}_{0, s'}) = \left| \int_{[0, T]^d} p(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} - \sum_{i=1}^n w_{0, s'}(\mathbf{x}_i, X) p(\mathbf{x}_i) \right|$$

can be bounded by the following L^2 -norm:

$$\begin{aligned} e_X(p, \mathbf{w}_{0, s'}) &\leq \|p - I_X p\|_{L^1} \\ &\leq (T^d)^{1/2} \|p - I_X p\|_{L^2}, \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality follows from Hölder's inequality on $[0, T]^d$. Since $I_X p$ is an RBF-interpolant, we can apply the result from Fuselier and Wright (2012, Theorem 17) (taking $\mu = 0, q = 2$ there). Thus, we obtain

$$\|p - I_X p\|_{L^2} \leq C_0 h_{X, T}^s \rho_{X, T}^{s'-s} \|p\|_{H_{\text{per}}^s}.$$

Moreover, since $\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_\tau}([0, T]^d)$ is norm-equivalent to $H_{\text{per}}^s([0, T]^d)$, we can ensure that

$$\|p - I_X p\|_{L^2} \leq C_1 h_{X, T}^s \rho_{X, T}^{s'-s} \|p\|_{\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_\tau}}$$

and

$$e_X(p, \mathbf{w}_{0, s'}) \leq (T^d)^{1/2} C_1 h_{X, T}^s \rho_{X, T}^{s'-s} \|p\|_{\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_\tau}}.$$

Thus, we have

$$e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_\tau}, \mathbf{w}_{0, s'}) \leq T^d C_1^2 h_{X, T}^{2s} \rho_{X, T}^{2(s'-s)}. \quad (18)$$

Now, we consider the vector of optimal unbiased weights $\mathbf{w}_{u, s'} = T^d \mathbf{w}_{0, s'} / \mathbf{w}_{0, s'}^\top \mathbf{1}$ (see Eq. (14)). By a straightforward calculation, $e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_\tau}, \mathbf{w}_{u, s'})$ can be written as $e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_\tau}, \mathbf{w}_{0, s'})$ plus an error term:

$$\begin{aligned} e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_\tau}, \mathbf{w}_{u, s'}) &= e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_\tau}, \mathbf{w}_{0, s'}) + \left(\frac{T^d - \mathbf{w}_{0, s'}^\top \mathbf{1}}{\mathbf{w}_{0, s'}^\top \mathbf{1}} \right) \cdot \\ &\left(\left(\frac{T^d + \mathbf{w}_{0, s'}^\top \mathbf{1}}{\mathbf{w}_{0, s'}^\top \mathbf{1}} \right) \mathbf{w}_{0, s'}^\top \mathbf{K}_{\Phi_\tau} \mathbf{w}_{0, s'} - 2T^d \mathbf{w}_{0, s'}^\top \mathbf{1} \right). \quad (19) \end{aligned}$$

In addition, we have $\Phi_{\tau'}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \phi_{\tau'}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$. Hence, it holds (we abuse notation for the embedding)

$$\phi_{\tau'}(\mathbf{z}) = \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d} \hat{\phi}_{\tau'_T}(\mathbf{k}) e^{\frac{2\pi i}{T} \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{z}}, \quad \hat{\phi}_{\tau'_T}(\mathbf{k}) \geq 0, \quad \hat{\phi}_{\tau'_T}(\mathbf{0}) = 1$$

by Eq. (15). Moreover, there exist constants $K_1, K_2 > 0$ such that

$$K_1 (1 + \|\mathbf{k}\|^2 / T^2)^{-s'} \leq \hat{\phi}_{\tau'_T}(\mathbf{k}) \leq K_2 (1 + \|\mathbf{k}\|^2 / T^2)^{-s'},$$

(see Eq. (7) with $\boldsymbol{\xi} = \mathbf{k}/T$ and s replaced by s'), so that

$$\alpha_{s'} = \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}^d} \hat{\phi}_{\tau' T}(\mathbf{k}) < \infty.$$

Define $\mathbf{w}_\beta = \beta \mathbf{1}$ with $\beta > 0$. Then the squared WCE in $\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_{\tau'}}([0, T]^d)$ satisfies

$$e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_{\tau'}}, \mathbf{w}_\beta) \leq (n^2 \alpha_{s'}) \beta^2 - (2nT^d) \beta + (T^d)^2, \quad (20)$$

where n is the size of X . If we take $\beta = \frac{T^d}{n\alpha_{s'}}$, then the value $(T^d)^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{\alpha_{s'}}\right)$ appears on the second side of Eq. (20). Consequently, we obtain the following:

$$\begin{aligned} T^d \left(T^d - \mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{1}\right) &= e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_{\tau'}}, \mathbf{w}_{0,s'}) \\ &\leq e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_{\tau'}}, \mathbf{w}_\beta) \\ &\leq (T^d)^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{\alpha_{s'}}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we get this lower bound for $\mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{1}$:

$$\frac{T^d}{\alpha_{s'}} \leq \mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{1}, \quad (21)$$

and we can ensure the existence of a positive constant $C_2 > 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{T^d - \mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{1}}{\mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{1}} &= \frac{T^d(T^d - \mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{1})}{T^d \mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{1}} \\ &= \frac{e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_{\tau'}}, \mathbf{w}_{0,s'})}{T^d \mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{1}} \\ &\leq \frac{\alpha_{s'}}{(T^d)^2} e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_{\tau'}}, \mathbf{w}_{0,s'}) \\ &\leq \frac{\alpha_{s'}}{(T^d)^2} C_2 h_{X,T}^{2s'}, \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where the first inequality is thanks to Eq. (21) and the second inequality follows from applying the same arguments as at the beginning of the proof when the RKHS has the same smoothness as the chosen Bayesian weights, and using the result from Fuselier and Wright (2012, Corollary 13).

Note that, applying Equations (18), (21) and (22) in Eq. (19), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_\tau}, \mathbf{w}_{u,s'}) &\leq T^d C_1^2 h_{X,T}^{2s} \rho_{X,T}^{2(s'-s)} + \\ &C_2 h_{X,T}^{2s'} \left(\frac{2\alpha_{s'}^2}{(T^d)^2} \mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{K}_{\Phi_\tau} \mathbf{w}_{0,s'} - 2 \right), \end{aligned}$$

because, using $\mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{1} \leq T^d$ and the lower bound $\mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{1} \geq T^d/\alpha_{s'}$ from Eq. (21), we have

$$\frac{T^d + \mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{1}}{\mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{1}} \leq 2\alpha_{s'} \quad \text{and} \quad -2T^d \mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{1} \leq -\frac{2(T^d)^2}{\alpha_{s'}}.$$

Moreover, from

$$\mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{K}_{\Phi_\tau} \mathbf{w}_{0,s'} = e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_\tau}, \mathbf{w}_{0,s'}) + 2T^d \mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{1} - (T^d)^2$$

and the same reasoning, we deduce

$$\mathbf{w}_{0,s'}^\top \mathbf{K}_{\Phi_\tau} \mathbf{w}_{0,s'} \leq T^d C_1^2 h_{X,T}^{2s} \rho_{X,T}^{2(s'-s)} + (T^d)^2.$$

Since $h_{X,T} \leq 1$ and worst-case errors of norm-equivalent RKHSs are equivalent up to constants, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{r_s}, \mathbf{w}_{u,s'}) &\leq C_3 e_X^2(\mathcal{H}_{\Phi_\tau}, \mathbf{w}_{u,s'}) \\ &\leq C_4 h_{X,T}^{2s} \rho_{X,T}^{2(s'-s)}, \end{aligned}$$

and one application of Eq. (13) finishes the proof. \square

As a result, the following corollary is an immediate consequence of applying the above theorem to the equidistant and perturbed grids.

Corollary 4.4. *Let X be either the equidistant grid or the perturbed grid (as in Examples 1 and 2). Assume $t > 0$ is small enough so that the corresponding fill distance satisfies $h_{X,T} \leq 1$. Define*

$$T_* = \inf\{L > 0 : S(f) \subseteq [0, L]^d\}$$

and set $m = \lceil T_*/t \rceil$. Consider $T = mt$ for the equidistant grid and $T = (m+2)t$ for the perturbed grid. Under the assumptions of Theorem 4.3, the estimator $\hat{V}_T(f)$ (with the $\Phi_{\tau'}$ -optimal unbiased weights) is unbiased, and its variance satisfies

$$\text{var}(\hat{V}_T(f)) \leq Ct^{2s}, \quad (23)$$

where $C > 0$ is a constant independent of t .

Proof. From Examples 1 and 2 we know that the fill distance is of order t and the mesh ratio remains bounded independently of t . Thus, Theorem 4.3 yields the claimed rate. Although the constant in Eq. (17) may depend on T , note that $T \in [T_*, T_* + 1]$ for the equidistant grid (and analogously for the perturbed grid). Therefore T remains uniformly bounded in terms of $S(f)$, independently of t . \square

To conclude this section, we note the following. For any translation-invariant periodic kernel

$$\varphi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \psi(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$$

satisfying Eq. (15), the kernel matrix \mathbf{K}_φ on an equidistant grid is (block-)circulant, hence $\mathbf{1}$ is an eigenvector:

$$\mathbf{K}_\varphi \mathbf{1} = \lambda \mathbf{1}, \quad \lambda = \sum_{j=1}^n \psi(\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_1)$$

Therefore $\mathbf{K}_\varphi^{-1} \mathbf{1} = (1/\lambda) \mathbf{1}$, and the φ -optimal unbiased weights (see Eq. (14)) reduce to

$$\mathbf{w}_{u,s} = \frac{T^d \mathbf{K}_\varphi^{-1} \mathbf{1}}{\mathbf{1}^\top \mathbf{K}_\varphi^{-1} \mathbf{1}} = \frac{T^d \frac{1}{\lambda} \mathbf{1}}{\frac{n}{\lambda}} = \frac{T^d}{n} \mathbf{1} = t^d \mathbf{1},$$

where $T = mt$, $n = m^d$. Thus, for the equidistant grid $X = t\mathbb{Z}^d \cap [0, T)^d$,

$$\hat{V}_T(f) = \sum_{i=1}^n t^d f_T(\mathbf{x}_i + U),$$

which coincides with the (multivariate) classical Cavalieri estimator. Therefore, our results extend the classical asymptotic theory in stereology to the function space $\mathcal{E}_{r_s}(\mathbb{R}^d)$.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

This section presents simulation experiments designed to empirically evaluate the theoretical results obtained. The focus is on the following one-dimensional function ($d = 1$), which has been previously studied in the context of the classical Cavalieri estimator (see, e.g., García-Fiñana and Cruz-Orive (2004)):

$$f_a(x) = \begin{cases} \pi(1 - x^2)^a, & \text{if } x \in [-1, 1], \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

The parameter a takes the following values: $a = 0.25, 0.75, 1.25, 1.75, 2.25, 2.75$. The Fourier transform of this function exhibits an algebraic decay with the following exponents: 1.25, 1.75, 2.25, 2.75, 3.25, 3.75, respectively.

The goal is to verify the decay behavior predicted by Eq. (23) for this function at different values of the parameter a . To achieve this, we estimate the empirical variance with respect to the thickness t , which ranges from 1 to 0.05, corresponding to an

average number of intersection slices ranging from 2 to 40. The discretization step for t is set to 0.001. The empirical variance is computed using 2000 Monte Carlo simulations, and a regression line is fitted to estimate the variance decay rate on a logarithmic scale, using the least squares method within the specific range $20 \leq 1/t \leq 40$.

The point process used in the experiments follows a perturbed model, implemented via independent uniform jitters. In this model, the relative standard deviation of the point increments, with respect to the nominal step t , is fixed at 10%. The estimator $\hat{V}_T(f)$ for $V(f)$ is constructed using

$$T = \left(\left\lceil \frac{2}{t} \right\rceil + 2 \right) t,$$

and the optimal weight vector $\mathbf{w}_{u,s}$ is obtained using Wendland kernels with parameters (3,0), (3,1), (3,2) (see, for example, Zhu (2012, Table 4.1)), rescaled so that condition Eq. (15) holds. These RBF kernels define RKHSs that are norm-equivalent to the standard Sobolev spaces $H^\tau(\mathbb{R}^3)$ with $\tau = 2, 3, 4$, respectively (Zhu, 2012, Proposition 3.3). Restricting them to the circle $S^1 \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ yields RKHSs that are norm-equivalent to $H_{\text{per}}^s([0, T])$ with $s = 1, 2, 3$, respectively. Additionally, to benchmark \hat{V}_T , we also consider the Cavalieri estimator (see Eq. (2)), which, when applied to non-equidistant sampling locations, is referred to as the generalized Cavalieri estimator.

The numerical results can be seen in Fig. 1. We observe that the generalized Cavalieri estimator, as is known for the integer smoothness case (see, e.g., Ziegel *et al.* (2010); Kiderlen and Dorph-Petersen (2017)), exhibits variance inflation, except for $a = 0.25$, where the variance decay is close to the theoretical value of 2.5. For the lower smoothness kernel-based estimator ($s = 1$), the optimal variance ratio is achieved up to approximately $a = 1.75$. In this case, for the two largest values of a , significant variance inflation is also observed, corresponding to the highest smoothness cases of the function. The higher smoothness kernel-based estimators ($s = 2, 3$) perform almost identically, showing a variance decay that is consistently close to the theoretical expectation. In addition, we note that using a kernel-based estimator with overestimated smoothness did not lead to worse results, while using an estimator with underestimated smoothness, although showing some adaptation—as previously observed in other experiments (Bach, 2017; Kanagawa *et al.*, 2020)—does not guarantee optimal decay in all cases.

Fig. 1. Empirical variance (y-axis) of the generalized Cavalieri estimator (top left) and of kernel-based estimators with optimal weights $\mathbf{w}_{u,s}$ for smoothness levels $s = 1, 2, 3$ (top right, bottom left, bottom right), for the test function $f_a(x)$ defined in Eq. (24), whose Fourier transform decays as $O(|\xi|^{-(a+1)})$. Least-squares log-log fits to the empirical variances are shown as lines, and the estimated decay rate (slope) is reported in the legend for each value of a . The x-axis shows the mean number of cuts $1/t$, where the sampling errors tE_i are drawn from a uniform distribution $U(-\varepsilon, \varepsilon)$, with ε chosen so that the relative standard deviation of the perturbed increments is 10%.

CONCLUSIONS

We analyzed the variance of kernel-based quadrature rules with randomly shifted periodic point sets. We derived variance bounds with optimal decay rates that match the integrand's smoothness, even under smoothness misspecification. Our results contribute to the theory of Bayesian quadrature in misspecified settings by treating isotropic smoothness on the d -dimensional torus with randomized point sets, extending related work.

From a more geometric perspective, our results are complementary to asymptotic variance formulas for isotropic uniform systematic sampling with periodic grids in \mathbb{R}^d (Janacek and Jirak, 2019). In that line of work, the leading variance term is asymptotically expressed as a boundary measure of the set (perimeter or surface area) times a grid-dependent constant given by a lattice sum, whereas here it is driven by Fourier/Sobolev smoothness and the geometry of the underlying point sets (fill distance, mesh ratio).

Furthermore, we advance the stereological theory of Cavalieri volume estimation: our kernel-based estimator improves on the generalized Cavalieri estimator for non-equidistant point models (e.g., perturbed grids). Compared with recently proposed Newton–Cotes estimators, our approach accommodates fractional (non-integer) smoothness and extends to higher-dimensional settings, whereas the Newton–Cotes theory currently covers broader point-process classes in one dimension. Preliminary experiments suggest that our kernel-based estimators perform well beyond the settings analyzed here, opening interesting avenues for future work.

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A TWO-STAGE AUTOMATED FRAMEWORK FOR QUANTITATIVE MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF MAST CELL DEGRANULATION IN HISTOPATHOLOGICAL IMAGES BASED ON YOLO AND CNN

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ABSTRACT

Quantitative analysis of mast cell (MC) morphology and degranulation states is crucial for assessing inflammatory responses and therapeutic efficacy in biomedical research. This study presents a novel two-stage deep learning framework for the automated quantitative morphological analysis of MC degranulation states in toluidine blue-stained histological sections. We constructed a specialized dataset of 1,054 rat tissue images. In the detection stage, YOLOv11m achieved superior performance with a mean average precision (mAP@0.5) of 84% for locating MCs amidst complex tissue backgrounds. In the classification stage, using the model we previously acquired to extract pure mast cell images, EfficientNetV2-S attained an accuracy of 89.6% ± 2.1% in discriminating degranulation states through fine-grained morphological analysis. Critically, Class Activation Mapping (CAM) visualization demonstrated that the model's decision logic aligns precisely with pathological features of degranulation—such as membrane rupture and granule dispersal—thereby providing interpretable morphological evidence for automated classification. The proposed framework effectively decouples the tasks of cell localization and state classification, offering a robust, efficient, and morphologically interpretable solution for quantitative image analysis in histopathology. This approach has significant applications in acupuncture mechanism research and can be extended to other fields requiring granular structure analysis.

Keywords: Class Activation Mapping, CNN, Degranulation, Mast Cell, Quantitative Image Analysis, YOLO.

INTRODUCTION

Quantitative analysis of cell morphology in histopathological images is crucial for research in immunology and inflammation. Mast cells (MCs) are of particular interest due to their complex functional states (Austen and Boyce 2001), which are reflected in their morphological dynamics, especially degranulation (Krystel-Whittemore *et al.* 2016). Their granules—intact or released—directly indicate cellular activation and function (Ito *et al.* 2008). In tumors, mast cell density and location affect cancer progression; activated MCs also interact with immune or stromal cells to either modulate immunity or promote tumor growth (Guo *et al.* 2023). In inflammation, MCs serve as key effector cells through degranulation (Yang *et al.* 2023). Their roles in both contexts are closely tied to their activation state and spatial distribution (Vazquez *et al.* 2024; Wang *et al.* 2024; Johnson *et al.* 2017; Gaudenzio *et al.* 2016).

The quantification of MC counts and degranulation rates is a cornerstone of immunology and inflammation research, typically accomplished through microscopic analysis using staining techniques such as toluidine blue, followed by manual cell counting. In virology, influenza triggers mast cell (MC) recruitment to bronchial inflammation sites (Zarnegar *et al.* 2017); their degranulation is a key driver of excessive inflammation and tissue damage in SARS-CoV-2 infection (Cao *et al.* 2024). At injury sites, substance P release recruits MCs via Mrgprb2 (Albert-Bayo *et al.* 2019). While MCs can suppress inflammation in contact hypersensitivity (Reber *et al.* 2017), their degranulation is also targeted to alleviate inflammatory pain (Srebro *et al.* 2023). Pharmacologically, paeoniflorin alleviates urticaria by inhibiting MC degranulation (Wang *et al.* 2025). Notably, acupoints harbor denser MC populations; acupuncture prompts their accumulation and degranulation, releasing mediators

that modulate local inflammation and function (Weber *et al.* 2001). Thus, MC recruitment, accumulation, and degranulation are central processes across these fields.

However, current manual counting methods present several notable drawbacks. First, they require substantial time and effort, often leading to issues such as repeated counting, omissions, or errors due to visual fatigue. Second, the identification of MC degranulation heavily relies on the individual experience of technicians, introducing significant subjectivity into the assessment. To manage the high resource demands of whole-slide analysis, researchers often adopt a field-of-view sampling strategy. Yet, since MCs frequently exhibit heterogeneous distribution within tissues (e.g., forming perivascular clusters), such sampling methods fail to adequately represent the entire tissue, inevitably introducing errors and compromising both data representativeness and statistical power.

Deep learning reliably supports interpretable decision-making in complex biomedical scenarios. Existing research demonstrates its strong capabilities in analyzing pathological images: for instance, a CNN model based on Inception v3 and PCA identifies fecal cellular images with 90.7% accuracy (Du *et al.* 2019). Notably, the YOLO series has advanced considerably in detecting diverse types of cells. One study integrated a FACE algorithm into YOLOv5 to improve yeast cell detection under difficult imaging conditions (Huang *et al.* 2023); another combined YOLO with deep active learning to enhance performance in detecting mitotic cells (Anaam *et al.* 2023). These findings confirm that improved YOLO architectures effectively handle complex biomedical image tasks.

Although deep learning has revolutionized cellular image analysis, current methods primarily detect and count common cell types like blood cells (Sun *et al.* 2025; Shi *et al.* 2024), tumor cells (Zhong *et al.* 2024; Haq *et al.* 2024), and germ cells (Kahveci *et al.* 2023; Wu *et al.* 2024), while automated approaches specifically designed to recognize mast cells and their degranulation states remain notably absent. Furthermore, stereological and morphometric methods (Gual-Vaya 2024), though computationally efficient and highly interpretable, adapt poorly to new devices or scenarios, generalize weakly, and struggle within complex cellular environments. Crucially, both paradigms largely overlook the challenge of automating fine-grained morphological classification to determine functional states—such as degranulation—in specialized cells like mast cells. Consequently, a significant gap exists in the development of automated frameworks dedicated to the morphometry of mast cell degranulation. This highly specialized cell type

and its critical functional states remain excluded from mainstream computational pathology analysis.

We propose a novel two-stage deep learning framework for the quantitative analysis of mast cell degranulation states, integrating high-precision localization with fine-grained morphological classification. The first stage employs YOLO series models to rapidly locate cell regions and perform initial classification, while the second stage constructs dedicated CNN models to achieve detailed morphological classification of degranulation states. Most importantly, we incorporate Class Activation Mapping (CAM) to provide interpretable morphological insights, ensuring that model decisions align with pathological features.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

OVERALL RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

This study proposes a two-stage deep learning framework, as illustrated in Fig.1, which achieves precise identification of MCs and their degranulation states through the synergistic integration of object detection and fine-grained classification. In the first stage, YOLO series models are employed to localize and preliminarily classify MCs within the tissue images. The second stage involves constructing classification models based on transfer learning, utilizing deep neural networks such as ResNet101, ResNet152, ResNeXt-50, and EfficientNetV2-S to discriminate the degranulation states. The framework integrates strategies for data augmentation, class balancing, and model optimization, significantly enhancing detection efficiency and classification robustness.

MAST CELL DATASET DESCRIPTION

MC Detection Dataset

Due to the absence of public standard datasets for mast cell pathology slides, this study leveraged samples from acupuncture interventions at rat Zusanli (ST36) points accumulated by our laboratory and collaborators between 2023-2025. All animal procedures were performed in strict compliance with internationally recognized ethical standards for laboratory animal care and use, and were formally approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC) of Shanghai University of Traditional Chinese Medicine (Approval No. PZSHUTCM2308010011). Rat tissue sections stained with toluidine blue exhibit purple coloration through specific heparin granule-dye binding, enabling direct observation of MC granule morphology and

Fig. 1. Framework for mast cell identification and fine-grained classification. Mast cell regions are localized and cropped via You Only Look Once detection, followed by fine-grained classification of degranulated versus non-degranulated states using a convolutional neural network-based model.

degranulation states (Reber *et al.* 2017; Klatt *et al.* 1983). The staining process yielded 1,054 rat mast cell slide images captured at 400× magnification using an optical microscope (NTB900-FL, Ningbo Yongxin Optical, China) and an inverted research microscope (Eclipse Ti-S; Nikon, Japan), with digital images acquired through an MShot MSX2 camera controlled by MShot Image Analysis System V1.1.6 software.

This dataset was rigorously annotated through a manual process: Researcher A initially labeled all mast cell bounding boxes (for localization only) using LabelImg. Subsequently, Researchers B and C independently and blindly assessed each cell, assigning binary classification labels (0 = non-degranulated, 1 = degranulated). Finally, samples with inconsistent classifications were subjected to a joint review by B and C to determine the final judgment.

The morphological identification criteria for MCs degranulation are primarily based on the following three characteristic changes; the presence of any one indicator qualifies the cell as degranulated: First, cytoplasmic granules penetrate the plasma membrane and distribute in the peripheral region of the cell; Second, the cell margin exhibits an irregular morphology, with a significantly increased perimeter and blurred boundary; Third, toluidine blue staining reveals abnormal vacuolar structures within the cytoplasm exceeding twice the diameter of normal granules. Non-degranulated MCs exhibit a typical morphology with a complete shape and smooth, clearly defined boundaries. Representative figures are shown in Supplementary Material, Fig.S1(left vs. right, ND vs. D).

MC Classification Dataset

Based on the optimal YOLO MC detection model identified during initial training (with an input resolution of 640×640 and a confidence threshold of 0.5), cells were located within the whole-slide images and subsequently cropped to obtain pure-region image samples. The degranulation labels for these cropped images originate directly from the final gold standard dataset described in the “MC Detection Dataset” section—labels that researcher B and C agreed upon after joint review. Their task involved verifying and confirming that each cropped cell image correctly corresponded to its label in the gold standard set, ensuring no image–label mismatch occurred during dataset construction. This quality control process guarantees the reliability of the dataset used to evaluate subsequent classification models.

MAST CELL DETECTION BASED ON YOLO MODELS

This study employs YOLOv5 and YOLOv11 as the foundational detection frameworks. The YOLO series algorithms are renowned for their efficient real-time detection capabilities and balanced accuracy-speed performance, making them suitable for the rapid localization of dense, small targets like mast cells. For YOLOv5, we adopted the officially implemented Ultralytics models YOLOv5n, YOLOv5s, and YOLOv5m; For YOLOv11, we used the models provided in Ultralytics YOLO: YOLOv11n, YOLOv11m, YOLOv11l, and YOLOv11x (code repository: <https://github.com/ultralytics>). Mast cell slice images were divided into training and validation sets in a 7:3 ratio. Input images were uniformly resized to 640×640

pixels, and the training batch size was set to 16. Extended methodological specifications appear in Supplementary Sections S1.1.

CNN-BASED MAST CELL CLASSIFICATION

To balance model depth and computational efficiency, this study selected ResNet-101, ResNet-152, ResNeXt-50, and EfficientNetV2-S as multi-scale feature extractors. All models were trained and evaluated using a rigorous 10-fold cross-validation strategy. During transfer learning, we adopted a layer-wise unfreezing strategy, progressively unlocking convolutional layers combined with adaptive learning rate scheduling. For the binary classification task distinguishing degranulated versus non-degranulated mast cells, a newly constructed classification head with a single output neuron (Sigmoid activation) was fine-tuned. This transfer learning strategy effectively mitigated medical image data scarcity. Extended methodological specifications appear in Supplementary Sections S1.2.

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION STRATEGY

This study employed the confusion matrix, Area Under the Curve (AUC), and mean Average Precision (mAP) as core evaluation metrics. Classification results were visualized via heatmaps generated with the Seaborn library, using color gradients and numerical annotations to illustrate outcome distributions. The confusion matrix summarized model performance by tabulating True Positives (TP), True Negatives (TN), False Positives (FP), and False Negatives (FN). Based on these values, Precision, Recall, Accuracy, and the F1 score were computed to further assess classification efficacy.

Detailed calculation formulas for each metric are provided in the following section:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{(TP + FP)}, \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{(TP + TN)}{(TP + TN + FP + FN)}, \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{(TP + FN)}, \quad (3)$$

$$F1 = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}, \quad (4)$$

Precision (Eq.1) measures the proportion of true degranulated samples among those predicted as

degranulated. Accuracy (Eq.2) evaluates the overall predictive performance by calculating the ratio of correctly predicted samples to the total. Recall (Eq.3) reflects the model's ability to identify actual degranulated samples. The F1-score (Eq.4), as the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, balances both metrics and is particularly informative in class-imbalanced scenarios. AUC defined in Eq.(5):

$$\text{AUC} = \frac{1}{M \cdot N} \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N \left[I\left(f(x_i^+) > f(x_j^-)\right) + 0.5 \cdot I\left(f(x_i^+) = f(x_j^-)\right) \right], \quad (5)$$

measures the model's ability to discriminate between positive (degranulated) and negative (non-degranulated) mast cells. It represents the probability that a randomly chosen positive instance receives a higher prediction score than a negative one across all thresholds. As a threshold-independent metric, AUC robustly evaluates global ranking performance and remains unaffected by class imbalance, which is common in histopathological image analysis. To address the requirements for mast cell localization and confidence estimation, the mean Average Precision (the mAP) metric is introduced as defined in Eq.(6):

$$\text{mAP} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N A \cdot P_i}{N} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \int_0^1 P_i(R_i) dR_i}{N}, \quad (6)$$

where N denotes the number of classes (*binary classification* in this study) and AP_i represents the *Average Precision* for class i . This metric comprehensively quantifies the model's robust recognition capability for degranulation events in mast cell histology images by integrating the precision-recall trade-off across multiple confidence thresholds.

RESULTS

DEFINITIVE GROUND TRUTH ESTABLISHMENT FOR MC DETECTION AND DEGRANULATION ASSESSMENT

Researcher A annotated 1,054 rat mast cell histology images and identified 2,325 mast cells. This study employed a blinded design where two independent researchers (B and C) classified degranulation states across all 2,325 purified mast cell samples. Their consensus outcomes appear in Table 1. The calculated Kappa coefficient ($\kappa = 0.78$, $p < 0.001$) demonstrates statistically significant high inter-observer agreement.

Table 1. Manual Verification Results of Mast Cell Degranulation State Based on MC Detection Dataset

Manual Verification	Degranulated (Positive)	Non-Degranulated (Negative)	Total-B
Degranulated (Positive)	1648	13	1661
Non-Degranulated (Negative)	176	488	664
Total-C	1824	501	2325

Fig. 2. Performance evaluation of mast cell recognition models. (A) Multidimensional performance analysis of mast cell recognition models. All denotes overall performance, N Deg indicates non-degranulated mast cells, and Deg represents degranulated mast cells. (B) Detection results of mast cells and their degranulation states by the YOLOv11m model; Subfigure (B1) visualizes ground truth bounding boxes, while (B2) displays predicted bounding boxes with confidence scores. (C) Confusion matrix for classification of mast cells and degranulation states using the YOLOv11m model.

Both researchers then jointly re-examined discordantly classified mast cells and established the definitive ground truth dataset. Technicians B and C achieved 95.27% and 95.18% classification accuracy respectively (Table S2). Their assessments closely aligned with the ground truth, both exceeding 95% accuracy.

OVERALL ASSESSMENT OF THE MAST CELL DETECTION MODEL

This study used seven model types: YOLOv5n, YOLOv5s, YOLOv5m, YOLOv11n, YOLOv11m, YOLOv11l, and YOLOv11x for mast cell detection training. Fig.2A shows the training results, and Table S1 in the Supplementary Sections provides specific numerical values.

As shown in Fig.2A and Table S1, the YOLOv11m model achieves an mAP50-all score of 0.84, significantly outperforming all YOLOv5 series models. It also attains a Recall-all score of 0.783, demonstrating comprehensive superiority over the YOLOv5 baselines (YOLOv5m: 0.745; YOLOv5s: 0.725; YOLOv5n: 0.753). These results indicate that its architectural optimizations simultaneously enhance both detection accuracy and target sensitivity.

The models show notable differences in recognizing degranulated versus non-degranulated mast cells, with generally better detection of degranulated cells. YOLOv11n achieves the highest recall for degranulated cells (0.865), but has significantly lower recall for non-degranulated cells (0.680), which may limit its generalization in mixed samples. For balanced performance, YOLOv11m is optimal, leading in mAP50 for degranulated cells (0.850) and showing competitive recall for non-degranulated cells (0.785), making it the most robust choice for comprehensive mast cell analysis.

YOLOv11m Model Results

Fig.2B compares the detection results of the YOLOv11m model against ground truth labels, showing accurate localization and classification of mast cell degranulation states based on morphological features. However, the model struggles to distinguish degranulation in dense cell regions with stromal interference, indicating limited robustness under complex histological noise. As shown in the confusion matrix in Figure 2C, the model achieves recall rates of 0.85 and 0.71 for degranulated and non-degranulated mast cells, respectively. Error analysis reveals that 296 and 110 background regions were misclassified as degranulated and non-degranulated cells, far exceeding the number of missed true cells

(64 degranulated and 12 non-degranulated). This indicates two main issues: first, overdiagnosis risk is higher than missed detection due to difficulty in distinguishing degranulated cells from complex stromal structures; second, the recognition capability for non-degranulated cells remains insufficient, limiting practical application. Further analyses are provided in Supplementary Material Fig.S2.

DEGRANULATION STATE CLASSIFICATION MODEL PERFORMANCE

Analysis of the previously trained YOLO model reveals that the optimal YOLOv11m model demonstrates certain errors in detecting degranulation states of mast cells and exhibits noticeable background misidentification. Therefore, we implement a CNN model to specifically identify mast cell degranulation, thus enhancing the overall accuracy of the model.

Fine-Grained Mast Cell Classification Results

To eliminate interference from the tissue microenvironment, this study employed a purified mast cell dataset (containing degranulated and non-degranulated samples), which was extracted using YOLOv11m and rigorously validated through manual verification. Using a transfer learning approach, ImageNet-pretrained ResNet101, ResNet152, ResNeXt-50, and EfficientNetV2-S were selected as backbone models. Feature transfer was facilitated through layer-wise unfreezing and adaptive learning rate scheduling. Evaluation based on key classification metrics revealed significant differences in model performance regarding degranulation state recognition within the transfer learning framework (Zhu *et al.* 2024). The dynamic changes in training loss and validation accuracy throughout the 10-fold cross-validation are provided in Supplementary Material Fig. S3.

Experimental results (Fig.3A) show that the EfficientNetV2-S model achieved the best overall performance in cross-validation. It attained a mean classification accuracy of $89.6\% \pm 2.1\%$, significantly outperforming ResNeXt-50 ($85.0\% \pm 2.0\%$), ResNet101 ($86.0\% \pm 3.0\%$), and ResNet152 ($86.0\% \pm 2.0\%$). EfficientNetV2-S consistently outperformed other models in fine-grained classification, achieving a precision of $86.7\% (\pm 2.9\%)$, a recall of $85.4\% (\pm 3.2\%)$, and an F1-score of $85.9\% (\pm 2.9\%)$. It surpassed the second-best model (ResNet152) by margins of 3.1% in precision, 6.2% in recall, and 5.8% in F1-score. These results demonstrate EfficientNetV2-S effectively captures fine-grained features across mast cell subclasses, providing a robust solution for degranulation classification.

(A) ResNet101 ResNet152 ResNeXt50 EfficientNetV2-S

Fig. 3. Comprehensive Evaluation of Fine-Grained Mast Cell Degrgranulation Classifiers. (A) Overall performance metrics for mast cell degranulation Fine state classification models; (B) Confusion matrix: Optimal ResNet101 classifier; (C) Confusion matrix: Optimal ResNet152 classifier; (D) Confusion matrix: Optimal ResNeXt-50 classifier; (E) Confusion matrix: Optimal EfficientNetV2-S classifier.

The current top-performing model, EfficientNetV2-S, achieves an average accuracy of 89.6% and a best accuracy of 92.7%, approaching the human classification benchmark of 95.27%. This finding demonstrates that lightweight models optimized via compound scaling may outperform complex architectures for fine-grained classification tasks. Its built-in SE (Squeeze-and-Excitation) attention mechanism (Hu *et al.* 2018) enhances the model's focus on degranulation-related features, such as membrane rupture and granule dispersion, by dynamically recalibrating channel-wise feature responses, while effectively suppressing interference from interstitial backgrounds.

Confusion Matrix Analysis

As shown in Fig.3(panels B-E) all four models identify degranulated mast cells more accurately than non-degranulated types due to class imbalance (degranulated samples triple non-degranulated). ResNeXt-50 achieved high sensitivity to degranulated cells but produced a false positive rate of 39.68% - 2.16 times that of EfficientNetV2-S (18.37%) - while both models maintained similar false negative rates (approximately 4.1%). EfficientNetV2-S limited false positives to only 9 cases and demonstrated high classification stability. These results identify EfficientNetV2-S as the optimal model, combining efficiency and balanced performance in complex, noisy medical imaging scenarios with pronounced class imbalance.

Feature Visualization

Employing CAM, we visualize model decision logic by reconstructing feature activation maps into 50×50 resolution space via bilinear interpolation and quantifying activation intensity with Jet colormap. Analysis reveals divergent attention mechanisms across models for mast cell degranulation assessment (Fig.S4).

As shown in Fig.S4, distinct activation patterns were observed across models for non-degranulated samples. ResNet101 exhibited radially expanding activation from the nuclear region, ResNet152 showed synchronized activation at dual cross-membrane interfaces, and ResNeXt-50 displayed pronounced extracellular matrix-oriented activation. In contrast, EfficientNetV2-S consistently localized activations to perinuclear dense areas and membrane edges, effectively minimizing interference from transmembrane noise.

For degranulated samples, all four models concentrate attention on granule dispersal areas, aligning with clinical "granule exocytosis" patterns, yet diverge

in granularity: ResNeXt-50/ResNet models overemphasize discrete granule boundaries and overweight stromal context, while EfficientNetV2-S activates regionally diffuse areas covering both the cell body and dispersed granules—demonstrating strong consistency with manual classification standards. The corresponding CAM visualizations are presented in Fig.4.

DISCUSSION

DETECTION MODEL PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

The YOLOv11 architecture, enhanced with spatial attention and dynamic label assignment (Khanam and Hussain 2024), is well-suited for mast cell detection in histopathological images. In dense tissue regions, YOLOv11m achieved a higher mAP@50 than YOLOv5m (0.84 vs. 0.76) with a comparable parameter count, demonstrating superior architectural efficiency. Its effectiveness has also been supported in complex cellular environments such as dense blood cells (Sazak and Kotan 2025) and overlapping cervical cells (Wu *et al.* 2023). Nevertheless, YOLOv11m still exhibits clear limitations in distinguishing mast cell degranulation states.

These limitations underscore the necessity of our two-stage framework. Specifically, YOLOv11m shows a notable disparity in recall between degranulated and non-degranulated mast cells (0.823 vs. 0.743), reflecting the fundamental challenge detection models face in discriminating subtle inter-class morphological variations. While highly capable in localization, such models struggle with fine-grained classification that requires distinguishing degranulation patterns from complex background noise. To address this, we introduced a dedicated CNN classifier for detailed image analysis. This two-stage approach leverages YOLO's high-sensitivity candidate detection, followed by CNN-based re-evaluation of each cell's state. As a result, the false positive rate for degranulation recognition decreased from 25.74% to 18.37%, confirming the critical role of the dedicated classification stage in improving the accuracy of mast cell state analysis in histopathological images.

PERFORMANCE DISPARITY ANALYSIS OF CLASSIFICATION MODELS

Performance disparities among the four fine-grained mast cell classifiers arise from inherent architectural differences. ResNet architectures exhibit

Fig. 4. Visualization of CAM using the optimal EfficientNetV2-S framework. (A) Not Degranulation category displays original images, CAM heatmaps, and activation maps for three representative cases. (B) Degranulation category presents corresponding image sets for three samples.

oversensitivity to local textures due to gradient propagation constraints. Studies show that when physical depth (d) far exceeds effective gradient depth (l), residual units degrade into static processors (Wu *et al.* 2019), and uniform scaling amplifies redundancy, emphasizing local noise over semantic context (Lin *et al.* 2023). This leads to: (1) inadequate low-level feature extraction with noise sensitivity, and (2) overreliance on high-level static features, exaggerating local patterns like granule boundaries. While ResNeXt-50 improves local feature reuse via group convolutions, it fails to address core deep network issues. In contrast, EfficientNetV2-S employs compound scaling and dynamic training for efficient feature extraction and noise suppression (Tan and Le 2021), reducing false positives to only 9 cases (Fig.3E)—consistent with Abd El-Aziz *et al.* (2025)'s leukemia classification results. The integrated SE attention mechanism, combined with CAM visualization, further validates the model's biologically relevant decision-making (Fig. 4), helping to bridge the gap between deep learning's 'black box' nature and interpretable morphological analysis.

PRACTICAL APPLICATIONS

This study presents a two-stage deep learning framework with broad pathological applicability. By automating the recognition of mast cell degranulation, the system reduces manual analysis time from hours

to minutes per batch, greatly accelerating quantitative assessment in areas such as infectious disease, tissue damage, inflammation, drug studies, and acupuncture research. Its in situ detection capability without requiring segmentation offers a new paradigm for examining mast cell dynamics within tissue microenvironments and bridges a critical gap in functional cell state identification. The framework supports an AI-assisted workflow that integrates fully automated screening with human-AI collaboration: the YOLO-EfficientNet model conducts panoramic scanning and initial detection of tissue sections, automatically accepts high-confidence degranulation predictions (≥ 0.7), and produces digital pathology reports including spatial coordinates, classification states, and confidence scores. Detections below the confidence threshold trigger expert review, with priority given to verifying "non-degranulated" classifications.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This study has three primary limitations: First, dataset constraints pose challenges to model generalization, though our pipeline demonstrated robust feasibility for the target task. Second, distinct model architectures exhibit significant performance divergence in specific detection scenarios—YOLOv11m excels at detecting degranulated mast cells while YOLOv11l shows superior performance for non-degranulated cells—highlighting the framework's

need for improved adaptability to cellular phenotypic diversity. Furthermore, addressing false positives in complex tissue backgrounds requires refining feature learning mechanisms.

Future work will address these challenges through two key initiatives: First, expanding mast cell data diversity in subsequent experiments while leveraging generative AI (e.g., GANs and DDIM) to synthesize non-degranulated cell samples—creating balanced training sets. Second, deploying the algorithm onto digital pathology scanners to develop clinical modules supporting real-time microscopic imaging analysis, enabling dynamic monitoring of mast cell responses during acupuncture interventions.

CONCLUSIONS

This study presents an interpretable deep learning framework for high-throughput analysis of mast cell degranulation. Using a dedicated dataset of 1,054 annotated images, our two-stage system combines YOLOv11m for efficient cell detection (0.84 mAP@50) and EfficientNetV2-S for fine-grained morphological classification (89.6% mean accuracy and 92.7% peak accuracy). CAM ensures pathological interpretability by highlighting discriminative features. This approach enables robust analysis of cellular dynamics in tissue microenvironments, with applications in acupuncture mechanism research and inflammatory diseases.

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TRIDIMENZIONALNA KARAKTERIZACIJA OBLIKE ERITROCITOV S STEREOLOŠKIMI METODAMI

Lluïsa Gual-Vayà

Eritrociti (RBC) so raznolike morfoloije, ki odražajo njihovo fiziološko ali patološko stanje. Natančna klasifikacija teh oblik je ključna za klinično diagnostiko in hematološke raziskave. Večina obstoječih pristopov temelji na dvodimenzionalnem (2D) slikanju, običajno razmazov krvi, ki pa pogosto popačijo naravno tridimenzionalno (3D) zgradbo eritrocitov; zato lahko takšni pristopi spregledajo diagnostično pomembne 3D informacije o obliki in vodijo v napačno razvrščanje. V tej raziskavi predlagamo novo metodo 3D klasifikacije oblike eritrocitov na podlagi dveh geometrijskih deskriptorjev: sferičnega faktorja oblike (F) in upogibne energije (E). Deskriptorja ocenimo neposredno iz zloženek konfokalnih mikroskopskih slik s stereološkimi tehnikami, brez potrebe po popolni 3D rekonstrukciji. Predlagani stereološki okvir omogoča učinkovite, ponovljive in nepristranske ocene morfoloških značilnosti iz naborov vzporednih ravninskih rezov. Učinkovitost pristopa prikažemo na podatkovnem naboru, ki vključuje standardne eritrocitne tipe SDE (diskocite, stomatocite, sferocite in ehinocite) ter različne abnormalne morfoloije.

Ključne besede: 3D konfokalna mikroskopija; upogibna energija; geometrijsko vzorčenje; integralna geometrija; eritrociti; stereologija.

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VIRTUALNA IMUNOHISTOKEMIJA ZA NAPOVED BIOMARKERJEV RAKA DOJKE IZ H&E SLIK Z UPORABO GENERATIVNE MREŽE

Shuying Wu, and Shiwei Xu

Imunohistokemija (IHC) je v diagnostični patologiji nepogrešljiva, vendar jo pogosto omejujejo stroški, čas in razpoložljivost tkiva. Virtualno IHC barvanje, pri katerem iz standardnih hematoksilin-eozin (H&E) preparatov napovedujemo IHC barvanja, predstavlja obetavno alternativo. V tej raziskavi predstavljamo novo arhitekturo pogojnega generativnega adversarialnega omrežja (cGAN), zasnovano na U-Netu z globinsko ločljivimi konvolucijami, s katerimi povečamo natančnost in učinkovitost virtualnega IHC barvanja, pri tem pa ohranimo visoko kakovost slike. Model smo učili in ovrednotili na podatkovnih zbirkah BCI in MIST ter njegovo učinkovitost primerjali z uveljavljenimi metodami za pretvorbo slike v sliko, vključno z Pix2Pix, CycleGAN in različico U-Neta s standardnimi konvolucijami. Učinkovitost smo ocenili s kvantitativnimi metrikami, kot so razmerje signal-šum (PSNR), indeks strukturne podobnosti (SSIM), srednja absolutna napaka (MAE), koren povprečne kvadratne napake (RMSE) in Frechetova inceptivna razdalja (FID). Rezultati kažejo, da naš model presega primerjane pristope: doseže višje vrednosti PSNR in SSIM, nižje MAE in RMSE ter izrazito zmanjša FID, kar pomeni boljšo kakovost slike in večjo podobnost z referenčnimi IHC slikami. Poleg tega uvedba globinsko ločljivih konvolucij skrajša čas inferenc in zmanjša velikost modela, kar izboljša izvedljivost za klinično uporabo. Ugotovitve kažejo potencial naše metode kot pomembnega koraka na področju virtualnega IHC barvanja, saj prinaša boljšo natančnost, učinkovitost in uporabnost za širšo klinično rabo.

Ključne besede: generativno adversarialno mrežje; H&E; IHC; virtualno barvanje.

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NATANČNOST INVARIATORNEGA OCENJEVALNIKA POVRŠINE ELIPSOIDA

Luis Manuel Cruz-Orive

Obravnavamo triosni elipsoid K s površino S . Izberemo poljubno točko P v notranjosti K ($P \in K^\circ$) ter skozi P generiramo rezno ravnino $L_{32}[P]$, katere normalna smer u je enakomerno naključna na polkrogli S^{2+} . V elipsi prereza $K \cap L_{32}[P]$ naj M in m označujeta dolžini velike oziroma male glavne polosi, p pa razdaljo točke P od središča elipse. Tedaj je $\hat{S} = 2\pi(M^2 + m^2 + p^2)$ nepristranski ocenjevalnik za S . Namen prispevka je izraziti \hat{S} z vidika osmih parametrov: dolžin treh glavnih polosi elipsoida K , treh kartezičnih koordinat točke P ter dveh sferičnih polarnih koordinat (φ, θ) vektorja u . Tako je varianca $\text{Var}(\hat{S})$ podana z dvojnimi določenimi integralom v (φ, θ) , ki ga je mogoče hitro izračunati z razpoložljivo programsko opremo za poljubni K in izbrano točko $P \in K^\circ$.

Ključne besede: eliptični integrali; elipsoidni prerez; cvetna formula; toplotna karta; integralna geometrija; invariator; ravnina vrtenja; točka vrtenja; stereologija; podporna množica.

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PRIMERJAVA MODELOV GLOBOKEGA UČENJA ZA KLASIFIKACIJO GLASOVNIH MOTENJ Z UPORABO FONOVIROGRAM- SKIH SLIK

B Panchami, and S Pravin Kumar

Natančna diagnostika motenj glasilk je zahtevna zaradi subtilnih razlik med patološkimi stanji. Fonovibrogram (PVG), pridobljen iz visokohitrostne videoendoskopije (HSV), zabeleži vzorce vibriranja glotisa v obliki statičnih slik, kar omogoča sistematično analizo. V tej študiji predlagamo PVGNet, hibridni model globokega učenja, ki združuje večskalnno ekstrakcijo značilnosti in pozornost po kanalih ter je posebej zasnovan za klasifikacijo na osnovi PVG. PVGNet smo primerjali z uveljavljenimi modeli (InceptionResNetV2, VGG19, DenseNet169 in X-ViT) pri binarnih, trirazrednih in večrazrednih nalogah. PVGNet je pri vseh nalogah dosledno prekašal primerjane pristope glede natančnosti, F1-ocene in AUC, hkrati pa je zmanjšal število lažno negativnih rezultatov, kar je ključno za zanesljivo diagnostiko. Rezultati potrjujejo diagnostični potencial PVG kot slikovne modalitete ter učinkovitost PVGNet pri avtomatizirani klasifikaciji glasovnih motenj.

Ključne besede: klasifikacija; modeli globokega učenja; funkcionalne glasovne motnje; visokohitrostna videoendoskopija; fonovibrogram; glasovna motnja.

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NAKLJUČNA KVADRATURA S PERIODIČNIMI JEDRI: UPORABA PRI CAVALIERIJEVI OCENI VOLUMNA

Francisco Javier Soto Sánchez

V študiji preučujemo naključne algoritme za nepristransko numerično integracijo d-razsežnih periodičnih funkcij z uporabo kvadraturnih pravil, temelječih na jedrih, pri čemer se posebej osredotočamo na pravila, ki jih inducirajo periodična jedra

radialnih baznih funkcij (RBF). Integracijske točke so bodisi deterministično generirane bodisi lokalno perturbirane in nato naključno premaknjene, s čimer v shemo vnesemo strukturirano naključnost. Analiza temelji na teoriji Hilbertovih prostorov z reprodukcijskim jedrom (RKHS) in Soboljevi interpolaciji. Pokažemo, da tako dobljeni ocenjevalniki dosegajo optimalne stopnje upadanja variance ter učinkovito zajamejo gladkost integranda, tudi kadar je predpostavljena regularnost precejšnja. Delo je motivirano s Cavalierijevo oceno volumna, klasičnim problemom stereologije. Teoretični rezultati okvir posplošijo na višje dimenzije in ponudijo Fourierjevo perspektivo gladkosti, kar omogoča prilagodljivo in matematično utemeljeno alternativo naključni kvadraturi s periodično strukturo.

Ključne besede: Cavalierijeva ocena volumna; kvadratura z jedri; radialne bazne funkcije; Hilbertovi prostori z reprodukcijskim jedrom; stereološke metode.

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DVOSTOPENJSKI AVTOMATIZIRANI OKVIR ZA KVANTITATIVNO MORFOLOŠKO ANALIZO DEGRANULACIJE MASTOCITOV NA HISTOPATOLOŠKIH SLIKAH NA PODLAGI YOLO IN CNN

Enna Chen, Jiadong Li, Xuan Qiao, Liuji Ren, Zouqin Huang, Wei Yao, and Yi Yu

Kvantitativna analiza morfologije mastocitov in njihove stopnje degranulacije je ključna za ocenjevanje vnetnih odzivov in

učinkovitosti terapij v biomedicinskih raziskavah. V tej študiji predstavljamo nov dvostopenjski okvir globokega učenja za avtomatizirano kvantitativno morfološko analizo degranulacije mastocitov na histoloških rezinah, obarvanih s toluidinskim modrilom. Zgradili smo poseben podatkovni nabor 1054 slik tkiv podgan. V fazi detekcije je YOLOv11 dosegel povprečno natančnost (mAP@0,5) 84 % pri lokalizaciji mastocitov v kompleksnem tkivnem ozadju. V fazi klasifikacije je Efficient-NetV2-S – z uporabo predhodno naučenega modela za ekstrakcijo čistih slik mastocitov – dosegel natančnost 89,6 % ± 2,1 % pri razlikovanju stopenj degranulacije na podlagi finoiznate morfološke analize. Vizualizacije z mapiranjem aktivacije razredov (angl. Class Activation Mapping (CAM)) so pokazale, da se logika odločanja modela dobro ujema s patološkimi značilnostmi degranulacije, kot sta ruptura membrane in razpršitev granul, s čimer je mogoče pridobiti razločljive morfološke dokaze za avtomatizirano klasifikacijo. Predlagani okvir učinkovito loči nalogi lokalizacije celic in določanja stanja ter ponuja robustno, učinkovito in morfološko razločljivo rešitev za kvantitativno analizo slik v histopatologiji. Pristop ima pomembne aplikacije pri raziskavah mehanizmov akupunkture, možno pa ga je razširiti tudi na druga področja, kjer je potrebna analiza granularnih struktur.

Ključne besede: mapiranje aktivacije razredov (CAM); CNN; degranulacija; mastocit; kvantitativna analiza slik; YOLO.

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